

A Study of Factors Influencing Teacher Turnover in Private Schools in District Gujrat Pakistan

A Research Thesis in Fulfilment of Requirement for the Award of Doctor of Business
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DECLARATION

I, Salma Nazim, hereby declare that this paper is my original work and has never been presented to any organisation earlier for the degree of doctorate.

Signed:

Date:

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my first baby boy, Abdullah Ahmed, who was born sleeping on 27th January 2018 during the research study and will always be remembered (RIP). The work is also dedicated to my daughter, Alaya Ahmed, born on 25th December 2018 for bringing immense pleasures in my life and for being really joyous and challenging while I was studying and completing my work. I also dedicate my work to my beloved husband, Waqas Ahmed, for all his support in my study; and to my parents, Nazim Hussain and Yasmeen Chaudhry, for their constant encouragement, prayers and best wishes for me to complete my degree.

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at identifying and exploring the factors of teacher turnover in private schools in district Gujrat and to devise a retention framework for policy makers of private schools. Teacher turnover is becoming a serious issue not only in developed countries but also in developing countries like Pakistan. It is expensive as it incurs high costs and leads to poor student performances. The teaching profession in Pakistan has lost its true glory due to the high turnover rate in recent years for many reasons. This wearisome situation prompted to conduct the current research to find out the factors behind this phenomenon.

The study was conducted using a qualitative research design with an open-ended questionnaire survey and interviews as instruments for data collection. This method was adopted due to the exploratory nature of research. Multistage and multiple sampling techniques were used to select the appropriate sample, who were comprised of: existing teachers and former teachers of private schools in district Gujrat. Thematic analysis technique was adopted to manually analyse data using excel spreadsheets and the results are presented in the form of percentage charts and a descriptive story.

The findings show very high percentage of teachers leave private schools before completing five years and, similarly, more than half of private school teachers intend to leave within the first five years. Moreover, notable findings are; reasons to become teachers, importance of workplace components in career decisions and early career teachers. along with some personal factors the study revealed many work-related factors of turnover including, lack of support, heavy workload, poor work conditions, student issues, low salaries and lack of monetary rewards and incentives.

Lastly, recommendations to retain teacher were treated as strategies to improve teacher retention in private schools such as providing better facilities, support and higher work recognition, paying well, reducing workload and increasing job satisfaction.

1 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

This study seeks to recognise why teachers' turnover happen, or what are the factors that can influence the outcomes of turnover in terms of moderating them. For this purpose, two types of characteristics are identified as being the main contributors. Teachers' personal characteristics are quite significant as one of the predictors of turnover. However, elements of school in which teacher is working, such as organizational characteristics, attributes of students and the availability of resources also influence teacher turnover. The evidence from studies suggests that turnover factors are dynamic in nature ranging from personal to professional areas of teachers' career cycle.

Similarly, it has also been noted from earlier studies that the decisions of teachers to leave the profession significantly depend on the work conditions of the school where a teacher is working. However, the nature of such problems can be addressed through policies and initiatives. Although, quite a lot of researches have been applied to investigate the phenomenon and address such issues related to teacher turnover, there is still a need for more nuance theory across teachers' career path according to many authors' argument in this context.

The new estimates from the UNESCO Institute of Statistic (UIS) substantiate the serious requirement of additional teachers in huge number all over the world to achieve the collective educational goals and objectives. According to data from the Schools and Staffing Survey (SASS) and the National Centre for Education Statistics (NCES) the shortage of teachers is continuously rising since 1980s (Ingersoll, 2001). Ingersoll have identified the consistently higher turnover rates in teaching profession compared to all other occupations in the United States and this suggests that maintaining high quality teachers in a classroom is becoming more and more difficult with such high turnover rates.

There are different reasons behind this phenomenon highlighted by different scholars and researchers. Some point out to increased student enrolment as the primary reason whereas some believe that attrition of teachers from profession is the main factor (Ingersoll, 2001). There is a great need of investigation to find out the reoccurrence of the multiple factors behind attrition (Eberhard, Reinhardt-Mondragon, & Stottlemeyer, 2000).

According to research by Kelly (2004), teachers' characteristics play an important role behind their choice of staying or leaving the profession. Similarly, Goldring, Taie, & Riddles (2014) also suggest the importance of teachers' characteristics in their decisions to leave. They also claim that turnover rates vary across schools, districts and states. For example, teachers in rural schools or those with less than 5 years' experience are more likely to quit. According to a research by Ingersoll (2001), 33% of teachers leave at their early stage of profession especially within the first 3 years and 46% leave teaching within first 5 years.

Another research by Ingersoll & Smith (2003) indicates that new teachers who leave profession within their first year are 15% and an additional 15% are movers i.e., they move to another school. Similar results are shown with regards to experience and level of certification. Luekens, Lyter, & Fox (2004) & Aud et al., (2011) have suggested in their studies that teachers experience is key factor in their decision to stay or leave the profession. Their studies also indicate higher rate of turnover among teachers with less experience of teachings and less rates among teachers who have more experience of teaching. Similarly, lower certification level is a great predictor of teachers' decision to leave or stay in the profession. Therefore, it is believed that beginning teacher are more likely to quit the profession as compared to any other group of educators, whereas, teachers who complete their first five years of teachings are more likely to stay in the profession.

Better career opportunities, job satisfaction and good salaries are also found to be vital reasons for about half of teacher to quit (Boe et al., 2008). Typically, teachers are earning 12% less than other careers with similar qualification according to a study conducted by Allegretto et al, (2004). 'The Project on the Next Generation of Teachers' is a recent research conducted by Harvard's School of Education focusing on teachers' choice behind leaving or staying. The

result shows that job satisfaction is a key in making such choice. If the teachers feel successful, they are likely to stay. Johnson (2006) presented the similar thought claiming that administration support and good working environment together make the teachers feel successful, thus, helpful in retaining them. Some believe that success comes with experience which is an ongoing process. As stated in a famous article, "Top Ten Issues to watch in 2007,"

"We can pay now by investing in improving teacher quality . . . or we can pay later in decreased purchasing power, increased costs of remediation and job-training, increased need for social services, higher unemployment rates, and in the inability to attract and retain industry." (2006, p. 1)

Moreover, Loeb, Darling-Hammond, & Luczak (2005) consider the school environment and daily conditions of respective school as an important reason of teachers' turnover. Many researchers have focused primarily on the most important factors such as school environment and daily working conditions (Futernick, 2007; Tye & O'Brien, 2002, Quartz, 2003; Hirsch, 2004, 2005; Harrell, Leavell, & van Tassel, 2004). Low salary has also been considered a primary determinant after working condition in earlier studies. (Liu & Meyer, 2005). The factor has gained much national emphasis. Therefore, many schools started to attract and recruit teachers with good salary packages and extra bonuses. However, these strategies did not seem to retain as much teachers as were anticipated originally.

Such recruitment policies are usually made to attract new teachers because very little number of college graduates are choosing education as a career (Ingersoll, 2001; Johnson & Kardos, 2005; Henke, Chen, & Geis, 2000;). However, these strategies do not hold much value if the teachers continue to leave the profession. According to Hunt & Carroll (2002) & Ingersoll (2003b), the current educational dilemma can be solved by retention strategies.

Retaining quality teachers by identifying and addressing the underlying causes of problem can lead to a positive outcome. This can be achieved by directly reflecting upon teachers' perceptions of daily work experiences. Teachers' perspective upon the attrition problem was first given importance in 2002 in the state of North Carolina (Hirsch, 2004).

According to Kardos (2002), to deal with the problem of teachers' turnover, the emphasis should be focused on the availability of an adequate support to the teachers by understanding their daily experiences. A number of studies suggest that a greater degree of support and assistance to new teachers, especially those in their first year, should be primary focus of school administration along with induction and mentor facilities (Berry et al, 2002; Kardos et al, 2001). For such purpose, there is a need for schools' administration to look beyond the annual pay increments and parking facilities for teachers. Retaining competent staff is challenging but important, as turnover badly affects not only schools but also the students' performances. Clement (2000), claims that hiring the best and brightest is not enough to succeed, there is a need to support them throughout the year.

“We believe that teaching can and should be a lifelong career” (Minarik, Thornton, & Perreault, 2003, p. 234).

Employees are the spirit of any organisation and are considered to be the important resource. The turnover of employees, therefore, is one of the challenging issues facing the organisations all over the world. Teachers' turnover is becoming a serious issue in developed countries like UK and USA as well as in developing countries like Pakistan. The teaching profession in Pakistan has lost its true glory due to the high turnover rate in recent years for many reasons. Moreover, teachers who are already in service also take days off or do not perform as efficiently due to high workload or stress related reasons.

According to *Education For all Global Monitoring Report (2015)*, the pupil-teacher ratio (PTR) is very high at 40:1 in Southern and Western parts of Asia (such as, Afghanistan, Bangladesh and Pakistan). This means that there is only one teacher available to accommodate 40 students in a classroom thus compromising the quality of education.

The in-hand research study stipulates information about factors behind teachers' turnover and retention and other significant attributes related to teachers themselves as well as about schools in Pakistani private education sector that may be helpful to update policy makers in their decisions to improve teachers' retention.

Pakistan is situated in the South part of Asia with 184 million populations. Out of this, 62% are in rural whereas 38% are living in urban locations (*Pakistan EFA Review Report, 2015*). Educational statistics of Pakistan still indicate very low numbers although during the last few couple of years some steady improvement has also been observed. The growth of existing schools and establishment of new private and public schools indicate that people of Pakistan are getting more and more aware of the educational needs.

In Pakistan, types of schools are five; public, semi-government, private, religious and NGO assisted community schools. Of these, private schools are attracting more attention due to a better-quality education compared to public schools. There are many challenges faced by Pakistan's education department such as high number of out of school children, low literacy rate and high teachers' turnover rate. However, the attrition rate of teaching staff is higher in the private sector, therefore, the in-hand study only covers the private schools in one of the districts (district Gujrat) of Punjab province, as Punjab is the largest province in Pakistan.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Teachers' attrition is a big issue all over the world. Teaching staff tend to leave their profession before reaching retirement age and in many cases even before completing 5 years of experience. Ingersoll (2001) has named the phenomenon of this speedy turnover as "revolving door".

Over the past decade, the policy makers and education administration are highly concerned about the issue of teacher turnover. This concern is increased due to the reports in media as well as field researches, such as AAE report (2005) & NCTAF (2003), that showed very distressing numbers of teachers fleeing from the profession especially in their early few years of experience (National Commission on Teaching and America's Future [NCTAF], 2003; Alliance for Excellent Education, 2005). Such detailed reports have appeared parallel with other evidences. For example, one evidence indicates that academically more skilled teachers quit at higher rates after only a few years in the profession compared to academically less skilled teachers (Podgursky, et al,2004; Lankford, et al, 2002; Boyd et al, 2005). Another

evidence from a study by Scafidi, et al, (2007) & Hanushek, et al, (2004) indicates that schools with more students from minority and/or schools with low performing students have higher rates of teacher turnover. So, it is of no wonder that the issue of teacher turnover is perceived as having reached crisis levels by many researchers and scholars.

It is of great interest for policy makers to observe the trends in education sector in terms of teachers' decisions to stay in a school over the period of time. This is important to seek teachers' long term stay and reduce turnover rates due to its effects on student achievements. In addition, many researchers have appeared to identify some school characteristics to be key contributor of teacher turnover rates. Such argument has been presented in studies by Guin, (2004) & Hanushek & Rivkin, (2010). Therefore, the variation in teacher turnover rates according to teacher and school characteristics within a particular state or district is important to understand for policymakers.

Teacher turnover is expensive as it leads to poor student performances. The cost of hiring, recruiting, training and replacing is also linked with the problem (Hirsch, 2005). However, Ingersoll (2003a) claimed previously that the concerns with such cost and its consequences are somewhat minimum. There are some latest studies that analyse the costs behind replacing or refilling the gap existing teachers create when they leave. According to Carroll (2007), these costs figures range from over \$7 billion per year nationwide to \$43,000 per teacher.

Although a good amount of valuable information has been provided in prior researches in view of the factors that determine teachers' decisions to depart from the profession altogether or move schools from one school to another (Guarino, et al, 2006; Borman & Dowling, 2008). However, all these previous studies uncover statistically noteworthy differences between the characteristics of teacher and organization, less consideration has been paid in order to measure the underlying factors that could be explored using qualitative methodologies allowing the teachers to express their actual opinions about the phenomenon.

Therefore, the current research focus was to properly analyse as to why the teaching is not being much rewarding career for many people by using a method that would bring the actual opinions of teachers on surface. For this purpose, individual teachers from specific region were surveyed because with this approach not only the reasons were identified but surveying individual in specific region also served as a directing force in retaining teachers and educational developments (Elfers, et al, 2006; Hirsch, 2004, 2005).

1.3 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

1.3.1 Research Significance

Teachers' turnover is the burning issue in developed countries like USA and UK as well as in developing countries like Pakistan. The research study is unique as majority of studies on the topic have been conducted in Western countries and therefore cannot be generalised in Asian countries like Pakistan as the teachers in developing countries have different perspectives with regard to the phenomenon.

1.3.2 Research Gap

The researcher could not locate any previous study related to teachers' turnover in primary, middle and high sections in private schools in Pakistan. However, very few studies have been found on college and university level. Moreover, these studies have been conducted using quantitative methods thus the underlying facts have been neglected. Therefore, the in-hand research aimed at using qualitative methodology to dig deep into the phenomenon targeting main factors behind teachers' turnover in private schools' sector in Pakistan.

1.3.3 Research Context

Similarly, this topic has never been covered by any researcher earlier in District Gujarat's private school sector, so this research is going to contribute in the "body of knowledge" contextually. Additionally, a staff retention framework will be developed for policy makers to retain teachers in this sector contributing to the existing body of knowledge practically.

1.4 PURPOSE & SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The in-hand research study stipulates information about factors behind teachers' turnover and retention and other significant attributes related to teachers themselves as well as about schools in Pakistani private education sector that may be helpful to update policy makers in their decisions to improve teachers' retention.

In this period of growing demands and pressures it is considered to be worthy to investigate the leading factors that govern the continuity or departure of a teacher from the profession. The best and straight method to attain the actual reasons behind this is to directly investigate for the feedback from the teachers about their own individual understandings and how these influences their views about the profession. There is no direct study from this perspective in district Gujrat, Pakistan, especially at school level, consequently, more pragmatic analyses are needed to appropriately endeavour to assess the causes affecting teacher shortages within the specific areas of the Pakistan.

The purpose of the research study was, therefore, to identify and explore the major factors behind teachers' decisions to depart from the private school or from the profession altogether. The study focuses on the private schools in one particular district of Punjab, Pakistan in order to examine each individual teacher from a particular region. In this way, not only these motives can be appropriately identified, but can also help as a directing force in teacher retaining and educational developments. Thus, the current study focuses on such principal studies that measured turnover and retention as two key outcomes of teachers' career decisions.

The typical goal, therefore, is to recognise why teachers' turnover happen, or what are the factors that can influence the outcomes of turnover in terms of moderating them. Such factors to discuss and evaluate the retention strategies include teachers' workplace characteristics such as work conditions, support, students, resources, and salaries and benefits.

1.5 RESEARCH AIMS & OBJECTIVES

1.5.1 Research Question

What are the major factors influencing teachers' turnover in private schools' sector in district Gujrat, Pakistan and how can a successful staff retention framework be developed to help retain teaching staff in this sector?

1.5.2 Research Aim

"To identify the major factors influencing teachers' turnover in private schools' sector in district Gujrat, Pakistan and to develop a successful staff retention framework to help retain teachers in this sector"

1.5.3 Sub Questions

Q1: What is the current scenario of teachers' turnover in the private schools' sector in Pakistan?

Q2: What are the reasons for teachers' turnover in private schools in District Gujrat, Pakistan?

Q3: What are the options for staff retention strategies available to be used in teaching sector in Pakistan?

Q4: How can a successful staff retention framework be developed to help retain teaching staff in this sector in Pakistan?

1.5.4 Research Objectives

1: To evaluate the current scenario of teachers' turnover in private schools' sector in Pakistan?

2: To identify the reasons for teachers' turnover in private schools in District Gujrat, Pakistan?

3: To examine the options for staff retention strategies available to be used teaching sector in Pakistan.

4: To develop a successful staff retention framework to help retain teaching staff in private schools in Pakistan.

1.6 DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS

1.6.1 Teacher Turnover

This is a shared term denoting to teachers departing from their existing schools. Many scholars have defined turnover in their own way. For example, according to Boe (1990), one category of turnover is “transfer” which reflects that teachers move to another teaching position either in the same or a different district. Another category is “exit attrition” that includes those who depart from teaching profession altogether. They retire, stay in homes with their young kids, or select positions in education other than teaching (counselling, administration etc.).

It is believed that “the most troublesome component of turnover is exit attrition, because it represents a reduction in the teaching force, requiring a compensating inflow of replacement teachers” (Boe, Bobbitt, and Cook, 1997). Some researchers often identify both categories as one. Miller, Brownell, & Smith (1999) and Whitener, & Weber (1997) have recognised teacher’ turnover as being the result of both; teachers who moved to other schools or districts as well as those who quit the profession altogether.

Turnover can be both voluntary and involuntary. In a voluntary turnover, an employee resigns from a position either in the pursuit of another better career opportunity, move to another place with spouse or family or might leave the profession due to personal reasons like having children or raising a family. As a result of such turnover, the employer starts to find another potential candidate for the vacant position through the process of new recruitment and selection. Retirement is also a form of voluntary turnover.

Whereas, involuntary turnover typically occurs as a result of employer's decision to terminate an employee due to reasons such as low performance, unnecessary non-attendance and violating the company's regulatory policy or making an offense. Dismissal, reduction in workforce or elimination of a certain position is normally involuntary because the employment relationship is closed due to the circumstantial factors rather than employee's decision to depart.

Teacher turnover in the present study refers to teachers leaving a particular private school in Pakistan before completing 5 years in the same private school.

1.6.2 Teacher Turnover Rate

This is the most projecting expression that signifies to the rate at which teachers depart from the teaching profession.

The skills of teachers who leave, the skills of those being hired and the overall turnover cost together mark an optimal turnover rate of a certain school, however, it is not easy to quantify these factors.

1.6.3 Teacher Migration

An expression that suggests teachers' relocating to other schools or districts, however, continue in the education.

1.6.4 Teacher Attrition

Attrition is a kind of involuntary turnover where the relationship between an employer and employee ends as a result of either a business closing down or due to the low profits the employer decides to cut down company's workforce, a strategy to save cost. The attrition is different from turnover because when attrition occurs, the employer has no immediate plan to fill the vacant positions and leave it empty (Mayhew, R. n.d).

1.6.5 Total Turnover

Total turnover of teachers includes the total number of “leavers” and “movers” from a school, where leavers are teachers who leave the profession altogether and movers are those teachers who move to another school or district but remain in the same profession. As it has been noted by Ingersoll (2001) and many other scholars that turnover includes teachers’ overall departure from education sector and not only a loss of teacher from an individual school or position. Although teacher departing from an individual school or position is a big loss to that specific school, however, it cannot be generalized as total turnover. Nevertheless, in both cases where teachers are leavers or movers, the school is affected in same way because there is an immediate impact on school’s operations when teachers depart to join another profession or another school. This impact could be long term also if school fails to hire a new replacement immediately or near-term. In this case the school must either change its setting or class size to accommodate the loss of a teacher.

1.6.6 Teacher Retention

Retention is a process of keeping something for a long period of time. Teacher retention is a term that demonstrates a procedure to retain teaching staff either in a school or field of education. The researches on retention focus on policies to keep quality teachers stay for a long period of time. A significant importance has been given to the subject for policy makers and other educationalists to retain quality teachers in order to achieve long term educational goals.

Thus, teacher retention in the present study refers to the private school teachers in Pakistan to remain in the same private school for at least 5 years.

1.7 RESEARCH ASSUMPTIONS

Numerous assumptions were also made in relation with the current research study.

1. Each participant would respond honestly and without persuasion.

2. The selected schools for this research investigation were going to serve as the representative for all private school faculty views and opinions in district Gujrat.

3. The survey instrument would be agreed and understood. Such tools would appropriately address all of the existing matters affecting teacher turnover.

1.8 LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

The current study has faced the following limitations and the author had tried to resolve as many as possible.

1. The fact that schools' administration and principals were contacted and made in-charge of distributing the surveys among teaching staff, the possibility of administrators' influence over the responses cannot be ignored. The responses, therefore, may not be genuine expression of the true opinions of teachers. The fear or influence of administration on the way the existing teachers responded to the questions was a limitation of this study. However, as a preliminary measure, the author put the questionnaires in a box to be placed in the staffroom and advise them to return the filled surveys back in the box and not to the administration or principal's office.

2. As the research was limited to one specific district in Pakistan, this may not represent the collective nationwide opinion of the teachers.

3. The research had only taken into account the perspectives of private schools and, is therefore limited to one type of education sector in Pakistan.

1.9 STRUCTURE OF THE STUDY

The structure of this investigative study consists of six chapters.

- **Chapter I**

Chapter I includes the overview and background of the research study focusing on the main purpose behind conducting this valuable research. The section highlights the issue of teachers' turnover in general, specifically focusing on the reasons of turnover and how teachers can be retained in education section. This leads the debate further in context of Pakistani education system and how the problem of teacher turnover is becoming serious day by day. A statement of the problem follows shedding the light on turnover issue with regards to its impact on schools, bringing it into notice with details. The chapter also highlights the justification of study as to why the researcher finds the topic important and worthy of a research reflecting on the purpose and implication of the research. The research aims, and questions are also part of this chapter. Key terms related to teacher turnover are defined in simple words for the readers to understand well. Lastly, the chapter draws attention towards some of the limitations as well as assumptions of the research study.

- **Chapter II**

Chapter II sheds light on an inclusive review of the literature and pragmatic research associated with teacher turnover and/or retention. Several scholarly reports have been incorporated in this chapter to examine the main topic and its ingredients. The chapter starts with a general background keeping the focal point of teacher turnover in view thus highlighting the global importance been given to the topic. The study then specifically draws readers' attention towards the problem making it the most interesting part of discussion and bringing it towards the specific research context of Pakistani education system.

An extensive literature has been included in this chapter to understand the factors of turnover and retention examined in previous studies. These studies suggest that there are many important working environment features that predict turnover. Such features are noted by many researchers and most prominently by Ingersoll (2001). They include school characteristics, students' characteristics and teachers' personal characteristics. These are all prone to change over the time and vary across schools and districts.

- **Chapter III**

The research methodology for the under-hand study forms the content of chapter III. The chapter discusses in detail all the available research methodologies taking into account the positive and negative aspects of these available methods thus providing a logical rationale behind choosing a certain research paradigm, design of research study, nature of research, approach, strategy and methods for collecting and analysing the research data. Due to the interpretive paradigm and qualitative research nature, the exploratory design and inductive approach to collect primary data was adopted for the present study. This chapter also portrays the target population, i.e., the teachers in private schools in district Gujrat. The sample includes two types; the existing and departed teachers. Non-probability sampling techniques were used to select the sample for the present study. Thematic content analysis was chosen to analyse the primary data of the research as this is the best suited analysis method for the qualitative study.

- **Chapter IV**

Chapter IV discusses the results from the investigation and analysis of the data gathered. This is helpful in examining the reasons of teachers' turnover and retention in private schools of district Gujrat, Pakistan. This also includes the discussion on some teachers' characteristics and workplace components important to play a part. Teacher characteristics considered for the analysis include gender, age, marital status, academic skills, qualification, subject speciality and years of teaching experience whereas workplace components include working conditions, salary, work recognition and job satisfaction levels of teachers. Similarly, student characteristics (high/low performance, behaviour issues), role of administration, colleagues, and influence of school climate conditions and availability and quality of resources on teachers' career decisions uncovered the key findings. In addition, the recommendations made by sample teachers are treated as available strategies to reduce turnover and increase teacher retention.

- **Chapter V**

This chapter is based on the outcomes of research study leading to an extensive debate and discussion on the subject of teacher turnover and retention. The discussion revolves around

the three main themes, subthemes and sub-sub themes that emerged after a careful thematic analysis of the primary data. A critical evaluation of the main themes and subthemes against the existing literature forms the important part of this chapter. The chapter also informs valuable suggestion and recommendation for the policy makers based on the responses of the current and former teachers to help retain teachers in the profession in order to improve education quality and students' achievements.

- **Chapter VI**

Chapter VI concludes the research study by informing the reader about how far the research objectives have been achieved. This chapter also presents manner in which the research contributed in the body of knowledge on two levels; i.e., theoretical level and practical level contribution. A teacher retention framework is devised by the researcher based on discussion prompted solutions and theoretical framework of Maslow and Herzberg to inform the policy makers in district Gujrat to address the issue of turnover and retain teaching staff into the profession. The framework highlights the key areas that needs attention with regards to the strategies useful to implement to successfully retain teachers in private schools. Lastly, the chapter concludes by presenting the research limitations, implications and future recommendations.

2 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter delineates upon literary and empirical evidence on the significance of teachers' turnover phenomenon with regard to developing countries such as Pakistan. The focus of literature is the issue of teacher turnover and retention factors in private schools in Pakistan. This will also shed light on the factors behind the phenomenon from previous studies mainly conducted in Western countries. Moreover, available strategies for retaining teachers are identified and their applicability on private schools in district Gujrat is addressed. Theoretical framework of teacher turnover factors and conceptual models of Maslow and Herzberg with regards to teachers' job satisfaction and their dissatisfactions are also included in this chapter. The literature review includes researches that highlight the motivations of becoming teachers in first place, role of teachers and problem of teacher shortage by providing an understanding of the issue on one hand, and by providing a comprehensive description on the other hand as to why teachers leave the profession especially in their early years of experience. Available strategies for retaining quality staff is also part of the literature review.

Generally, a workplace of an employee includes many obvious elements. Similarly, the components of teachers' workplace are also very clear however wide-ranging such as salary, school building, facilities, amount of workload and many more. In addition, there are many other elements important of discussion that may not seem much relevant to retaining teachers at first such as training and preparation of teachers before they enter the classroom or allowing them to influence the way they like to work inside and outside the classroom. From a teacher's perspective, all these elements are important and policy makers and school's HR officials cannot focus on one or few elements to improve retention or change teachers' career decisions. For example, increase in salary merely may not work for some teachers, similarly, providing a facility may not work for another.

Moreover, staying in the profession for a new teacher may be dependent on how well she is prepared to teach or the way she has been hired. The decision may also be dependent on her salary scale as if she needs to work somewhere else part time to earn some extra quid or attend some course to enhance her career skills for progressing in the same field. Similarly, using a new curriculum in the classroom may be dependent on the available facilities and equipment and her collaboration with colleagues and administration might depend on the amount of work she has been assigned. These factors also influence whether the students will benefit from teacher's talent and ideas in general. All these elements are interdependent and must be considered worthy after a careful analysis of the problem in specific school or region to make a successful effort in retaining good teaching staff.

The topic of employee's turnover is studied widely and these studies have revealed various factors causing the employees' turnover in an organisation. However, teachers' turnover is becoming a serious issue in developing countries like Pakistan. Teachers are the spirit of educational institutes and are considered to be an important resource. The turnover of teachers, therefore, is one of the challenging issues facing the education sector all over the world.

In conducting the review of existing literature, an analysis has been made to understand the teaching profession broadly. For this purpose, the key features that make the teaching an attractive as well as rewarding career are analysed. Several surveys have been conducted on teachers by many individuals and organisations to uncover the aspects of workplace environment and its influence on the choices, teachers make to enter in or depart from teaching profession over a certain period of time. Likewise, the role of teachers in students' achievement is also important to discuss to understand the issue of teacher turnover.

2.2 BACKGROUND OF TEACHERS' SHORTAGE IN INTERNATIONAL & PAKISTANI EDUCATION SECTOR

2.2.1 Global Scenario on Teachers' Shortage

According to UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS, 2016), in order to accomplish the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4), teachers' shortage gap of almost 69 million will need to be filled by 2030. Some developing countries are in continuous struggle to recruit and retain sufficient teachers to keep up with an outsized and rising number of school population. On World Teachers' Day (5 October 2016), UIS has released a paper setting out the first-ever estimates of how many more teachers are required to make sure and guarantee that every kid is in school and learning what they need to know by 2030. In short, the world has just 14 years to employ 68.8 million teachers in total: out of these 24.4 million teachers are required at primary level and almost twice as many (44.4 million) teachers are needed at secondary school level (Montoya & Pota, 2016).

According to Ingersoll (2004), the problem of teacher turnover is rooted in the way schools operate and treat the teaching profession. In NCTAF's¹ (2014) report, the problem of teacher turnover is 50% higher in schools with high poverty rates compared to affluent schools. Both schools and students are badly affected by these high turnover rates which seriously affects the nation's ability to ensure the access of every student to great teaching and learning opportunities.

¹ NCTF is National Commission on Teaching & America's Future.

2.2.2 South Asian Scenario on Teacher Shortage

According to Education For all Global Monitoring Report (2015), the pupil teacher ratio (PTR) is very high at 40:1 in South and West Asia (Afghanistan, Bangladesh and Pakistan). This means that there is only one teacher available to accommodate 40 students in a classroom thus compromising the quality of education.

Southern Asia is placed on a critical position due to the second largest gap of teachers and is facing serious challenges in terms of congested and overcrowded classrooms with very little facilities in secondary schools' level in particular. However, pupil-teacher ratio (PTR) at primary level stands high at 34:1 whereas 29:1 remains at secondary level (2014 estimates). This PTR is much higher than the overall global ratio where 1 teacher accommodates 18 students (18:1). South Asia needs to fulfil its teachers' gap by recruiting 15 million more teachers until 2030 out of which 11 million are needed only at secondary level according to UIS (2015) paper. Pakistan along with some other developing countries would need more primary school teachers than today by 2030 if current trends continue according to this paper (Montoya & Pota, 2016).

There is an ultimate need to make effective strategies and policies to retain teachers in the profession. The schools in general can retain quality staff by offering them competitive salaries along with supportive administration. This will also help attract new teachers in the profession. Motivation, support and training are also important in improving teachers' willingness to stay in the profession (Montoya & Pota, 2016).

2.2.3 An overview of Rates of Teacher Turnover in Asia

Mancuso (2010) indicated high teacher turnover rates in the Asian region. Though the turnover rates vary from school to school, the rates higher than 22% are considered very high (Mancuso et al., 2010). Data on international school services (2016) show teachers in international schools in Asia stay in any location for 2 to 3 years on average.

There are some member schools in the East Asia region council of schools (EARCOS), that offer international standard programs and curriculum and employ skilled teachers to meet

the needs of local student bodies as well as international students. Although the EARCOS does not maintain statistic data on teacher turnover, few recent accreditation reports established high turnover rates ranging from 20% to 50% annually in some parts of EARCOS region (International School Eastern Seaboard 2016; International Schools Association of Thailand, 2014; International Schools Kaula Lumpur, 2014).

Similarly, the statistical data on some schools surveyed in Near East South Asia (NESA) council of overseas schools revealed that teacher turnover rates have reached 60% with an average turnover rate of 23% (Marcuso et al, 2010). EARCOS and NESA are similar to other parts of Asia in their geographical, political, and cultural diversities.

Moreover, a middle eastern country, Dubai, also reported high turnover rates at 60%, on an average of 30% (Bunnell, 2014). Dubai shares cultural and religious similarities with Pakistan. Thus, high turnover rates in the education sector continue to be a universal problem.

2.2.4 An Overview of Rates of Teacher Turnover in Pakistan

There has been no comprehensive small- or large-scale study on teachers' turnover in Pakistan. Everyone seems to be interested in the state of children enrolment in Pakistan and the state of schools in which they study, but few seem to be interested in the source of learning: our teachers.

There is no statistical data available on both governments recognized private schools and unrecognised private schools. However, limited statistics on teachers exist in the public-school sector. The public-school data, though not specifically on the inflow and outflow of teachers, show the following trends.

There are nearly 1.4 million teachers in Pakistan, both in public and private sectors, according to a survey conducted by Alif Ailaan (2016). The report also shows that 58% of public-school teachers lack professional knowledge and skills.

Moreover, 67% of private school teachers have less than 5 years' experience compared to public school teachers where the majority (62%) have more than 16 years of teaching

experience. This shows that teachers in private tend to leave the profession in the early years of teaching contributing to high turnover rates (Tribune 2016).

Pakistan education statistics 2016-2017, 25th annual publication since 1992-93, shows a declining trend in data on the number of teachers over time. From 2016 to 2017, a decrease of 1.0% and 5.1% in male and female teachers respectively compared to 2015-16 statistic report on primary level schools.

Similarly, at middle-level schools, a slight decrease of 0.9% in males and 1.4% in female teachers have been observed. Contrary to that. A 10% and 25% increase in the number of teachers in 5 years is observed at high and higher school levels respectively.

These trends of decrease in lower levels and an increase in higher levels show that teachers might move from lower levels to higher levels. Teachers' movement, level to level, or school to school, also contributes to the turnover rates at a particular level or school.

Teacher shortage in Pakistani private schools is a result of increased teacher turnover which substantially contributes to an increased number of inexperienced teachers in the field thus intensifying the problem of minimum access to quality education. This corresponds to the situation in the context of Pakistan where years instability has already badly weakened the education system. The achievement of Education for All (EFA) goal is, therefore, has become significantly difficult due to teacher turnover and it is also a barrier in achieving educational quality, equity and efficiency.

A comparative analysis of private and public-school sectors on quality of education conducted by Amjad (2012), shows that both intended and unintended attrition among private school teachers is high compared to the public-school sector. Even though well-educated people are attracted to joining the private education sector in Pakistan, but they are more likely to leave teaching as soon as other job opportunities arise especially in terms of attractive financially rewarding opportunities.

Pritchett and Viarengo (2008) conducted a research study to investigate the variation between the output of private and public schools in countries with diverse cultures. They found that the scale of output of schools vary country to country depending on the functionality of public-school sector. The developed countries such as USA, where the public-school sector is well functioned and efficient there is not much difference between public and private whereas in countries such as Pakistan and India there is a big difference of productivity in two sectors.

A research produced by Khan (n.d) on *Teachers job satisfaction and incentives in Pakistan*, shows that wages play a fundamental role in teachers' job satisfaction and therefore there are less chances of them leave the job. One of her interviewee teachers said,

“I am not at all happy in this profession. It is difficult to teach children all day long with such a low salary package. I can only think of remaining in this profession if I get a lecture ship in some reputable college or university. Since college and university level jobs are honoured and respected in the society”
(Khan, n.d).

According to a study on employee's turnover in private organisations in overseas Pakistan by Khan (2013), retirement benefits and job satisfaction have resulted in positive impact on turnover whereas financial crises have negative impact on turnover. Generally, a very low salary is paid with no job security to the staff in low income private schools, community schools and Deeni Madaris (Khan, n.d).

Thus, the literatures on the previous research studies shows that these studies have been conducted using quantitative methods generating numeric data therefore establishing the relationship of different dependant variables on teacher's turnover. Hence, the underlying facts have been neglected. Therefore, the in-hand research aims at using qualitative methodology to dig deep into the phenomenon bringing main job-related factors behind teacher turnover in private schools' sector in Pakistan.

2.2.5 Pakistani School Education System

This section presents an overview of Pakistani education system to comprehend its structure and main components so that the topic is further elaborated in the context of this region.

According to Article 25-A-Right to Education of Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan (1973), the Government is responsible for providing free and compulsory education to all children of the age 5-16 years. Hence, it is the basic right of all children in Pakistan to get quality education.

However, government's spending on education accounts for only 2% of the country's total GDP in FY 2016-17 according to the most recent data (The World Bank, 2018). As a result, inevitably, unqualified teachers are recruited in the schools that have crumbling infrastructure at the same time. The education system in Pakistan has the following types and levels of schools.

2.2.5.1 Types of Schools in Pakistan

In Pakistan, the main types of schools are four; public, private, religious (Deeni Madaris) and NGO assisted community schools. The private education schools run for profit and have long history in Pakistan. Such schools are not financed by government and are self-financed. The focus of the in-hand research study is private school sector which is attracting much attention as private schools are flourishing rapidly in both rural and urban areas from past few years.

A study has been conducted to provide insight into The Learning and Education Achievements in Punjab Schools (LEAPS) by Andrabi (2007) for the purpose of evaluating the education sector in Pakistan. He used the detailed education statistics and data from Punjab education department and found that low fee private schools in Pakistan are playing a significant role in providing quality education. Generally, an individual runs a private school on profit basis in a rented premise and therefore has very few teachers who are not very well trained. These are completely self-financed and receive no beneficiary support from local government. Their expensed are met with the tuition fee received by students (Andrabi, 2002). However, the

nature of such private schools varies location to location where schools in urban areas show better and effective professional management in terms of accountability compared to schools in rural areas.

Khawaja et.al (2005) stressed that these private schools are appeared in Pakistan as a result of poor education quality in public schools' sector. Khan (n.d) emphasised that the emergence of private schools indicates that the low and middle-income families have now better understanding of value for good quality education.

2.2.5.2 Levels in Pakistani School System

There are five levels in school systems in Pakistan, i.e., pre-primary, primary, middle, secondary and high secondary levels.

- Pre-Primary level starts from the age of 3-5 years
- Primary level is from grade 1 to 5. It has a duration of 5 years. Children of 4-5 years take admission in grade 1.
- Middle level starts from grade 6 to 8 over the period of 3 years.
- Secondary level is from grade 9 to 10. The length of time is 2 years. The Secondary School Certificate (SSC) is issued by the secondary board on passing the secondary exam.
- Higher Secondary level (also known as intermediate) begin with grade 11 to 12 again over 2 years' time period. Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC) is issued by the higher secondary board on passing the higher secondary exam.

2.2.5.3 Teachers' Recruitment/Development Process

There is an increase demand of quality teachers to be recruited and retained in Pakistani education sector due to a rapid expansion of school system not only in government but also in private sector. A lack of transparency in the recruitment process as well as the recruitment of non-qualified teachers is generally reported by many candidates in Pakistan (Halai & Durrani, 2016). The nepotism offsets the merit in the selection process. Similarly, the process

of deployment of teachers in a region of their preference is also influenced by powerful politicians with their vested interests (Bari et al. 2013).

In order to address the issue, a compulsory pass test administered by National Testing System (NTS) was introduced to get the right candidate on merit base. To meet the demand of quality staff, many reforms have been made by the education department including enhanced qualification to enter the profession, teachers' training degree such as B.Ed.² and a pay rise (HEC, 2012).

Teachers are trained and prepared by a network of institutes (MoE 2009; Halai & Durrani, 2016). Following table shows the total institutes for teacher education at public and private levels.

Table 2.1 Teacher education institutions and enrolment in millions

Total Teacher education institutions	Teacher education institutions (public)	Teacher education institutions (private)	Total enrolment	Public sector	Private sector	Male	Female
201	154 (77%)	47 (23%)	0.722 million	0.717 (99%)	0.005 (1%)	0.480 (66%)	0.242 (34%)

Source: Pakistan Education Statistics 2013–14 (NEMIS-AEPAM 2015)

The table above shows quite an imbalance in the number of public and private enrolment which is the result of an imbalance in public and private education institutes (Halai & Durrani, 2016). However, the dominance of political interference, nepotism, ghost teaching and non-

² B.Ed. is bachelor's in education degree compulsory to enter teaching profession at some grades.

transparent processes is required to be address rigorously in order to improve the quality of teaching in Pakistani education sector on both public and private level.

2.2.6 Current Challenges Face Pakistani Education Sector

Pakistan will be the 4th largest country in population in the world behind, China, India and the USA by 2050. The country continues struggling with multiple issues including poverty and national security. This issue of rising population in the country also poses a serious challenge to all organisations in Pakistan, especially to the Ministry of Education for providing quality education to every child. Pupil teacher ratio³ in Pakistan in primary schools was reasonably low at 33:1 in 2000, while maximum at 44:1 in 2015 according to the estimates of UNESCO Institute of Statistics. The country's instability has taken a toll on its education system. The education sector of Pakistan is going through numerous transformations that has resulted in the creation many opportunities as well as challenges for policy makers in this sector.

2.2.6.1 Enrolment of All Children in The Country Aged Under 16

The current research study suggests that there is a big challenge for the government of Pakistan to not only enrol all the children in the country aged below sixteen but also to improve education quality and attain sustainability in this sector after the addition of article 25A to the constitution under 18th Amendment Act 2010 (Amjad, 2012).

³ The student (pupil) to teacher ratio (PTR) in is the total number of students in primary schools divided by the total number of teachers in those schools. Having fewer students per each teacher is generally considered to be better.

According Education Watch (2000), the complexity and range of challenges faced by Pakistani education sector is enormous due to the fact that there are 5.5 million children out of schools. Almost 12 million children are enrolled however half of them are usually dropped out before they complete their education at primary level in public schools. The statistics of illiterate adult populations are also worrisome especially among female population in rural areas of Pakistan.

Alif Ailaan⁴ published a report entitled “*25 Million Broken Promises*” containing a broad picture of Pakistani out of school children (OOSC). The report revealed that 25.02 million children of ages five to sixteen are out of school. It is also revealed in the report that more than half of the country’s out-of-school children live in Punjab (see appendix 6). In addition, there are 70% OOSC who have never been to any school. The worst part is the increasing number of OOSC with rise in education level.

2.2.6.2 Improve Education Quality

Hanushek et al., (2007) presented a paper on the role of education in promoting economic well-being, with a specific emphasis on the role of educational excellence and established a causal relationship between the quality of education and economic well-being. They assert that completing 5 to 9 years of education alone is not necessarily enough for students as it lacks the basic cognitive skill especially in developing countries. The developing countries are facing a severe shortage of both number of schools and quality of education.

⁴ “Alif Ailaan is a campaign launched in 2013 that seeks to put education at the front and centre of public discourse in Pakistan with a goal to get every Pakistani child into school, keep them learning and ensure that they receive a quality education.”

There are many social inequalities in Pakistan that have negative impacts on the process of achieving quality education. For example, in many areas the girls are not allowed to go to school. Similarly, children from poor financial backgrounds and with disabilities are deprived of quality education in many rural areas. The government and education policy makers are struggling to seek improvements so that every child in the Pakistan has access to quality education without social inequalities. The education system in Pakistan need a rapid and thorough transformation in order to enable every child to progress with today's fast changing world. For the purpose to achieve such goals, the government must seek reforms in educational priorities and encourage researches in the field. Policy makers are seeking to improve programming and management systems efficiently, sustainably, and cost-effectively to improve the quality of education in Pakistan.

2.2.6.3 Attain Sustainability

Though Pakistan has made remarkable achievements during the last decade, there are still massively challenging tasks lie ahead in the department of education. Additionally, the insecurity and state of instability due to the terror attacks on schools and teachers have aggravate the situation in the country. Such a condition of instability impact badly on retaining and managing teachers in the education field. Hence, among the key challenges facing the country of Pakistan is attaining sustainability in many aspects such as decreasing poverty, achieving social equalities, sensibly utilising natural resources and successfully tackling the other problems ranging from health to education.

Moreover, due to the lack of financial resources and strong political will and stability the development goals are hard to achieve. However, the most important SDGs can be picked and worked upon then slowly progressing towards the other SDGs, education being the most important SDG. Implementation of actual work on development goals require such an initiative that every rupee spent on each goal can be tracked through a compliant and transparent budget coding system (Sheikh, 2016). Fortunately, the Planning Commission has

commenced to involve planning and development departments (P&DDs)⁵ in the formation of special units or SDG centres.

2.2.6.4 Reduce Teacher Turnover/Increase Retention

Other key challenge facing the Pakistani education department is the high teacher turnover. As pointed out by Heller (2004) *“teachers have one of the highest attrition rates of any profession”* (page. 4). Lencioni (2012) puts forward the five characteristics of a healthy organisation such as; least politics in management, less confusion, great morale of employees, high output and low turnover. Like many other countries whether developed, developing or underdeveloped, teacher turnover is among the obvious threats to Pakistan's national goal of providing quality education at schools.

Dawn News Pakistan reported that the teaching profession in Pakistan has lost its true glory due to the high turnover rate in recent years for many reasons. Moreover, teachers who are already in service also take days off or do not perform as efficiently due to high workload or stress related reasons (Khalid, 2015).

2.3 DEFINITION OF TEACHER TURNOVER

Turnover means quitting the job. When an employee intends to leave the current organisation he is working in, the result is turnover. Teacher turnover in the present study

⁵ “The Planning and Development Department is the principal planning organization at the provincial level in Pakistan. It coordinates and monitors development programs and activities of various departments of the provincial government. The department also prepares an overall Medium-Term Development Framework (MTDF) of developmental activities in the province.”

refers to teachers leaving a particular private school in Pakistan before completing 5 years in the same private school.

In general, many scholars have defined turnover in their own way. For example, Price (1977) gives a very numerical definition that turnover is the ratio one gets when total number of employees who have left the company are divided by the average number of in-service workers in a specific given time period. Whereas Tette and Meyer (1993) have presented a different type of definition by stating that turnover is a conscious choice of an employee to quit and look for alternative profession or companies. The Attitude Behaviour theory of Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) also referred to this description of turnover. Another similar viewpoint is found where Cotton and Tuttle (1986) mentioned that the turnover is the estimated likelihood of an employee's intention to remain in a company. Therefore, the factors that influence the employees' intentions are considered to be significant and should take into account during the development of employee retention framework.

Attrition is another term referred to the process of quitting. Many scholars have defined attrition in their own way. For example, according to Boe (1990), one category of attrition is “transfer” which reflects that teachers move to another district for another teaching position or sometimes merely change the school but remain in the same district. However, on the other hand, the category called the “exit attrition” refer to those teachers who depart from teaching profession altogether. They get retired, staying home with their children, or join other non- teaching posts in education sector such as counselling or administration. According to Boe, Bobbitt, and Cook (1997), “the most troublesome component of turnover is exit attrition, because it represents a reduction in the teaching force, requiring a compensating inflow of replacement teachers.” Therefore, it is highly important to frame such strategies that would help in retaining the teaching staff.

Furthermore, some researchers such as Miller, Brownell, and Smith (1999) and Whitener, and Weber (1997) often identify both categories of transfer and exit attrition as one. This is due to the fact that in both cases, a school faces a loss which then need to be filled with a cost.

2.4 TYPES OF TEACHERS' TURNOVER

There are generally two types of teachers' turnover.

- Teachers' turnover from profession
- Teachers' turnover from school

Teachers in such turnover are categorised as "leavers" and the "movers" from a school. Leavers are teachers who leave the profession altogether and movers are those teachers who move to another school or district but remain in the same profession. As it has been noted by Ingersoll (2001) and many other scholars that turnover includes teachers' overall departure from education sector and not only a loss of teacher from an individual school or position. However, in both cases the school is affected in the same way because there is an immediate impact on schools' operations when teachers depart to join another profession or another school.

2.4.1 Teacher Turnover from Profession (Leavers)

This type of turnover categorises those teachers who leave the teaching profession altogether to join a profession other than teaching. Many scholars including Ingersoll (2001) believe that loss of teacher from an individual school happen when a teacher depart from the teaching profession overall. The high percentage of such loss from profession is a matter of concern for policy makers and both schools and state administration. This raises many doubts on the teaching profession as an attractive and competitive career and also leaves many questions on the efficiency of teachers' training programs and the adequate supply of teachers to meet schools' demands.

The latest researches on the topic of turnover mostly compare the difference between the turnover from teaching profession and turnover from other occupations. Such efforts have been made in an attempt to relieve the concern of high turnover rates in teaching profession. Most of these studies such as those conducted by Boe et al., (2008), Presley (2003), Henke et al., (2001) and Harris & Adams (2007), show the favourable results in this regard. However,

there is one exception where Ingersoll (2001) uncovered a slightly different outcome with higher rates of teacher turnover comparing turnover rates in other occupations.

Ingersoll and Smith (2003) indicated that the reasons of teacher turnover from profession mainly related to an individual's circumstances, such as starting or raising family and health issues. They believe that a considerably large number of early teachers leave due to such personal reasons. Nevertheless, the overall conditions of teaching as a career is important for policy makers as many early teachers who depart from teaching do not intend to leave teaching forever. Some of them return to join back the teaching later. There are not many research studies found that provide the information on the percentage of teachers who return to the profession later, however, one study by Deangelis and Presley (2012) discovered that there is a substantial number of new teachers returning back to the profession later.

Several studies have found differences in the rates of teacher turnover from profession, depending on the characteristics of individual teachers and schools (Guarino et al., 2006, & Borman & Dowling, 2008). The individual teachers' traits include their academic background and subject specialities and expertise. The stronger these traits tend to be, the higher their turnover rate would be. Similarly, school characteristics include the location of school (urban/suburban), students' financial backgrounds (high/low income) and the social background of students (minority/majority). The higher percentage of low income and minority students in a school leads to the higher rates of turnover due to the school's less attractiveness in terms of teaching and learning facilities.

2.4.1.1 Impact of Teachers' Characteristics on Leavers

A teacher's personal characteristics play an important part in their decision to stay in the profession of teaching or leave the profession altogether. There are number of studies that highlight the fact that there are more trends in female teachers to leave the profession based on personal reasons compared to male teachers although in recent times such differences are not very prominent (Stinebrickner, 2002; Theobald & Laine, 2003; Quartz et al., 2008; Imazeki, 2005).

The gender differences of turnover vary from one study to another. For instance, there is a 7 to 12 percent difference according to an old study by Grissmer and Kirby (1992), whereas a 4 percent difference has been reported by relevantly new study by Theobald & Laine (2003). Indeed, age along with gender has also powerful impact on turnover rates. For instance, a young female teacher (generally 30 years old) tend to leave the profession more than a young male teacher according to few old and some new studies (Murnane & Olsen, 1989; Imazeki, 2005; Grissmer & Kirby, 1992).

Similarly, there are mixed rulings about the race/ethnicity of teachers. An older study by Kirby et al., (1999) discovered that White teachers are at greater risk of departure from the profession compared to Latino teachers, whereas a relatively new studies such as those by Feng (2006) and Ingersoll (2004) found no difference in turnover rates generally among White and minority teachers. Theobald & Laine (2003) indicated that White teachers are more likely to leave whereas Imazeki (2005) has suggested greater likelihood of exit among minority teachers.

Similarly, in two other racial categories where White teachers are compared with African American teachers, the findings of research studies are again quite diverse. These two racial categories are considered to be the largest group of teachers in US (Feng, 2009). Moreover, the diversity in the range of turnover rates among highly qualified and average teachers is also noticeable. For instance, Feng (2006) reported higher turnover rates among highly qualified (generally master's degree holder or above) teachers, whereas, Goldhaber et al., (2007) indicated lower rates of turnover among qualified teachers compared to teachers with less advanced degrees.

Another important category in this regard is the level of school, where Smith & Ingersoll (2004) see the difference in turnover rates among higher and elementary school teachers. They found the higher turnover rates among high school teachers compared to elementary schools. However, the findings of different researchers on the category of subject area appear to be generally coherent that show higher rates of turnover among science and special education teachers. Indeed, research outcomes related to teachers' academic skills are most

constant irrespective of the method used to determine teachers' skills. Research studies conducted by Boyd et al., (2005); Goldhaber et al., (2007); Lankford et al., (2002); and Podgursky et al., (2004) show the higher exit trends among teachers with strong academic skills compared to teachers with weaker skills.

2.4.1.2 Impact of School Characteristics on Leavers

Many research studies have identified that teachers' turnover is affected by their own personal characteristics, but the factors related to school characteristics are equally worthy of discussion in this context. For instance, the location or district in which the school is based also play important role in teachers' career decisions. There are various findings on the turnover rate in suburban schools whereas the outcomes of turnover rate in urban schools are quite consistent (Theobald & Laine, 2003). Comparisons of these two levels of schools show a higher leave trend among urban schoolteachers (Feng, 2006; Hanushek et al., 2004).

Similarly, large urban city schools such as schools in New York city suffered from higher turnover rates compared to nearby suburban schools. These differences are highlighted by many scholars in their reports on the issue. Lankford et al., (2002) compared urban schools with suburban schools in a large urban area of New York and found a 10%-point difference of turnover rates, whereas the difference is only 2% point when compared the urban schools with suburban schools in a small urban area in New York. Imazeki (2005) also compared Milwaukee teachers (urban schoolteachers) with Wisconsin teachers (suburban schoolteachers) and discovered 15% higher turnover trends in Milwaukee teachers but when compared with other urban teachers in the same area, there was a 6% lower turnover rate.

It has been noted that significant number of teachers leave the profession due to lower salaries. So, salaries have been found to have this impact on turnover of teachers from profession. Teachers with higher salary packages on average are found to be happy staying in the profession compared to those with lower salaries (Feng, 2009; Goldhaber et al., 2007; Hanushek et al., 2004; Stinebrickner, 2002;). However, it has also been found that new teachers prefer to relocate in another district for a better salary package than to leave the profession altogether.

In addition to school characteristics, the students' traits are also important to discuss in relation to turnover rates. These traits are especially considered important in relation to the beginning teachers who start their career in a low income or minority students' school. There seem to be higher turnover rates among such teachers and schools. The rates tend to be even higher if the students are also low performing, i.e., they show less/low academic progress.

However, Hanushek et al., (2004) and Goldhaber et al., (2007) claim that taking the percentage of minority students into account, the low-income students leave a very little impact in a school. The higher the percentage of minority students is, the higher are the turnover rate as opposed to lower percentage of minority students (Scafidi et al., 2007, Feng, 2009). Similarly, the percentage of minority students affects the exit behaviours of male teachers (Imazeki, 2005) and white teachers (Hanushek et al., 2004). The impact of students' achievements is also very important to consider in this regard. Many studies have been found to show the impact of low and high performing schools on teachers' exit behaviour. The studies conducted by Scafidi et al., (2007) and Boyd et al., (2007), showed higher turnover rate in low performing schools whereas lower turnover rates in high performing schools. This is especially true with highly qualified teachers in low performing schools.

Finally, there have been many research studies conducted to examine the impact of school's climate conditions and resources' availability on teachers' decision to leave the profession. Whether the teachers have supportive administration, or they have choice to take part in decision making, when it comes to teach in a particular style, relationship with colleagues and students all are important to study the exit behaviours of teachers (Kukla-Acevedo, 2009; Johnson & Birkeland, 2003). Working conditions of a school and the support from administration are especially considered to make a huge difference when it comes to reduce turnover rates (Boyd et al., 2009).

2.4.2 Teacher Turnover from Schools (Movers)

The concerns for policy makers and educational bodies are beyond the aggregate discussion presented in the above section. The recent condition of teaching overall is yet to understand in terms of substantial cost and impact of "movers", i.e., the teachers who depart from one

school or district to another school or district. Leavers from profession present one half of the picture while movers from school present another half. Ingersoll (2001) claims an equal loss whether a teacher leaves temporarily or forever or whether a teacher depart from one school to another. Thus, the local administration not only have to deal with the turnover rates from profession but also have to recruit for the vacancy where a teacher leaves for another school or district. In this section, the discussion will focus on the reasons behind teachers' mobility decision to from school to school.

2.4.2.1 Impact of Teachers' Characteristics on Movers

There are several studies that focus on the influence of teachers' personal traits on their decision to leave a school and move to another school. There are two types of moves, intra- and inter-district moves. Some studies find no distinction in these two and the current research also do not focus on distinguishing between these intra and inter district moves. However, the findings of some significant studies in this context are important to consider in an attempt to examine the factors behind these moves.

Many studies such as those conducted by Smith & Ingersoll (2004), Boyd et al., (2005) Theobald & Laine (2003) and Feng (2006) claim a slightly higher trend of moving from one school to another among male teachers and few other scholars find no gender difference in this regard. Similarly, there are mixed results found about the impact of race/ethnicity on moving teachers, where Feng (2006) and Theobald & Laine (2003) reported higher turnover rates from schools among minority teachers, whereas, Imazeki (2005) and Elfers, Plecki, & Knapp (2006) did not report any difference at all.

While evidence regarding the qualification is concerned, a study report by Imazeki (2005) reported higher turnover from schools among young staff, whereas the study found a very little difference in terms of the impact of qualification on such turnover. Almost no difference of turnover between the other subject teachers and special education teachers have been reported in few studies (Ingersoll & Smith, 2004). However, few other studies found higher trend to change school among special education teachers compared to other subject teachers (Theobald & Laine, 2003; Feng, 2006; Imazeki, 2005). The difference of the results of these

studies could be due to fact that perhaps some studies have been conducted during the early years of teaching while the other might have been conducted over a longer period of time.

Studies that examine the influence of teachers' qualification on turnover from school present more mixed results compared to the rate of turnover from profession altogether (Lankford et al., 2002; Feng, 2006; Boyd et al., 2005). The research study conducted by Goldhaber et al., (2007) found that teachers with high qualification are less likely to change to another school and same results have been found about highly qualified teachers' decisions to quit the profession.

2.4.2.2 Impact of School Characteristics on Movers

In terms of influence of schools' characteristics on teachers' mobility decisions from one school to another, there are mixed results found. Boyd et al., (2005) reported higher transfer rates among teachers who work in schools with high percentage of low-income or minority students. In addition, Feng, (2006, 2009) and Goldhaber et al., (2007) also found similar results with regards to the impact of schools with low -income and minority student on teachers' career decisions. On the other hand, Imazeki (2005) found almost no impact of students' characteristics on teachers' movement decisions.

Similarly, White teachers are found highly likely to change schools with high percentage of non-white students (Goldhaber et al., 2007; Hanushek et al., 2004), therefore, it can be rightly said that the differences of turnover among staff in various districts are largely driven by the teachers' characteristics as well as students' characteristics. The higher rates of turnover from schools have also been noted in low-income or low-performing schools in the early years of teaching career.

Moreover, evidence with regards to the influence of working conditions of schools on the movement of teaching staff from one school to another shows similar results as those on the decisions to leave the profession altogether (Boyd et al., 2009; Johnson & Birkeland, 2003; Kukla-Acevedo, 2009). The working conditions include the overall climate in the schools, behaviour of senior faculty, relationship with other staff members and availability of

resources and facilities. Although all of these factors are important to make a working environment healthy, however, there are mixed results found regarding the impact of each on teachers' decisions to change a school. For example, Kukla-Acevedo (2009) identified the behavioural climate of the school as being the biggest contributor in teachers' decisions whereas Boyd et al., (2009) consider that the support from administration have the largest impact on such decisions by teachers especially the beginning teachers who are in the first year of teaching.

Findings regarding the impact of salaries on teachers' decision to change the school show that salaries do not play much role in such decisions, however, the impact of salaries on teachers' decision to quit the profession are higher (Scafidi et al., 2007; Feng, 2006; Imazeki, 2005). An important aspect, however, is highlighted in this regard by Hanushek et al., (2004) who found that salaries play some role on male teachers' decisions to change a school or district. This shows that female teachers might not find it suitable to relocate due to a difference in salary on the basis of their family ties in a particular district.

Evidence suggests a very little or no difference when it comes to study the likelihood of teachers' decisions to change school in urban and suburban areas (Smith & Ingersoll, 2004; Feng, 2006; Hanushek et al., 2004). Nevertheless, comparative studies about inter-and intra-district moves present very interesting results. The teachers in urban schools prefer to stay within the same district while moving to another school whereas suburban schoolteachers are more likely to change the district (Elfers et al., 2006; Imazeki, 2005; Lankford et al., 2002). Better facilities and higher salary packages can be the key factors behind such decisions among suburban schoolteachers.

It is imperative to note that the teachers' personal characteristics and students' characteristics are not constant across schools. There are many research studies that show a substantial difference across different schools among teachers in terms of their background, qualification and skills (Lankford et al., 2002; Clotfelter, et al., 2006; Rueben, & Danenberg, 2000; DeAngelis, et al., 2005). Many researchers' approach to study these variables is doing so one by one to present a better understanding of their influence on teacher turnover.

However, it is also necessary to consider these differences in totality to reach a perspective regarding the effects of these factors on teachers' leave decisions or decisions to change the school and move to another school or district.

2.5 TURNOVER EFFECTS

2.5.1 Turnover Costs

The continuous requirement and demand to recruit and retain high quality staff within a school is not only driving up the teachers' salaries fast but also incurring huge cost in recruitment and retention practices. The voluntary turnover occurs when teachers decide to leave the school prior to retirement. The school systems bear a significance expense due to such a turnover. The Human Capital Benchmarking Report 2016, by SHRM (Society for Human Resource Management) reveals that when an average salaried employee leaves the company, it incurs a cost of 6 to 9 months' salary of that employee.

According to Southern Association of Independent Schools (SAIS),⁶ the average cost per teacher leaver is estimated to be \$7,500 per teacher for public schools. Since the comparable data on independent schools in this regard is not available so the same calculation for non-public schools is taken into account considering the fact that self-financed schools are more selective in faculty recruitment and, therefore, the amount is more likely to be higher. The

⁶ SAIS is a membership organization of over 375 independent K-12 schools, representing over 200,000 students.

teacher turnover in an ordinary SAIS school incur \$54,750 annually which is a huge cost (Kavanagh, 2016).

The study by Texas Centre for Educational Research (2000) found the estimated cost of turnover per teacher is 25% of the total salary and benefits. Carroll, (2007) discovered that the American public schools incurred an estimated cost of 7.3 billion dollars per year for teacher turnover. The turnover cost includes many elements such as separation cost in form of exit interviews, advertising the post, hiring, background checks and lodging costs and training cost for candidates (Kavanagh, 2016). Thus, an early career support in form of induction and training to improve teachers' commitment with the job can be helpful in reducing the high cost of teacher replacement.

2.5.2 Students' Performance

Teacher turnover leads to negative consequences not only for schools but for students' achievements. A report by Alliance for Excellent Education (2014) warns that the objective of having career ready students cannot be fulfilled unless the high rates of teacher turnover are addressed. Teachers with more experience govern the students' academic progress in a positive manner compared to a newly appointed teacher. Therefore, high turnover of experienced teacher leads to distribution problems across schools, consequently, influencing the performance of students. Hence, students' performance will be lower with inexperienced teachers in the school compared to the schools with a high percentage of experienced staff.

The distribution of experienced teachers across school according to their specific qualification and skills is incredibly vital for students' achievements. The same is true across districts as few studies, for instance, discovered severe effects of teacher turnover on poor districts. Similarly, low performing students have adverse effects on teachers' career decisions. Boyd et al., (2005) also revealed more likelihood of highly skilled teachers to leave schools with low performing students.

In high needed school across the states of America, the turnover rates have reached 30% per year undermining the students' achievements and quality of education thus imposing significant financial costs on education sector (see Figure 1).

Figure 2.1: The 74 million¹, November 2017

High turnover of teachers also leads to inequities in their qualifications across schools (Lankford et al., 2002). The qualification here refers to passing a certification exam from a recognised college in the first try. Similar results are found in other studies such as those by Hanushek et al. (2005). Hence, teachers who achieve the targets on student test scores are likely to stay whereas teachers with less student test scores and lower grades on evaluation quit the profession in the first few years of teaching. However, the percentage of leaving teachers may vary across schools and districts.

2.5.3 School Reputation

As discussed earlier that turnover effects are severe both on schools and students. Teacher turnover seriously affects the achievements of student thus the poor performance of students results in a bad reputation of the school in the town. The high turnover rates cause disruption in the morale of existing staff which lead to dissatisfied staff and non-productive work environment. Parents of the students with small classes especially require consistency in teaching staff as the relationship between parents of students with educators is very important to build a positive work climate within the school. thus, evidence suggests that a better understanding of teacher turnover may improve education quality as well as students' achievements consequently leading to a better school reputation.

2.6 TEACHING AS CAREER CHOICE

There have been many philosophies behind people's reasoning to enter teaching profession. Australia's Ministerial Council on Education Employment Training and Youth Affairs (MCEETYA, 2003) had carried out a survey on teachers and revealed that nearly 31% of the teachers loved to work with young students, 22% had an aspiration for teaching, and 11.5% had the positive impact of a role model. An additional 8.6% were attracted to the work conditions of the schools and 8.3% were found to make a good difference in lives of others (Skilbeck & Connell, 2003).

Previous studies have classified the motivational preferences of teachers into three main categories; i.e., intrinsic, altruistic and extrinsic. The intrinsic motivation refers to teachers' inner sense of pleasure and joy to work with young children, altruistic is about imparting knowledge to others whereas the extrinsic motivations are more work-related.

2.6.1 Intrinsic Motivations

According to the Self-Determination Theory (Deci, & Ryan, 1985), the intrinsic rewards are more basic and fundamental influencing teachers' sense of pleasure. Being with their children, enjoying teaching their favourite subject, contributing in students' achievement, developing new skills and exercising influence in their role all are included in intrinsic rewards. Similarly, Lester (1986) also debated that many people are interested in teaching due to personal satisfaction they feel upon seeing their students' accomplishments later in their lives.

Lortie's study (2002) has reported that the primary reason to teaching given by the practicing teachers in their study was the "desire to work with young people". Similarly, staying in touch with one's favourite subject is also a frequent motivation found to influence some teachers as an intrinsic reward. Similarly, according to Tomšik (2016) enjoyment of the subject was given to be one of the dominant motivations to join teaching as a career by first year teacher trainees. Moreover, Clarke, (2009) discovered that in a recent study in Ireland examining the

second-level student teachers' career inspirations, "love of subject" was one of the intrinsic factors that achieved the third highest mean value.

2.6.2 Altruistic Motivation

Altruistic motivation is known as something worthwhile socially that enables someone to make a contribution to the wellbeing of mankind and society in general (Heinz, 2015). Therefore, the desire to teach is meant to be altruistic fundamentally because it signifies an individual's impulse to share what they value by empowering others at the same time.

Moreover, contributing in students' lives and making a difference in the society by imparting intellectual knowledge gives an inner sense of pleasure to the teachers (Reid & Thornton, 2000; Ornstein & Levine 2006). Richardson and Watt (2006) tested how various types of altruistic motivational factors influence the career choice, which they categorise as "social utility values." Accordingly, Australian teachers measured a strong desire to "shape the future of children/adolescents", to "enhance social equity", "to make a social contribution", and "to work with children and adolescents." Thus, a "love of and wanting to help children" is considered to be the most significant motive agreed by student teachers for joining teaching.

2.6.3 Extrinsic Motivations

Unlike intrinsic motivations, the motivational preferences of some to join teaching as career are extrinsic. The evidence suggests that some people join teaching profession because of the job security it provides (Webster et al., 2004; Kyriacou & Coulthard, 2000;). Similarly, Reid & Thornton, (2000) included other extrinsic motivations that incorporate some perceived benefits come along with the profession such as promotions, facilities, and length of holidays.

The satisfaction one derives from the external work components are major extrinsic reason behind some people choosing teaching profession (Hunt, 2002). Having teaching resources and material; manageable class sizes, realistic workloads, appreciation and recognition of good performance, growth and progression opportunities and better salaries are among those extrinsic components of job satisfaction that most commonly influence teachers career

choices as identified by Skilbeck & Connell, (2003). When these are present, the implication is that people will attract to the teaching career and remain within the profession.

Moreover, teachers' personal experiences with other teachers, their family background and convenience of alternative work aspects are some important factors to consider when studying attraction to teaching career. For example, Hutchings (2002) and Lewis (2002) pointed out that the negative perceptions of working with children can discourage men to accepting primary teaching profession.

2.6.4 Religious and Cultural Influences specific to an aspect of Islam

Apart from the intrinsic, altruistic and extrinsic rewards, there are also some religious and cultural inspirations that drive the career motivations of teachers. A recent cross-cultural, qualitative research was done to compare the career motivations of final-year Canadian and Omani pre-service teachers. The study highlights that Omani teachers are highly influenced by the socio-cultural impacts when they choose teaching as their career. The participating student teachers from Oman highly rated the culturally specific religious and gender roles in their qualitative survey responses such as, "teaching is the profession of the prophets", "teaching is the best job for women". Thus, the socio-cultural and religious aspects have strong influences on choices of career in Oman (Klassen et al., 2011).

Teaching is a highly respected profession in all religions and especially in an Islamic background and history, teaching is considered a profession of the prophets. This has a huge influence on teachers' career choices in Islamic countries. For instance, A quantitative research was carried out on 273 MBA students in Saudi Arabia to investigate the personal and institutional influences on their career choices (Albugamy, 2014). The findings show that the personal needs of Saudi MBA students are not solely the determinants of their career choices. The wider aspects of cultural and religious factors are highly influential in choosing a profession. Islamic religion is found to be one of the significant predictors of career choices of Saudi MBA students. Thus, in a non-western context such as Saudi Arabia, the social, cultural, and religious aspects are highly influential in career choices and the same is found to be true in the context of Pakistan.

The culture in Pakistan strictly adheres to Islamic principles and teachings. This Islamic culture is based on the Quran (the holy book revealed upon Prophet Muhammad PBUH), hadiths (sayings), and sunnah (practice) of Prophet Muhammad PBUH. Teachers in Pakistani culture have a religious specific role. Since the teaching profession has religious importance, females from the more conservative families in Pakistan are more likely to choose this profession as their first choice of career.

A qualitative study was conducted on 14 English language teachers in Pakistan to investigate the factors that motivate teachers to join teaching. The findings showed 'feminism' as a prominent theme in the teaching profession. This implies that females in Pakistan consider teaching as the most suitable profession for them and the culture in Pakistan also supports females to choose teaching as their career. They feel safe and secure in this profession as they can perform their duties in segregation compared to all other professions where mostly male and females are co-workers. They also mentioned that they were motivated to join teaching since teaching is a prophetic profession (Kamran & Shahbaz, 2018).

There are believed to be 124,000 prophets in Islam, starting from Adam to last prophet Muhammad (PBUH) and they were all teachers in one way or the other as their roles were to teach and guide humanity to submit to one God, Almighty Allah and seek righteousness. Some were given holy books to pass on to humankind. Islam speaks of the prophets as being the greatest human beings of all kind, thus teaching is also considered to be the greatest profession in this context.

Another reason, teaching is considered to be the noblest of professions in Pakistani society because Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) introduced himself as a teacher. Allah says in Quran, "We have sent among you a messenger of your own, rehearsing to you Our verses, and purifying you, and instructing you in scripture and wisdom, and in new knowledge." (The Quran, 2:151). Islam stress so much on the importance of acquiring knowledge and that is why the honour of the person who imparts this knowledge is high. Thus, a teacher is the most honoured and dignified person in Islam.

The importance of teaching-learning and knowledge can also be observed in the fact that the very first verse of the Quran started with the word *"Iqra"* meaning "Read". thus, the first teacher in the universe is our creator.

"Read! in the name of your Lord, who has created. He has created man from a clot. Read! And your lord is the Most Generous, who has taught by the pen (the first person to write was Prophet Idrees (Enoch). Has taught man that which he knew not" (The Quran, 96:1-5).

Moreover, the word *"Allama"* literally meaning "he taught" occurs 41 times in the Quran. Hence, the Quran emphasises on teaching, learning, knowledge, and exploring which of course is impossible without a teacher and a learner. Prophets were appointed as teachers to guide the principle of right and wrong, and teachers are said to be the inheritors of prophets. Islam has granted high status and many rights to the teachers. It instructs believers to respect the teacher. Teacher in Islam is considered to be a spiritual father as he provides spiritual nourishment to his learners and improve their learning and behaviour.

The Quran highlights the importance of teachers enormously. There are many verses in the Quran where God has pointed towards the high status of teachers and their rights.

"Are those who have knowledge equal to those who do not have knowledge" (The Quran, 39:9).

"Allah elevates to high positions those amongst you who are faithful and those who have acquired knowledge" (The Quran, 58:11).

Moreover, the hadiths (sayings of the Prophet Muhammad PBUH) also explains the superiority of teachers over common people. For instance,

"The superiority of a scholar over a worshiper is like the superiority of the moon over the rest of the celestial bodies. Indeed, the scholars are the heirs of the prophets. And the prophets do not leave behind dinars or dirham. The only legacy of the scholar is knowledge, so whoever takes from it, then indeed he has taken the ablest share" (Jami at-Tirmidhi, 2682).

Similarly, “One knowledgeable man is more formidable against Sheitan (devil) than one thousand devoted worshippers” (Sunan ibn-e-Majah, Vol.1 Book 1, Hadith 222).

In addition to that, Prophet Muhammad PBUH has also explained the high reward that a teacher gets in the hands of his Lord for imparting knowledge to others.

“The scholar and the seeker will share the reward” (Sunan ibn-e-Majah, Vol.1 Book 1, Hadith 228).

“Whoever teaches some knowledge, will have the reward of the one who acts upon it, without that detracting from his reward in the slightest” (Sunan ibn-e-Majah, Vol.1 Book 1, Hadith 240).

“The best charity is when a Muslim man gains knowledge, then he teaches it to others” (Sunan ibn-e-Majah, Vol.1 Book 1, Hadith 243).

Thus, the verses from the Quran and hadiths of Prophet Muhammad explain the superiority of a teacher over an ordinary person as well as high rewards for teachers to teach and guide the students. Therefore, Islam instructs the learners not to raise their voices towards teachers, listen well to them, respect them, and attend with devotion. Hence, teaching is the noblest of the profession in Islam as well as in Pakistani culture.

2.7 FACTORS OF TEACHERS' TURNOVER

Researchers argue that the problem of workers turnover have obtained significant attention from almost all human resource managers and organizational theoreticians (Allen, 2010). Teacher turnover is no different. A number of factors contribute in teachers' decisions to quit teaching profession altogether or transfer to some other schools/districts. Some scholars consider individual factors to be important while other consider the work-related factors are of most importance. Some scholars have discovered teachers with higher academic scores and greater academic ability get better job opportunities outside of teaching, and such teachers leave teaching profession sooner compared to the teachers with lower test scores

(Boyd et al., 2005; Feng, 2006). Similarly, salary plays important role in teachers' turnover for some scholars while workload is the biggest factors behind such phenomenon for others. Along with these, personal characteristics of a teacher such as age, gender, experience, marital status and qualification are given huge importance in discussing the turnover factors.

Overall, the reasons for teachers leaving the job are of two types; personal and job-related. Generally, on personal level the reasons are related to the experiences of an individual whereas job-related reasons are seen in the context of school (Beltman et al., 2011).

2.7.1 Theoretical Models of Teacher Turnover Factors

The study of teacher turnover factors has a long history that generated different theories in terms of the categorising these factors. Following is a brief description of three conceptual theories that underpin the foundation for the present study on teacher turnover.

Billingsley et al. (1993) conducted an open-ended survey and found various factors behind teachers' leave behaviour. They categorised the factors on the basis of teachers' career decisions that are affected by various factors. Such factors can be external, personal and/or employment related factors.

Figure 2.2: Turnover factors of Billingsley et al. (1993)

- I. **External Factors:** are mostly related with economic situation, social issues, and institutional factors. Such factors indirectly affect teachers' career decisions as they act externally on teachers and districts.

- II. **Personal Factors:** such factors are usually concerned with teachers' individual circumstances outside work related issues that may influence their career decisions directly or indirectly. These comprises of their life priorities and surroundings. However, he claims that "whether teachers actually leave depends on a host of personal, social, and economic factors" (p. 147).
- III. **Employment/ work related Factors:** such factors usually focus on professional qualifications, working conditions, incentives and remunerations, and commitments with the job role, profession and school and district. Billingsley (1993) hypothesizes that when "professional qualifications and work conditions are not as favourable, teachers are likely to experience fewer rewards and, thus, reduced commitment".

On the other hand, Brownell & Smith (1993) presented a modified model of Bronfenbrenner's that features four organised, correlated and interdependent systems. These systems are considered important in relation to teachers' career decisions.

MICROSYSTEM	MESOSYSTEM
EXO-SYSTEM	MACROSYSTEM

Figure 2.3: Turnover factors of Brownell & Smith (1993)

- I. The microsystem includes the outcomes of interactions between teacher and student' personal characteristics.
- II. The mesosystem incorporates the teacher's relationship with their administration and colleagues showing how much support is available to teacher from these variables.

- III. The exo-system consists of formal and informal social structures. This refers to the nature of district in which the teacher is working. For instance, urban or suburban districts.
- IV. The macro-system takes into account the economic conditions influencing teachers' career decisions as well as the ideologies and beliefs that are prominent in the society.

Moreover, Karsenti & Collin (2013) have identified and divided different factors of teachers' turnover into four categories as follows:

Figure 2.4: Turnover factors of Karsenti & Collin (2013)

- I. **Task Related Factors:** these factors are related to everyday routine and are very demanding and time-consuming in teaching profession such as classroom management difficulties, workload, disciplinary problems, autocratic administration and unnecessary tasks.
- II. **Individual Factors:** such factors deal with the personal characteristics of teachers such as their emotional and psychological needs that influence their decisions.
- III. **Social Environment Factors:** these factors include the teachers' relationships with administration, colleague and with difficult students. Working conditions are also part

of these factors and teachers' decisions to quit the profession are strongly influenced by them.

IV. Socioeconomic Conditions: include low salaries for example.

This is significant to note that above mentioned factors are closely associated with each other and influence each other strongly. For instance, number of years of teaching experience (individual factor) is related with working conditions of school (social economic factor). The better the working conditions are, the more are the number of years of teaching. Thus, these factors are interdependent and teacher turnover is affected by a set of factors rather than a single factor (Karsenti, T. & Collin, S. 2013).

2.7.2 Types of Teacher Turnover Factors

Based on the above-mentioned theoretical categories, there are generally two main types of turnover factors. Personal/individual factors and work/job-related factors.

2.7.2.1 *Personal/Individual Factors*

On personal level, the research studies on turnover suggest many characteristics of teachers as important factors that affect teacher's turnover. These characteristics are classified differently by different researchers such as; Stinebrickner (2002) and Theobald & Laine, (2003) give importance to gender; Imazeki (2005) considers race as important factor; whereas Boyd et al., (2005); Goldhaber et al., (2007); Lankford et al., (2002); and Podgursky et al., (2004) relate turnover decisions with educational achievements.

Furthermore, there is a strong effect of teachers' characteristics on the achievements of students. Hence, the more dynamic the teacher characteristics are, the more variance in the achievement of students is observed. However, there is still disagreements on which characteristics of teachers influence student learning outcomes most (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Hattie, 2009). Moreover, teachers' personal characteristics such as verbal intelligence

and self-efficacy are also considered to be vital for teachers' success by few other researchers (Scheerens, 2016).

Ondrich J. et al., (2008) find that teachers' characteristics govern their decision to transfer or quit in many cases. Such characteristics include their qualifications, certification, subject speciality and the grade level they are teaching at. In addition, the students' characteristics play another role here as they found less likelihood of leaving the profession among female teachers who are working in schools with privileged students.

Similarly, a study by Muller et al., (2016) conducted on teachers' retention, mobility and attrition presented a report where teachers' individual traits such as age, experience and the degree earned are of great importance in their decisions to stay, move or leave a school.

a) Age

Age is considered to be a dominant factor affecting teachers quit or transfer decisions. There is a higher turnover rate found among teachers who begin their teaching career at or after age 30. For example, a report released by the National Foundation for Educational Research (NFER, 2003) revealed that older teachers leave the profession before retirement due to stress of workload.

Similarly, Young teachers, often 30 years old, are more likely to leave the school compared to teachers with more age (Feng, 2006). According to Muller et al., (2016) teachers with age 31 or younger have high turnover rate whereas teachers who aged above 31 are more likely to stay in the same school. Moreover, the likelihood of changing from one school to another is higher in teachers who are 31 years old or younger compares to teachers with age of 40 or above.

*“Attrition is high for young or new teachers and lower for older or more experienced teachers until they reach ages at which retirement is feasible”
(Guarino, n.d).*

In addition, age is correlated with gender of teachers. As explained by Imazeki (2004), an older man might have strong ties with people in the community so there are less chances of him to change the district or profession. However, when a man begins teaching after the age of 30, it is more likely that he has attained experience in any other profession already so, upon being dissatisfied with teaching, he is more likely to look for opportunities outside teaching profession. On the other hand, age factor affects women differently, as they might have entered the profession late due to family ties, such as bearing and raising children rather than having acquired experience in any other profession. Therefore, opportunities for such women outside teaching career are minimal resulting in less likelihood of their decisions to quit.

b) Gender

There are a number of studies on how the gender factor is associated with teacher turnover. Although recent studies provide less evidence of difference between exit behaviours of male and female teachers (Imazeki, 2005; Quartz et al., 2008; Stinebrickner, 2002; Theobald & Laine, 2003;), there are yet some old studies that indicate high turnover trends among female teachers compared to male teachers. For instance, Grissmer and Kirby (1992) reported 7 to 12% gender difference, whereas on the other hand, a relevantly new study by Theobald and Laine (2003) found only 4% gender difference in turnover.

Few studies also discovered the gender and age as a combined factor affecting teacher turnover. For example, Imazeki (2004) claim that young male teachers are less likely to leave teaching whereas young female teachers are highly likely to leave teaching profession. Hence, the reason of young female teachers leaving the profession might be more of personal reasons than professional.

c) Race/Ethnicity

There are more mixed outcomes found with regards to race/ethnicity as being the factor behind teacher turnover. Comparative studies of White teachers with minority teachers generally show diverse results. For example, the study by Imazeki (2005) presents high turnover rates among minority teachers, whereas Feng (2006) and Ingersoll (2004)

demonstrate almost no difference in leave rates between White and minority teachers. On the other hand, Ingersoll (2001) found greater likelihood of exit among White teachers compared to Latino teachers. Almost similar findings can be related with regard to largest group of teachers in America comprised of White versus African American teachers. However, unlike these studies, Boyd et al., (2011) presented opposite results with minority teachers at a higher risk of turnover.

d) Marital status

Another study reveals that the marital status and fertility behaviour are explanatory variables influencing the individual's decision to determine how long he stays in the profession. Imazeki (2004) also found that individual's marriage plays a vital role in his decision to leave especially females leave in order to have children or to relocate with their spouses. Same results are found in Stinebrickner's study (2002) that personal or family factors affect females' decision of leaving the job more than males.

e) Qualification/Experience

The role of teachers is held very important in the achievements of students and therefore its relevance with the issue of teacher turnover cannot be overlooked. A full grade level of achievement of a student in one school year is translated by the capability of teacher. The difference between very capable and less capable teachers determine the difference between high achievers and low achievers. Previous studies suggest a long term and permanent effect a teacher's capability can make on a student's achievement.

According to Rivkin, Hanushek, & Kain, (2005) such long-term effects are beyond the potential short-term effects. They have demonstrated their point in detail by indicating in their study the impacts of third grade teacher's capability on the performance of fifth grade students. In addition to this, the change of teachers and the sequence in which teachers are changed for students of a particular class also contribute in the academic outcomes of students who were high achievers initially.

Several studies present data on teachers' qualification influencing their career decisions. It is revealed by many researchers in their studies that a master's degree holding teachers are more likely to stay in the profession (at a higher rate of 87.8%) compared to the bachelor's degree holders and teachers with professional level qualification.

With regard to the impact of teaching experience on teacher turnover, it is observed that teachers who have a 3 years or less experience or with more than twenty years' experience are highly likely to leave the teaching whereas teachers with experience between 4 to 19 years tend to stay in the profession. Similarly, teachers with fewer years of experience are found with greater probability to change a school or district (Goldhaber et al., 2007; Boyd et al., 2005).

f) Subject specialty

Moreover, teachers' specific attributes such as the subject speciality and academic ability also affects the individuals to make decisions to quit a profession. This is mostly due to the fact that subject specialist (mostly maths and science) may have more opportunities in relevant to other sectors (Podgursky et al, 2004; Smithers and Robinson, 2004). However, it is assumed that teachers with math and science qualification are not very likely to join teaching profession as they are highly in demand in other professions. So, if by any chance they become teachers, they tend to leave the profession as soon as they find their desired job because they have more opportunities due to their competitive advantage. This is same with special education and therefore retention of such teachers is quite challenging.

g) Regional attachments

Many studies reveal the importance of regional attachments in teachers' career decisions. Generally, teachers tend to teach near their hometown especially near where they attended high school or college. The findings of a study in *Pennsylvania* by Strauss et al. (2000) shows that on average, 40% teachers are more likely to continue teaching in the same district where they had earlier attended the high school. Similarly, quite high percentage (85%) teachers in New York State are found interested in teaching within 40 miles of their hometown (Boyd et

al., 2005a). Therefore, it is important to consider the role of teachers' location with regards to their district choices in which they want to teach. The nearer the institute is, the higher the likelihood of teachers' staying decisions.

2.7.2.2 Employment or Work-Related Factors

Contrary to the personal reasons, it is argued that financial and non-financial school characteristics are significant factors to determine how long a person remains in teaching (Stinebrickner, 2002).

In a study on teachers nationwide, Ingersoll (2001) states that:

“The data show that, in particular, low salaries, inadequate support from the school administration, student discipline problems, and limited faculty input into school decision-making all contribute to higher rates of turnover, after controlling for the characteristics of both teachers and schools”. (p. 7)

work environments play an important role in teachers' career decisions in terms of their job satisfaction. There are many research studies that imply range of analytical approaches to find out the relationship between work environment and turnover rates. Work environment is comprised of various variables that, either single or combined, contribute towards teachers' attrition and retention. These variables include all the school characteristics such as school's working conditions, salary, excessive paperwork, inadequate support from administration & colleagues, lack of opportunities to develop and progress, lack of training and mentoring facilities, availability and quality of resources and student-related issues.

These variables are discussed in detail below.

a) School Characteristics/Climate

The research study conducted by Ingersoll (2001) show that higher rate of turnover is result of poor school characteristics such as insufficient support from the school administration, discipline issues among students, lack of participation in decision making processes, job dissatisfaction and in many cases low salaries. Ingersoll (2001) argued that such

organizational factors cause teachers to leave the profession. Allensworth et al., (2009) also reported in their study that school climate conditions have a significant impact on teachers' turnover rates.

Teacher's mobility decisions are largely affected by working environment of the schools in which they are teaching. Ondrich et al, (2008) found that in order to raise teacher retention rates in poor urban districts with more disadvantaged students compared to levels in other schools in the district is highly unlikely. For example, schools with more disadvantaged students face teachers' mobility at higher rate compared to schools with relatively more advantage students. The working environment with disadvantaged students is quite challenging which makes it difficult for teachers to alter their quit decisions regardless of increase in their salary. In fact, it is indicated that substantial increase in teachers' salary alone would not be sufficient to dramatically turn the situation around and retain quality staff with large concentration of disadvantaged students in a school.

The characteristics of other schools in the same district are as important in a teacher's career decisions as are the characteristics of their current school of teaching in that district. If the number of disadvantaged students in which they are teaching are higher than the other schools within the same district, they are more likely to change the school or depart from teaching. Moreover, these findings also suggest less likelihood of teachers to move from the current school where there are many disadvantaged students because of the potential opportunity they may see in other schools with less disadvantaged students in future move (Ondrich et al, 2008). Thus, the school climate is one of work environment variables of a school that affects teachers' attrition. Hence, teachers are more likely to quit from a school with negative work climate.

In addition, the climate of a school plays an important role in retaining teachers. Freedom to work independently in school and classroom setting are considered to be positive school climate reducing the turnover (Pearson & Moomaw, 2005).

The *Study of Personnel Needs in Special Education [SPeNSE] (2002)* with the title of *A High-Quality Teacher for Every Classroom* recommend that positive school climate in a school

results in higher retention rates as compared to schools with less positive school climate. Thus, in the SPeNSE study, school climate incorporates range of items such as: supportive and encouraging administration of the school, cooperation among colleagues, availability of required necessary materials, participation in the decision-making, teachers' and students' safety in the school.

To summarise, school climate plays a part in teachers' career decisions. Studies suggest that an overall positive school climate contribute in teachers' decision stay and vice versa.

b) Poor Working Conditions

The working conditions of a school is a salient predictor of turnover intentions among staff compared to all other factors previously noted in the literature. The relationship between working condition and teacher turnover has been investigated in many research studies (McKenzie, Santiago & OECD, 2005; Boyd, et al., 2008). These studies found an association between working condition and teachers' leave intentions.

The primary reasons of teacher turnover are generally considered to be related with salary and finances, however Gross, & Player (2007) indicated that working conditions are more important issue. They corelate the working conditions with teachers' job satisfaction. Working conditions of a school directly affect teachers' effectiveness (Ladd, 2011). Factors such as sub-standard building, furniture and supply, lack of quality resources, and poor teachers' accommodation facilities are generally neglected by schools and districts in teacher retention policies as pointed out by Imazeki (2005).

McKenzie, Santiago & OECD (2005) asserts that;

“the reasons that teachers give for leaving the profession (other than retirement) confirm the pivotal role of working conditions (2005, p. 177).”

Thus, a teacher's workload is increased with the lack of instructional and technological resources on one hand, while the excessive workload makes the use the available resources difficult and continue with the profession on the other hand.

It has been largely observed that schools with less expenditure on working conditions face high teacher turnover, however, the importance of working conditions vary context to context and place to place. Seniwoliba (2013) reported that the teachers in developed countries such as Ghana, are more concerned about the quality of working conditions and suitability of these conditioned with school climate. Whereas on the other hand, the teachers of schools in developing countries are stressed about the basic facilities such as lights, books and classroom besides they struggle to continue working in poor working conditions.

Moreover, Buckley, Schneider, and Yi, (2004) asked K-12 teaching staff in large urban districts such as Washington D.C. in United States to complete a survey. The purpose was to investigate the reasons behind teachers' decisions to leave with respect to school facilities in a developed setting. The study compared the quality of facilities and salary with regard to leave behaviour and found high turnover trend among teachers who were less satisfied with working conditions compared to those who were less satisfied with salary.

Furthermore, the relationship between working conditions of a school and teacher turnover has also been investigated by Boyd, et al. (2009). Their sample of study was consisted of 4360 teachers in New York who entered the profession quite recently and did not have an experience of more than 2 years. A survey was administered among teachers based on factors such as personal goals, teaching practices and school characteristics. The data collected was then compared with district administration data in order to evaluate the relationship between schools' working conditions and teachers' career decisions. Hence the findings suggest that working condition is one of the primary factors of teachers' intentions to leave or stay in the profession.

Unlike the context of developed countries, Pakistan is a low resource developing country therefore working conditions are not among the primary causes of teachers' leave behaviour. Particularly, in countries with terror attacks, economic instability, crises and a destroyed basic infrastructure, creating an appropriate teaching learning environment is highly challenging due to lack of necessary resources (Glewwe, P., et al., 2011).

c) Low Salary

The relationship between salary and teachers' attrition has earlier been investigated by many researchers including other school characteristics. For example, Hanushek, et al., (2004), Stinebrickner (2002), and Imazeki (2002) examined the impact of salaries on teachers' career decisions. Their studies revealed that the higher the salaries are the lower the attrition is. Districts can set teachers' salaries as this variable is in the control of officials while they do not have control over other variables such as socio-economic background of the students. Similarly, Milkovich & Newman, (2005) indicated that low salary has identified as the main reason contributing in teacher turnover. Workers who felt unfairly paid leave their organizations ultimately.

There have many empirical studies been conducted to suggest an association between salary and turnover. The data collected in these studies compare the salaries of those who left with those who stayed. It has been observed that departed teachers of an urban school take salary as being one of the prominent reasons to quit the job. The number of teachers who move or leave decrease with the increase in salary (Ladd, 2007; Podgursky et al. 2004). Similar results have been seen by Boe, et al., (2008) where teachers are said to stay with high salaries as opposed to those with lower salaries.

The consistent finding of these three studies on effect of salary on teachers' attrition behaviour suggest that teachers can be retained for longer by increasing the salary of teachers as a retention strategy. As pointed out by Henke, et al. (2004) that school and districts can take advantage during hiring and recruiting teachers by offering competitive salaries as a staff retention policy. Similarly, motivations in the form of financial incentives such as cash rewards, bonuses, increments or progression onto a higher paid position are used as recruitment strategy by many large district schools. However, the effects of using these financial incentives as retention strategy are debateable.

Few other studies focus on the differential effects of salary on teachers' transfer or leave decisions with regard to the length of time they spend in teaching (Imazeki, 2002; Hanushek

et al. 2005). Similarly, the spending priorities of a school or district also found to have an effect on teachers' attrition.

A research study by Ondrich J. et al (2008) compare the salaries of teaching staff with the salaries of employees in other professions and found a significant impact of salary on teachers' career decisions. Additionally, the probability of teachers to quit or move is higher in relatively low paid district compared to surrounding districts with high pay scale for similar position. Transferring to high paid districts is more likely in this case however a district finds it difficult to move up the salary distribution in respond to increase in salary in another district.

Similarly, salary differences in the teaching and non-teaching professions in the same country also contribute towards teachers' career decision (Ondrich et al, 2008). Higher salaries in other professions compared to teaching result in high turnover of teachers. In addition, there is less likelihood of teachers to leave from high paid districts in the same country.

Thus, the salary has continuously been a salient predictor of and a prominent factor behind teacher turnover outcomes. For the purpose of retaining quality staff in education sector, it is important for policy makers to weigh the costs of losing and benefit of retaining teachers in the field of teaching in a particular school or district.

d) Workload/Paperwork

Although many studies confirm that low pay is a major factor behind teachers' turnover from the profession. However, Smithers and Robinson (2003) present a contrary viewpoint where they consider the salary as the least important factor behind turnover whereas workload is by far the most important factor at 44.8% among the five-main factor influencing turnover (i.e., "*workload, new challenge, the school situation, salary and personal circumstances*"). Workload has also found to be a big factor behind teachers' decision to quit job in UK. According to survey conducted by the Guardian in UK, 82% percent teachers plan to leave job in future due to unmanageable workload (Lightfoot, 2016). Workload manageability is, therefore, considered to be an important aspect in measuring the turnover rates.

Many researchers found paperwork as a key cause of role conflict among teaching staff and consider this as a major contributor in teachers' turnover. The studies revealed a significant relationship between paperwork problems and teachers' career decisions after having controlled the other work-related variables. Paperwork increases with addition of each new student in the class as pointed out by a teacher in a study by Billingsley et al. (2004). Some qualitative studies on teacher turnover explain what an excessive paperwork mean for teachers who describe it as nerve wrecking, redundant, inconsistent, unnecessary and devastating because of the pressure they feel to complete the paperwork for which they do not have enough time. Carlson & Billingsley (2001) compared the teachers who intent to leave with those who intent to stay. He found that the workload as "not at all manageable" is a significant factor behind teachers' intention to leave compare to the teachers who intent to stay in the profession.

Qualitative studies in the form of open-ended interviews such discovered that workload in form of paperwork contribute in teachers' intentions to leave teaching. For instance, a qualitative study conducted by Lucy (2018) revealed that twenty-two percent of the teachers specifically mentioned about the nerve-wracking amount of paperwork and heavy workload causing dissatisfaction with job. One teacher stated, "the workload is mentally stressful." (p. 57). Another teacher reported, "the amount of paperwork required for my job and the number of assessments required negatively affect the amount and quality of teaching I feel I can perform." (p.58).

In addition, Collie, et al., (2012) reported that workload was directly related to teachers being dissatisfied with their job. According a recent survey done by the Department of Education (DoE, 2018) two-third of teachers felt overwhelmed by the amount of paperwork required in the profession. Teachers also revealed that their work-life balance is negatively affected by the heavy workload which increase their stress levels and dissatisfaction, ultimately contributing in their decisions to quit.

Similarly, Fall and Billingsley (2011) concluded in their study that teachers tend to commit to the job and stay longer when the amount of paperwork, and number of caseloads are

manageable. It is also likely that the paperwork responsibility given to teacher may vary across schools and districts, hence, influence may also vary on career decisions of teachers.

e) Inadequate administrative support

A supportive administration is vital in raising teachers' morale. A research study by Boyd et al., (2007) on teacher attrition indicate that attachment of any employee with the organisation is affected by the overall workplace characteristics in addition his individual and personal traits. Of these the most important is the support from administration, especially for beginning teachers.

Similarly, teachers with supportive and encouraging administration are reported to be four times more likely to stay in the school compared to teachers without such a support from administration. Therefore, inadequate building administration support leads towards high turnover as suggested in many researches.

Numerous studies found a significant relationship between administration behaviour and teacher turnover. Positive behaviour of administration results in high teacher retention and vice versa. Similarly, adequate or more adequate support from administration is necessary for teachers who teach students with emotional disorders (Billingsley, 2004). With supportive administration, such teachers are found highly likely to stay in teaching because in this case they are less likely to be stressed with emotional disorders of the students. Thus, the administration support plays a crucial role in making the teachers feel more satisfied with their jobs and stay committed to their current schools. The more satisfied they are, the more chances of them to stay.

Many research studies reported that the teachers with plans to stay longer in their current school division consider administration support as being most important in their career decisions. The perceived support specifies the inclusion of teachers in decision making process. Supportive principal was reported to be a vital incentive behind teachers' stay decisions in the field (Haynes, 2014).

However, there are mixed results found on the relationship between central office administration and teacher turnover. For instance, an older study by Miller et al. (1999) did not discover any relationship between central office administration and teacher turnover in their research study on attrition behaviour. Whereas, a later study conducted by Gersten et al., (2001) on intent to leave and indicated an indirect influence of central office on turnover in the form of policies and development opportunities. The different results in these two studies might be dependent on the different methods employed to analyse the data or might be due to the different dependant measures adopted.

In addition, Billingsley et al., (2004) conducted a research study on an urban school setting presenting that teachers reported less dissatisfaction with principal whereas more dissatisfaction with the central administration. The results in this study discover that in an urban school setting, 25% teachers reported inadequate support from central office as a reason of their decision to leave while 20% teachers reported dissatisfaction with the principal as the main cause to quit teaching. However, the findings about the general educators other than teaching staff are contrary where 10% are dissatisfied with central office while 12% are reported to be dissatisfied with the principal. Therefore, central office support is indicated to be as important in teachers' career decisions as is the administration support of the school. The critical role of central officers in teachers' career decision is of no surprise given the fact that they are the ones who are responsible to make education policies.

Other important variables such as stress, job satisfaction, role problems and commitment have been studied in association with the influence of supportive administration on intention to leave teaching profession. These path analyses provide a very clear understanding of how the intention of teachers to leave is affected by administration behaviour. Gersten et al., (2001) found a direct and indirect influence of good support from administration on these variables indicating less stress, high job satisfaction, greater commitment and more professional development opportunities as a result of higher level of support from administration.

The varied type of support from administration is difficult to define due to its comprehensive nature. There are many dimensions of the paradigm of support on a worldwide level. However, for the purpose of examining the influence of support on attrition behaviour it is very important to review the most important type of support required by teachers to stay longer in a school climate. These include emotional on one hand and instructional support on the other. Emotional support denotes to maintaining open communication with staff, appreciating their work, giving positive feedback and making them feel included in the decision-making process. Instructional support is about providing required resources, space and material. Haynes (2014) have also found emotional support as being most important in teachers' career decisions. They found a positive relationship between these two support types and job satisfaction. Teachers are more satisfied with higher support from administration.

Moreover, according to Swars, Meyers, Mays, and Lack (2009), both supportive administrative and leadership is one of the important five themes essential for teacher retention. Similarly, Cochran-Smith, (2004) also reported that teachers must have school conditions where they are satisfied and supported and have collaborative leadership and colleagues. Thus, a support system that motivate teachers to conquer challenges they face in the profession and classroom might help them stay longer (Ndoye, Imig, & Parker, 2010).

f) Lack of support from colleagues

Unfortunately, there has been less attention paid to this aspect of examining turnover with relation to collegial support. Although previous studies suggest that administrators should support teachers however it is a process of exchange of support among one another. A positive school climate is where support is reciprocal. The role of administration to support and encourage teachers has certainly been a vital focus of teacher attrition literature, however, fostering a collegial environment for greater level of job commitments is also crucial. The role of principal or head of the school is prominent in this regard as he is the one who share the common goal and values and can foster collaborative communities within the school for a healthier collegial environment.

According to Swars, et al. (2009), shared value and teachers' relationship with each other is one of the five essential themes in a school. Similarly, Fall (2010) also suggested a general supportive environment that foster a collegial school culture where new teachers are provided the opportunities to interact with experienced colleagues and where colleagues are supportive to each other. NPR (2016) presented a report on attrition of teachers and revealed that teachers always demand a positive collegial environment where they can collaborate with their colleagues. They want to talk about how feel if they are supported in their efforts by getting a constant moral support. They say that they feel more satisfied in such an environment.

McCoy (2003) also reported that if new teachers have support from administrators and other colleagues, then they tend to remain committed with the teaching profession. However, it is imperative to examine the support factor as "cumulative" phenomenon consisting support from principal, assistant principal and colleagues in a particular school. The results can then be compared with support from colleagues separately that is more practicable (Gersten et al., 2001).

g) Lack of support through induction and mentoring

Teachers are more likely to leave during the early years of teaching therefore early teachers require more support to stay in the profession. Studies suggest that beginning teachers generally enter the profession with an optimistic approach to work which is however often turn into disappointment, disillusionment and discouragement (Bennet et al., 2013). Hence, it is very crucial to provide support to teachers in the beginning stages of their career when they are highly likely to quit.

There are range of problems that are faced by novice teachers and they struggle to handle such problems. For example, problem with students' attitudes, discipline issues, difficulty with parents, inadequate collegial support. Working with students who have significant learning and behavioural problems is also a cause of concern for early teachers and an additional responsibility on their shoulders. They also find it difficult to get familiar with school routine and get engaged in planning the scheme of study initially.

A few qualitative research studies presented various issues faced by teachers in their early years such as collaborating with other staff members, scheduling students, adhering to parents' concerns, managing workload, developing and monitoring IEPs, adhering to planned curriculum activities (MacDonald, 2001; Boyer & Gillespie, 2000).

Teachers can find it more manageable to cope with such challenges in the early years if they receive carefully proposed mentor program. They are also said to perform better if they receive high quality induction support (Haynes, 2014). However, only few studies have documented that the support through induction and mentoring results in lower attrition rates among new and beginning teachers although they are at higher risk of leaving the profession.

Billingsley (2002) found no significant relation between induction support available and early teachers' plans to stay. Nevertheless, he finds some beginning teachers seeing themselves as more adaptable if there is a high level of induction support compared to those with lower level of support available to them. With high level support, these teachers are motivated to go through the problem students and feel satisfied believing in providing the education to these students successfully.

The effectiveness of a mentoring and induction program depends on how the beginning teachers perceive this. Whitaker (2000) also investigated to examine the effectiveness of these programs on teachers' career decisions and discovered that such program is considerably related with teachers' job satisfaction ultimately resulting in teachers' retention in the education field although the impact is quite small.

The conflicting findings by Billingsley and Whitaker may be the result of types of measures employed and population selected for their respective studies on the impacts and effectiveness of mentoring and induction program on teachers' career decisions. For instance, Whitaker (2000) focuses only on the following year of teaching and expands onto the next five years, whereas, Billingsley (2002) explored the teachers' intentions to leave or stay over a total career duration. However, they both found informal contracts of mentoring programs more effective than the formal programs.

Fall (2010) argues that a well-planned induction program policy in place along with supportive work conditions and leadership influence teachers to stay longer in the profession. Similarly, to retain teachers, schools need to have a combination of factors such as mentoring, positive culture and encouraging leadership (Wynn et al., 2007).

Indeed, the primary goal of an induction program is not to reduce attrition but to equip teachers with skill needed regardless of existing teacher surplus. Thus, satisfying the novice teachers by giving them all the required skills, support, adequate feedback and fair amount of workload contribute to make them feel satisfied and stay longer and develop their commitment to the profession.

Moreover, such programs should be aimed at making the teachers develop their competence and become most effective in a school environment. If this remains the purpose behind such programs the turnover will likely to be reduced ultimately. Leaders should also make sure that they assign the right mentor to novice teachers so that the process is a positive experience for both the mentee and mentor. (Bennett et. Al., 2013). However, the extent to which such programs are helpful in retaining early teachers is debateable for many.

h) Poor opportunities for professional advancement

The concept of support is very broad and professional advancement is a part of this concept. Although the older studies such as that by Miller et al., (1999) claimed that professional development opportunities have no influence on teacher turnover, a relevantly new study on teacher attrition by Gersten et al., (2001) relate opportunities for professional advancement with lower attrition behaviour. They suggest that although professional development opportunities are not directly related to the teacher' intents to leave, however, there is an indirect effect. They found that teachers are more committed to the profession if they development opportunities which ultimately results in low attrition. The extent to which teachers perceive such opportunities of growth and advancement is important to consider in this regard.

“This scale measures satisfaction with items such as opportunities to learn new techniques and strategies and opportunities for professional advancement and promotion” (pp. 555-556).

Their study findings also indicate less role conflicts experienced by teaching staff who receive high degree of professional advancement opportunities. These findings show the importance of support at both school and district levels.

Moreover, the timing, quality and type of content of development opportunities also affect the satisfaction level of teacher. The professional level development opportunities are influenced by the incentives to participate in the development programs. Harter et al., (2002) have also implied that professional development of an employee decreases the turnover rates. According to their research, individuals go through different stages of professional developments including their growth as an effective employee. Similarly, teachers who have intentions to stay generally assume themselves responsible for taking initiatives to learn on their own and develop their own growth.

Quiocho and Rios (2000) highlight the need for qualitatively different methods for nurturing teacher and these methods must be dynamic in nature and adapt with teachers’ professional needs. The professional development opportunities must be responsive and systematic over the period of time. The report from SPeNSE (2002) entitled *A High-Quality Teacher for Every Classroom* discuss how teachers spend considerable time for a continuous professional development without formal incorporated best practices provided by the school. Whereas, schools must allow teachers to engage into learning new skills and implement these skills practically. Schools need to be better organised to promote such programs and activities for teachers wanting to learn and grow in their careers.

i) Students’ issues

Ingersoll (2001) reviewed teachers who depart from the profession due to high dissatisfaction level with their job and found lack of student motivation to progress and their discipline issues

as being two major contributors to teachers' intentions to leave. However, the extent to which these issues contribute in turnover is debatable.

There are a range of problems that teachers encounter with students and that result in teacher turnover. These problems include diversity of student needs, safety issues, lack of students' progress, their attitudes and disciplinary issues (Billingsley, 2004). In addition to discipline issues, the level of students and their learning issues also contribute in teacher attrition. Similarly, teachers of emotionally disturbed students tend to leave somewhat more than teachers working with students who have physical or learning disabilities.

Moreover, the number of students in a classroom is also considered to be worthy of investigation with regards to teacher turnover. Some empirical studies indicate a consistent relationship of the number of students and the caseload issue with teacher turnover (Brownell et al., 1994-1995; Morvant et al., 1995). Their studies reported that the number of students taught by a teacher and the students with varied type of needs contribute to teachers' leave behaviour. However, Carlson & Billingsley (2001) did not find any relationship of the number of students and their types with teachers leave intentions.

Hence, students' discipline issues were the second most prominent factor among the three main reasons of teachers leave intention in a qualitative study conducted by Lucy (2018). They found that twenty four percent teachers indicated in a response to an open-ended question that they would leave due behavioural and disciplinary issue with students. "Student behaviour is draining" (p. 57) as mentioned by one of the participant teachers.

Billingsley (2004) research on special education reported that the diversity of students' needs is more likely a factor contributing in teacher turnover than simply the number of students. However, Billingsley also rate other problems such as leadership issues and teachers' role problems as being more important factor behind turnover than student related issues.

2.8 TEACHERS' RETENTION

Recruiting more staff only cannot solve the problem of teacher shortages, since high rates of turnover quickly undo the efforts to hire new teachers. Instead, retaining the quality staff is a well-researched solution. Rewarding career paths, appropriate administrative support, induction programs and mentoring programs can be helpful in improving teacher retention.

Although teachers are mainly involved in endorsing the learning process of students, however, they represent a significant portion of a school's investment typically. Indeed, their salaries cost almost half of the school's expenditures. Therefore, to improve the efficiency of school, to build its reputation and to enhance its productivity, it is vital for the policy makers to focus on hiring quality teachers and implementing effective teacher retention policies. The previous empirical and investigative studies during past two decades seek to find out the ideas to endorse and revolutionized the training of teachers especially during the early years of experience.

Hence, many recommendations are put forward for improving the selection and retention process for teachers and for improving their professional growth and refining their qualities. For instance, the program on education legislation in 2002 that "No Child Left Behind" was introduced in an effort to make reforms in teachers hiring and retention processes focusing on the importance of placing good quality teachers in every classroom. However, the bill is replaced with Every Student Succeed Act later with more focus on accountability measures for student achievement, teacher effectiveness and schools' performances (Hunt, 2015).

2.8.1 Definition of Teacher Retention

Retention is a process of keeping something for a long period of time. Teacher retention is a term that demonstrates a procedure to retain teaching staff either in a school or field of education. The researches on retention focus on policies to keep quality teachers stay for a long period of time. A significant importance has been given to the subject for policy makers

and other educationalists to retain quality teachers in order to achieve long term educational goals.

Thus, teacher retention in the present study refers to the private school teachers in Pakistan to remain in the same private school for at least 5 years.

2.8.2 The Scope of Study Review on Teacher Retention

The purpose of this review on studies that focus on teacher retention strategies is to find out practical suggestions and recommendations for policy makers in order to avoid costs associated with turnover. The study review will enable to provide sensible answers to the questions related to impact of turnover, its costs, and benefits of retaining quality staff and to identify ways for research on turnover and retention phenomenon in the field of education.

It is clear that turnover is a major problem in education sector, and it occurs on a high scale in many schools. It has noted in the previous chapter that schools with low income students are more likely to experience turnover at a high rate. This review is based on quantitative and qualitative research studies investigating the important aspects of teacher retention in the education sector. Recent as well as older studies with continuous and ongoing importance relevant to the topic are included in this review.

Although the available researches are distributed unevenly in a way that many are found on the subject of salary related to turnover for example and less are found on the subjects related to hiring of teachers, however, this study attempts at giving equal attention to each subject for a better understanding of the topic. For this purpose, the findings of researches that are directly and indirectly focusing on various subjects are included in the current study.

2.8.3 Importance of Teachers' Retention

Retaining teachers who are already in the profession is all the more important for managing the future supply of teachers. The higher the retention of teacher is the higher are the achievements of students. It is, therefore, necessary for educators and policy makers to

identify the effective ways and strategies to increase retention rates in order to improve students' achievements.

Imazeki (2004) found a very strong relation between teachers' turnover and quality of education received by students. Turnover affects the education quality badly, therefore, it is vital to retain good teachers in order to have every child getting effective, high performance and quality education. There are many retention frameworks available for retaining employees. However, retaining teachers can be difficult and challenging compared to other professionals.

According to Education For all Global Monitoring Report (2015), by improving the working conditions, by giving pay rise and by offering professional growth in the career, teaching staff can be retained. It is, therefore, stressed that the best way to retain staff and enhance their commitment to the profession is the combination of suitable working conditions and incentives such as additional benefits and bonuses.

To limit the attrition rate caused by factors other than retirement it is vital to retain teachers in this sector. Teaching profession can be made a long-term attractive career opportunity in terms of attractive salaries, good working conditions and supportive school environment for not only the existing staff but also for the potential candidates. A competitive salary, for example, plays an important role to motivate existing teachers and attract new teachers. Similar research results were put forward by Ingersoll (2001) focusing on the importance of organisational conditions and role of salary in teachers' turnover.

Another important factor that should take into consideration while designing a staff retention framework is the type of contract. Temporary contracts make the profession uncertain and therefore lead to a de-motivating teaching staff as they consider themselves under less favourable conditions with lower salaries and less organisational support compared to the staff under permanent contract basis (UIS, 2016). That is why they are more likely to quit the job.

In terms of devising staff retention policies to reduce teacher attrition, the importance should also be given to non-financial aspects of the profession such as money should be spent on reducing pupil-teacher ratio (PTR). This corresponds to a practical substitute to generally proposed pay rise incentives (Stinebrickner, 2002). At the same time, this is helpful in lessening the workload on teacher making the job less stressful. Whereas on the other hand, Bennell & Ntagaramba (2008) stressed that individual teacher's characteristics should be taken into consideration while designing an incentive policy for teachers' retention.

2.8.4 Conceptual Models for Teacher Retention

Maslow's need hierarchy (1954) and Herzberg's two-factor theory (1983) are chosen as the available framework for teacher retention because these both theories emphasise on the needs fulfilment and level of satisfaction of an individual (teacher) in the context of the turnover issue. The factors behind teacher turnover are studied with regards to Maslow's concept of need fulfilment whereas the factors of retention are connected with teachers' job satisfaction proposed by Herzberg.

2.8.4.1 Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow (1954) assumes that each individual has the following five kinds of needs that he requires to fulfil.

Figure 2.5: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

According to Maslow's illustration, fulfilment of one need persuades the next need to be fulfilled. Teachers basic needs of better salary packages, better working conditions and better facilities are important for their retention. Moreover, teachers' social needs to be loved respected by students, fellow teachers, and leaders are also important to retain them longer in the profession. Teachers like all other employees need recognition, rewards and appreciation from the senior management and administrators for their good performance. The support in the form of such work recognition enhances their skills and knowledge. As a result, when teachers' social needs of recognition, respect and knowledge are accomplished they move to the next level of esteem needs fulfilment.

Once a teacher gets to the level of esteem needs, they are on a self-actualization level where they become self-aware and assess their strength and weaknesses. However, Maslow (1954) stated that it is highly difficult to fulfil the top-level needs of self-actualization because with psychological growth, the teachers keep developing and growing in their fields. Thus, these teachers reach an ideal level where they become more committed to their profession. Consequently, students' learnings are improved, and the schools' profile is enhanced with better teacher retentions.

2.8.4.2 Herzberg's Two Factor Theory

Herzberg (1959) proposed the theory of need satisfaction, that an individual's satisfaction is important in the fulfilment of needs. He classified the factors of need satisfaction into two categories:

Figure 2.6: Herzberg's two Factor Theory

Herzberg theory precisely portray that teacher attrition is driven by the dissatisfaction on their personal, social and professional levels. The factors that cause this dissatisfaction include lack of organizational support, heavy workload causing stress, poor working conditions, inadequate salary, and fears of beginning teachers. However, teachers' decision to stay in the profession are influenced positively with the satisfaction of all these factors.

Furthermore, safety also impact positively on teachers' stay decisions. teachers are more likely to stay in the profession if the work environment is supportive and secure to teach equipped with enough learning resources and with manageable workload along. Similarly, if the community and students give them the respect and gratitude, if they are appreciated and praised for their hard work, and if they receive adequate salaries; if both the lower level

extrinsic needs and higher level intrinsic needs are not fulfilled they will be demotivated and lose interest in the profession.

Thus, the factors of independence, reward, bonuses, success and work recognition, motivate teachers and ensure that they are capable to work efficiently and effectively to accomplish the difficult tasks (Aslami, 2013). Thus, both these theoretical frameworks depict that to motivate teachers to stay longer in the profession, their needs should be fulfilled and satisfied. For successfully retain teachers their individual characteristics, or personal needs should also be taken into consideration along with the usual incentive and reward system of the school.

2.8.5 Factors That Influence the Retention of Teachers

According to the Indiana General Assembly's study committee on education, the shortage of teachers can be eliminated by cutting the turnover of teachers into half (Herron, 2017). Following are the factors that play an important role in retaining the qualified teachers in order to eliminate teachers' shortages.

2.8.5.1 Teachers' Individual Needs

Of course, each teacher is an individual personality with individual needs. The expectations and priorities of teachers differ depending on their circumstances of workplace. Similarly, each teacher has a different level of satisfaction with regard to certain aspect of workplace. For instance, one teacher may be less concerned about class size and more exasperated about not having a curriculum. The school' shabby building may frustrate one teacher while such disrepair may be unnoticed by her colleagues.

In addition, exercising influence in the school is what engages few teachers in their job whereas having a chance to access the professional development opportunities is what other teachers may care more about. Similarly, unlike teachers who enter the profession at mid-career and has some military pension to support them financially, there are few teachers who are more concerned about their salaries as they have to have down payments for their dream house.

Hence, it is challenging to satisfy all teachers since human beings are different working in a workplace with interdependent sets of elements. All these elements are important of considerations when making a retention policy in order to satisfy individual's needs in a workplace.

2.8.5.2 Intrinsic & Extrinsic Rewards

As discussed earlier in chapter two how intrinsic and extrinsic rewards influence teachers' leave decisions. Similarly, a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic reward factors is associated with teachers' decision to remain in a school or in the profession. Such reward factors influence the teachers in their workplace as suggested in many researches. According to Patton and Kristonis (2006), intrinsic rewards should be taken into account at the time of recruiting teachers who are passionate about teaching children in order to improve teacher retention. Bennett, et al., (2013) also argues that experienced teachers decided to stay in the field of education because they loved teaching.

Unlike intrinsic rewards, extrinsic rewards including salary, financial rewards such as bonuses, monetary benefits, recognition of work by senior administration and being chosen for a development program are considered to exert more influence on teachers' stay decisions.

Nevertheless, both types of rewards are interconnected and influence one another. For instance, salary may not be the reason for someone to enter into the teaching field however it may influence their decision to remain upon finding poor working conditions in a school e.g., lack of facilities, making it hard for them to continue.

In order to achieve these intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, a balance is needed between positive and negative working conditions for teacher retention. The negative working conditions such as lack of resources, lack of support from colleagues or large number of students in a classroom can be compensated with positive working conditions such as well lighted, temperature-controlled and well-ventilated classrooms and a safe parking lot as well as supportive principal. If there are more negative aspect than the positive, the teachers are more likely to leave than stay.

All teachers generally want to be effective in the classrooms and contribute in their students' achievements. They leave the teaching or psychologically withdraw from being effective in the classroom if their intrinsic rewards are not achieved due to poor working conditions. Many research studies suggest a relationship between teachers' sense of being effective and retention. A teacher's opportunity to teach effectively is affected by whimsically stressful workload, lack of resources and lack of collegial support resulting in lower satisfaction level and, thus, lower teacher retention. Hence, a teacher's sense of efficacy in the classroom and satisfaction with their work is required to increase teacher retention. Darling-Hammond, (2005) also reinstates that while job satisfaction is highly important for teacher retention, for highly qualified teachers it has additional impact.

However, retention itself is not a worthy goal for law makers and educators despite the fact that it is highly important to improve the retention rates in a school or districts. Retaining teachers with necessary skills and qualification does not help in serving the students well. The students' learning and achievement is the ultimate goal which can only be achieved by retaining quality staff instead of retaining teachers who are incompetent, mediocre, disengaged, or burnt out. Therefore, schools must seek to retain skilled and efficient staff who are able to demonstrate high performance and contribute in students' achievements.

2.8.5.3 Favorable School Characteristics/Climate

Though Ingersoll (2001) has criticised the lack of enough knowledge with regard to the relationships between attrition and the schools' characteristics, some studies that documented the subject has been located in an attempt to validate the role of various schools' characteristics on teacher attrition and retention.

There is a mounting evidence to indicate that teachers' retention decisions are significantly affected by schools' characteristics including availability of resources, material, textbook and facilities, climate related factors, level of available support by schools' administration and principal, inclusion of teachers in decision making, progression opportunities, level of safety as well as type of relationship with students, parents and colleagues (Feng, 2006; Allensworth et al., 2009; Loeb, Darling-Hammond, & Luczak, 2005; Johnson & Birkeland, 2003; Kukla-

Acevedo, 2009; Ingersoll, 2001). In fact, Loeb et al. (2005) pointed out that after working conditions were made better in their models of California schools, the influence of student characteristics on teacher turnover was substantially reduced.

Similarly, all the aforementioned retention studies endorse that teachers, both beginning and experienced, are affected by the schools' resource and climate conditions. Previous researches show that poor climate conditions in schools not only negatively impact the teacher retention on one hand (Ingersoll, 2001; Allensworth et al., 2009), but also affect student achievement on the other hand (DeAngelis & Presley, 2011; Sebring, Allensworth, Bryk, Easton, & Luppescu, 2006). Hence, improving work conditions in schools can be aimed at by policy makers to not only retain teachers but to provide extended benefits including better student performances.

According to Lockwood (2007), to attract and retain employees in any organisation the mission of HR should be fostering a positive and encouraging workplace environment. A positive school climate is where support is reciprocal. Although administrators should support teachers however it is a process of exchange of support among one another. All educators, service providers, professionals and parents have important roles to provide support in creating a positive school climate.

2.8.5.4 Increase Job Satisfaction

Non-financial incentives play a role in improving teachers job satisfaction and making them stay longer (Hirsch, 2006). Such incentives include providing teachers with additional support, reduced load of work, better caseload, rest periods, opportunities to teach with freedom and play a role in decision making. Scafidi et al., (2007) also established that better salaries alone are not sufficient in teachers' job satisfaction and retention. To increase their job satisfaction factors such as respect, better work conditions and positive environment are vital ingredients. They also agreed that lack of opportunity to freely and effectively teach leads to the most teachers' departure. Thus, many teachers consider Job dissatisfaction to be main factor causing their leave decisions.

Allensworth, Ponisciak, and Masseo (2009) indicated that teachers with more opportunity to have input in school decisions are highly satisfied and are more likely to continue teaching. Ingersoll et al., (2017) also suggested that providing teachers with the opportunity to take part in fundamental decisions that affect teaching and learning is a key factor in increasing their job satisfaction levels. Similarly, Howard (2003) also suggested that leaders can retain teachers by improving working conditions and granting teachers more freedom and independence in the school's decision-making process.

Moreover, teachers who are provided with the proper resources and material to effectively teach students are more satisfied and therefore they stay longer in teaching (Fall 2010). Of course, teachers need necessary material to effectively teach in the classroom (NPR 2016).

2.8.5.5 Higher Teacher Pay and Compensation

Higher teacher pay has been suggested to be one of the powerful strategies in the previous studies on improving retention of teachers and reduce teacher turnover probabilities. This is particularly important once variances in other job opportunities are taken into account (Dolton & Newson, 2003). Therefore, it is imperative to consider the other financial benefits along with salaries in relation with teachers' career persistence such as incentives, cash rewards, bonuses and compensations.

Mounting previous literature suggest a positive relation between good salaries and teachers' stay decisions in the same school or district. For instance, Tekleab, Bartol, and Liu (2005) found that good salary packages provide a reason for teachers to change careers. However, some studies presented a difference of male and female teachers' career choices with regard to salaries. According to an empirical study by Bloland and Selby (1980), who presented a critical examination of the previous literature, salary plays an important role in male teachers' career changes compared to female teachers who are less concerned with salary issues. Although, policies to offer higher salaries with incentives and other monetary benefits in high-needs schools incur additional financial expenditures, however, such strategies could also curtail the high costs of replacing and recruiting new teachers to the schools.

Moreover, reasonable pay reduces turnover is also indicated by Hom & Griffest, (2000). According to Darling-Hammond & Ducommun (2007), the recruitment incentives are needed to attract and keep expert teachers in these schools. Clotfelter, Glennie, Ladd, and Vigdor (2008) found that offering a \$1,800 per year retention bonus decreased teacher attrition rates by 17%.

In addition, along with salary, other monetary benefits and compensation are also considered to be important for employees to meet their financial needs. According to Milkovich & Newman (2005), compensation and benefits are one of the most attractive rewards in recruitment process as well as in teachers' stay decisions.

2.8.5.6 Leadership Support

In addition, previous studies discovered that the lack of enough support from senior leadership play a prominent role in teacher turnover. However, whether the support from administrators and senior leadership can play a role in retaining teachers requires more research and development. The available literature reviewed on the subject suggest that less bureaucratic leadership and school system as well as more genuine support from principal, administration and senior colleagues promote trust among teachers and improve retentions. Darling-Hammond, (2005) found in her study that job dissatisfaction leads to turnover which is caused by a restrictive controls, bureaucratic leadership, and inadequate administrative support for teaching.

For successful initiatives to implement effective policies and improve school's work environment, the role of a principal is crucial. A facilitative leadership style of a principal is most effective in retaining the teachers. Studies found that an effective leadership from a principal improve productive collegial work in an organised school that results in increased teacher retention. For instance, Fall (2010) suggested that supportive programs for teachers as well as a general supportive environment with increased principal support is crucial to reduce the turnover and improve retention. Thus, principal play an important role in generating efficient and collaborative work environment where teachers are included in making ongoing decisions about the curriculum and teaching instructions.

Studies on school improvements maintain that principals can use the school structure and their authority to encourage collaborative staff in order to achieve common goals. These principals may act as reform leaders to promote supportive collaboration and positive social interactions among teaching staff to increase teacher retention. Brown and Wynn (2009) conducted a study with principals in an urban school district to identify different characteristics present and strategies used to recruit and retain teachers in their schools. They found that districts should ensure that principals are strong supportive leaders.

Similarly, school's leadership can provide supportive induction and mentoring especially to new teachers to improve retention. Hence, teachers feel satisfied when administrative support provides adequate mentoring, create a positive school environment and help them with behaviour management issues (Bennett et al., 2013). The study by Ingersoll & Strong (2011) also pointed towards the the impact of induction and mentoring program and found that leadership support in form of such program influence teachers career decision in a positive manner. Similarly, Petty et al., (2011) stated that to retain teachers, leaders should provide teachers with the necessary support which included to provided teachers with the opportunity to be heard.

2.8.5.7 Clearly Designed Role

A clearly defined role design is reported to have influenced teachers' career decision. There are many role-related elements associated with teachers' retention. For instance, school must define teachers' responsibilities clearly and must not instruct them to complete the tasks out of their job role. They must have enough time to plan lesson and prepare for relevant material as well as complete their paperwork. There should be no ambiguity and conflict in the role and role overload. The programs goals should be set clearly aforementioned and teachers should agree with those program goals.

Thus, a clear role design needs to be paid more attention to improve teacher retention. As Gersten et al., (2001) asks:

“Does the job, with all it entails, make sense? Is it feasible? Is it one that well-trained, interested, educational professionals can manage in order to accomplish their main objective—enhancing students’ academic, social, and vocational competence?” (p. 551).

2.9 SUMMARY

The literature review discussed the problem of teachers’ shortage all over the world bringing into attention how this problem is significant in the context of the Pakistani private education sector. Pakistani private education sector is also suffering from high teacher turnover rates. Turnover is expensive as this incur cost on education sector as well as influence the students’ achievements. The turnover of teachers leads to the shortage of teachers which can be eliminated by retaining the teachers in the teaching field. There are many factors identified in previous studies that cause the problem. There are two main categories of these factors, i.e., personal factors and work-related factors.

Among personal factors, teachers’ age, gender, race, ethnicity, qualification, marital status, subject speciality and regional attachments play an important role in teachers’ career decisions. Mostly young teachers often 30 years old are considered to be more likely to leave teaching. Some studies show a combination of age and gender collectively affecting teachers’ decision to leave teaching as female teachers’ turnover rates are generally higher. Similarly, marital status affects female teachers most as they leave due to relocation or bearing and raising children. Mixed results are seen among teachers’ leave behaviour with regards to the race or ethnicity. However, many studies claim higher rates of turnover among minority teachers. On one hand, teachers with maths and science qualification are more likely to leave teaching compared to the other subjects, whereas on the other hand, special education teachers’ turnover rates are higher. Similarly, regional attachments also play a role in turnover as most teachers who teach near their home or in the same district are found less likely to leave.

In addition to the personal factors, work-related factors are also very important in teachers' career decisions. The characteristics of schools and climate are significant among these factors. Poor urban district schools with more disadvantaged students face higher turnover rates. In addition, the school climate is one of the work environment variables of a school that affects teachers' attrition. Hence, teachers are more likely to stay in a school with more positive work climate. Similarly, many studies found an association between working condition and teacher turnover. Factors such as sub-standard building, furniture and supply, lack of quality resources, and poor teachers' accommodation facilities are significant in teachers leave intentions. As far as salaries of teachers is concerned teachers are said to stay with high salaries as opposed to those with lower salaries. Moreover, many researchers found paperwork as a key cause of role conflict among teaching staff and consider this as a major contributor in teachers' turnover. Furthermore, an inadequate building administration support leads towards high turnover rates. Other important variables such as stress, job satisfaction, role problems and commitment have been studied in association with the influence of supportive administration on intention to leave teaching profession. Similarly, poor opportunities to grow and develop, lack of mentoring program and issues with students are among many other reasons for teachers to quit teaching profession. By eliminating the factors that cause the turnover, teachers can be retained in the profession to reduce teachers' shortage.

3 CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH DESIGN & METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a system of approach towards solving a research problem. It is a scientific way of doing the research and understand the existing research problem. A researcher adopts this approach taking various steps with a logic behind them. It is necessary for a researcher to understand the methods and techniques to adopt a reasonable research methodology.

Following is a detail of all steps necessary for a researcher to take logically to understand and solve a research problem.

3.1 RESEARCH PARADIGM

According to Kuhn (1962), a research paradigm is “the set of common beliefs and agreements shared between scientists about how problems should be understood and addressed.” A paradigm consists of the following components: ontology, epistemology, methodology, and, methods (Also see figure in appendix).

Figure 3.1: Research Paradigm, Adapted from Hay (2002)

Ontology is concerned with what is the reality. Crotty (1998) explains that it indicates the study of being, dealing with the existence of something and its nature. A researcher makes ontological assumptions based on how things work in reality and takes a position, either positivist or interpretive position on that point.

Epistemology follows the ontology and is concerned with form and source of knowledge and how this knowledge is acquired and transferred. This deals with the question of 'how'. Epistemological assumptions help the researcher to investigate the relationship between reality and what can be known about that reality (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

Both ontology and epistemology are the branches of philosophy concerned with the existence of something. Since the researcher makes his own speculations about a phenomenon, the philosophical underpinnings of each paradigm do not deal with proving the assumptions right or wrong. The ontological and epistemological assumptions provide us with a holistic view of knowledge and enable us to see our relationship with that knowledge. The assumptions one makes in view of ontology and epistemology reflect in the method and methodology. The more a researcher is aware of the philosophical underpinning of paradigm and ontological and epistemological assumptions, the better is the quality of research strategies and techniques.

The Methodology is based on approaches used to acquire that knowledge of the existence of something. It is a strategy that deals with tools and techniques of the research. Crotty (1998) explains it as being a plan of action for a researcher as to what, why, when, where and how the data will be collected and scrutinized. Using these tools and techniques the researcher investigates what can be known.

According to Crotty (1998) there are specific tools and techniques used in order to collect and analyse primary data. Two types of primary data are usually collected i.e. qualitative or quantitative. The choice of research methods reflects the choice of epistemology and methodology.

There are two types of paradigm i.e. positivism and interpretivism.

3.1.1 Positivism

Positivism approach prefers the use of quantitative data collection methods such as surveys, structured questionnaires and statistic information. Positivists aim at finding the trends and

pattern based on hypothesis and the impacts of different variables on one another. They look for objective meanings and believe that individuals' behaviours are shaped by society. Their results are generalized and present a reliable statistic data. The researcher is conclusive in his purpose when using positivism. This approach allows the researcher to collect speedy data and the sample represents the total population however the results can be biased.

3.1.2 Interpretivism

Interpretive paradigm is opposite of positivism paradigm in social science and prefers to use qualitative method of data collection. This is used to explore the unknown by defining the problem. This allows the research process to uncover the general meaning and interpretive approaches deal with collecting data using naturalistic methods such as interview, observations and open-ended processes. The interpretivists believe that instead of society responsible to shape the individuals, it is individual who shapes the society. The purpose is to understand the complex phenomenon and gain an in-depth insight into the motives behind such phenomenon.

A researcher with this paradigm looks for subjective meanings and underlying reasons for certain behaviour. The results usually present rich and valid data. Interpretive paradigm allows the researcher to ask open-ended questions that results in better and in-depth understanding of the problem and help suggesting reasonable recommendations. However, on the other hand, there are some disadvantages of using interpretive such as the responses are not measured and statistically represented. Also, the responses are dependent on interviewer skills and how he interprets the data.

3.1.3 Paradigm of the Present Study

Both interpretive and positivist approaches help the researcher to understand the values, beliefs and views of people in an organisation, however, the ontology of interpretive is the best way to capture the emotional and subjective reality (Schein, 2011).

For the present study data collection, an interpretive position in relation to ontology was taken by the researcher due to the fact that the study aimed at dealing with the emotional reality of teachers in district Gujrat. Thus, the relative ontology for the current study assumes that teachers in district Gujrat cannot separate themselves emotionally from the reality. Their feelings and emotions are important to investigate to explore the reality of teachers' turnover in district Gujrat.

Goldkuhl (2012) discusses that the underlying assumptions of interpretive research paradigm are that understanding the emotional and subjective meaning assigned to individuals is the most crucial factor for fulfilling the research objectives. Hence, the interpretive paradigm selected for the present study enabled the researcher to take a position where emotional reality of teachers was negotiated through dialogue (interview with teachers) and open-ended questions, because the individuals have feelings and emotions and cannot be expected to behave in a specific way.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The nature of the research design describes the framework of carrying out a research project in any chosen area of study and helps to determine the methodology. There are two different types of research designs. One is exploratory research and the other is conclusive research. The later is divided into two sub-categories, i.e. descriptive research and casual research.

Figure 3.2: Types of Research Design

(Saunders et al, 2012)

3.2.1 Exploratory Design

The exploratory research design enables the researcher to understand the issue behind a certain phenomenon thoroughly without intending to offer any final and conclusive solution or evidence. Instead, the researcher ought to explore the topic in detail and depth. Singh (2007) defines the exploratory research as:

“the initial research, which forms the basis of more conclusive research. It can even help in determining the research design, sampling methodology and data collection method”.

In addition, Brown (2006) maintains the view that exploratory research *“tends to tackle new problems on which little or no previous research has been done”*. Moreover, Saunders et al., (2012) suggests that the revelation of new ideas and theories in an exploratory research allow the researcher to change his direction. The exploratory research design enables the researcher to design the survey and questions to reach the end goal. For instance, if a restaurant company intends to get feedback from customer in order to identify and improve the restaurant’s weaknesses. The researcher may decide to include customers’ level of happiness with menu, food quality and customer service and assume it to be an extensive list to record feedback. However, upon a preliminary exploratory research, they may identify

many customers being dissatisfied with location or atmosphere of the restaurant which was not possible to find out without exploratory research. Therefore, an appropriate use of exploratory research provides rich and quality information highlighting the main issues that need to be addressed and that will also inform the future researchers to statistically quantify the issues.

3.2.2 Conclusive Design

Conclusive research measures the data statistically and presents conclusive and final answer for the existing problem. It is defined as a research design aimed at assisting the researcher to decide, evaluate and choose a plan of action suitable in a given situation (Malhotra, 1999). Conclusive researchers tend to be deductive in nature and tests the hypothesis to achieve the objective of the research. Valid research instruments are applied on a reliable and relatively large sample which a true representation of the total population. This research design is quantitative in nature and is subcategorized into descriptive and casual research design.

Casual research design deals with the cause and effect relationship of different variables of an event. The major emphasis of this research design is work with attitudes and perceptions of people. Whereas descriptive research as the name implies deals with a descriptive data collected from a large research audience without establishing a causal relationship between variables of an event (Brannon, 1992). In fact, it explains the data based on facts of events and present accurate description of the research audience without manipulating the data. Things are measured as they in a descriptive research study.

Descriptive research is further divided into the sub-categories such as case study, longitudinal study, case series study, retrospective study and cross-sectional study. Similarly, casual research design has two popular methods of research to be used by the researcher i.e. experimental and quasi-experimental method of studies.

3.2.3 Difference between the Exploratory & Conclusive Design

The exploratory research aims at enabling the researcher to dig deep into a situation by providing an insight into the issue. Conclusive research, on the other hand, aims at describing the characteristics of something. Unlike exploratory researcher, the researcher with a conclusive research design formulates a hypothesis in the beginning and then answer questions like what, where, when, who and how to test the hypothesis. The data collected in such study is countable and measurable in numbers. Sandhursen (2000) explains that the conclusive studies result in a final solution of an existing problem whereas the exploratory studies identify a range of options for problem-solving.

Moreover, the exploratory design is not restricted to one paradigm, therefore, can use either qualitative or quantitative research. On the other hand, conclusive research design makes use of the quantitative method of data collection and data analysis Nargundkar (2008), and finally presents the conclusive answers in a statically reliable data. Also compared with exploratory research, the conclusive research tends to use large sample sizes and advanced techniques to analyse the data. This provides a way to quantify and verify the findings of exploratory research.

“an exploratory study may not have as rigorous a methodology as it is used in conclusive studies, and sample sizes may be smaller. But it helps to do the exploratory study as methodically as possible if it is going to be used for major decisions about the way we are going to conduct our next study” (Nargundkar, 2008).

In short, the exploratory studies explore a research problem leaving room for further researches to be done that can be carried out using conclusive style to provide final findings of the research study.

3.2.4 Research Design of the Present Study

The design of the present study is fundamentally exploratory due to its inductive nature as the researcher aimed at exploring the major factors that influence the career decisions of teachers in private schools in District Gujrat, Pakistan. As the researcher could not locate any earlier research on the topic in District Gujrat, neither of an exploratory design nor a conclusive one. Thus, an exploratory design was the best approach to begin with and encourage further researches using conclusive design.

There are many benefits of using such type of research design. The design allows the researcher to discover new insights and new ideas contrary to collecting statistically accurate data. A most prominent advantage is the degree of flexibility and adaptability a researcher has when using the exploratory research design. This encouraged the researcher of the present study to change his direction depending on the information received. The rich information gathered in exploratory research leads to future studies that are quantifiable. The findings of the current study also lay a groundwork for further researches to be done in the future in order to quantify and verify the results using a conclusive design.

There are also some disadvantages to using the exploratory research design. Although the exploratory research is useful in gathering rich qualitative data, there is a chance of bias when interpreting such type of data. Another downside is the relatively small size of the sample which may not be an adequate and true representation of the target population. In addition, the data collected from a small number of respondents may, therefore, not be generalized to a wider population. The findings also cannot be practically used in decision making as they do not provide a final solution to the problem, however, encourage further researches around the topic.

3.3 RESEARCH METHOD

There are two types of researches, quantitative and qualitative (Bryman, 2004). The quantitative is the measurement of quantity or amount and deals with a phenomenon that can be expressed in numbers or quantity. Whereas the qualitative refers to the phenomena related to quality or kind. Both have their pros and cons of usage and choosing between two is trading off between breadth and depth. Where quantitative allow to examine a large sample size in order to collect data, the qualitative design proposes a detail insight into the issue.

3.3.1 Quantitative

Qualitative deals with investigating human behaviour as to why they think and do certain things and like or dislike certain thing. Motivation research is kind of qualitative research that aims at finding out underlying reasons behind a certain matter with the help of technique like in-depth interviews. Attitude or opinion research is another kind where researcher tries to ascertain different impressions of people a particular subject. Quantitative research is considered a hard research because it deals with explaining data in numbers compared to the soft approach of qualitative research that explore and interpret social realities.

Similarly, the comparison of two types of research design reveals that due to the deductive approach of quantitative, it deals with predicting and testing the hypothesis and therefore the results are measures statically for the reliability and validity of data (Bryman, 2004). Contrary to that, the qualitative research directly deals with the perspective of people about a certain event, action or phenomenon. This allows the researcher to express commitment to viewing of the people being studied.

Moreover, the quantitative aims at the generalisation of data collected and emphasised on breadth rather than depth of the problem and therefore takes an objective approach of collecting data (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000; Easterby-Smith et al., 2011). This type of research is preferred in situations where human resources are invasive, time is constrained, and more

intensive methods cannot be adopted (Scot et al, 2006; Brown, 2006). Furthermore, quantitative research is assumed to maximize precision and considered to be cost effective and a convenient method allowing to collect data on a large scale, however, Coolican (2004) argues that the degree of precision remains questionable even in the quantitative design of research.

3.3.2 Qualitative

In contrast to quantitative method of research, the qualitative method is mostly used for exploratory purposes and allows the researcher to understand the personal experiences of the people being studied and observe their behaviour. This type of research is usually used to study an organisational culture, its values and norms. The qualitative research aims at exploring the underlying factors and investigate the issues behind a certain phenomenon, thus a social or psychological phenomenon that is difficult to measure by using any other method is studies with the help of natural science (Creswell, 2003).

As opposed to quantitative research method, Creswell (2003) argues that the aim of qualitative approach is not generalisation and therefore emphasise on depth of phenomenon rather than breadth. This method of research is explorative, all-inclusive and universal. It focuses on the understanding of problem following an interpretive and rational approach. The qualitative studies are not rigorous rather they found to be descriptive in contrast to quantitative studies. The is the same argument as represented by Gummerson (2000) comparing positivism and interpretivism leading to objective versus subjective debate.

There are many advantages of using qualitative method of research such as qualitative research design help to explore individual feeling by identifying the pattern of behaviour (Schein, 2011). Given the fact that qualitative approach allows the researcher to understand underlying reasons, motivation and opinion about a certain phenomenon, this results in a rich data displaying dynamics and complexity of the issue. However, bias and personal subjectivity could be the downside of qualitative method.

3.3.3 Research Method of the Present Study

A qualitative research method was used to collect primary data for the present study because of an exploratory design adopted for the research. Such a method is useful when the purpose is to understand the motivations behind a given phenomenon (Chilisa, 2012). The focus of the present research study was to explore the underlying feelings and opinions of teachers and to identify and uncover the factors behind teacher turnover in the private education sector in district Gujrat, Pakistan.

The high flexibility, openness, realism and adaptiveness are the key advantages of the qualitative method of data collection. The results of such type of research are non-quantifiable and non-numerical rather textual in nature, as opposed to the quantitative research where the results are numerical. Thus, the method of data collection for the in-hand study was essentially qualitative since it involved exploring facts and presenting them in a descriptive form and not establishing a relationship between the variables.

3.4 RESEARCH APPROACH

There are many ways to arrive at the reality of something by using different thoughts and roads. The deductive and inductive reasoning are two different ways to analyse the reality and uncover the truth. The researchers usually use one of them to discover the truth. Both of them have their advantages and disadvantages.

3.4.1 Deductive Approach

Deductive approach or reasoning is an accepted, self-evident and axiomatic approach to thinking about a certain phenomenon. Gill and Johnson (2010) explain that the deductive approach deals with the existing information in order to meet the research objectives. The existing information helps to make a hypothesis determine a theory. This hypothesis is then tested by the researcher using deductive reasoning to conduct a new study. The hypothesis is either confirmed or rejected by analysing the data collected by the researcher in the process. It is like building higher stories over a solid foundation constructed by the researcher.

As long as the researcher builds the logical structure on a strong foundation, the approach ensures that the point he reaches is always going to be true.

This is a very agile and highly responsive approach and used to solve problems. It is widely used approach to testify the hypothesis made by researchers considering past and present theories and literature relevant to the topic of study. However, the method discourages the divergent thinking and therefore restricts the researcher to create a theory or generate a universal law. The approach is generally adopted to conduct quantitative research.

3.4.2 Inductive Approach

In contrast to the deductive approach, the inductive approach does not start with a pre-determined theory and axiom and the researcher needs not to follow existing information. It is opposite of deductive logic and, therefore, aims to arrive at the greater generalization of a phenomenon. This approach generates the data collection first and then explanation is presented (Gratton & Jones, 2009). The laws are derived from specific cases using the inductive reasoning. Inductive reasoning has an ability to challenge the established thought with a possibility of going wrong. As this approach is not restricted by axioms, it allows the researcher to think beyond boundaries and the result is lot more open possibilities. Due to its flexible nature, it is highly supportive of problem-solving.

In this approach, the data is usually collected by observations or unstructured way to explore the feelings and opinions of the research audience. The collected data appears to be a cluster out of which many themes and patterns emerge. The researcher then begins to generate new themes by analysis the emerging patterns. This is considered to be an ideal method of research as you can arrive at more than one reality at the same time. However, the downside of the method is the argument that incorrect observations would lead to an incorrect conclusion. The approach is generally adopted to conduct qualitative research.

3.4.3 Research Approach of the Present Study

Given the exploratory design and qualitative method of data collection, the research approach of the present study is primarily inductive, aiming to explore the existing knowledge by identifying the key reasons for teachers' turnover and developing a theory to contribute to the body of knowledge. The inductive approach adopted for the present study allowed the researcher to think beyond the boundaries while analysing the open-ended responses of the teachers in district Gujrat. This resulted in a lot of open possibilities for problem-solving.

Teachers in this research were the research audience and their opinions and feelings were explored to generate universal results. According to Collins (2010), inductive research fundamentally refers to theory developing rather theory testing (opposite to deductive approach). Therefore, the inductive approach is best suited due to the exploratory nature of the topic and qualitative method for data collection.

To sum up, following flow chart gives a clear picture of the methodology adopted for the present study.

Figure 3.3: Present study research methodology

3.5 RESEARCH STRATEGIES

Strategy refers to the process of choosing a suitable sample out of target population and best instruments for data collection.

3.5.1 Sampling Process

Luck & Rubin (1987) explains that the sampling process is consist of different steps at different levels. Such steps include to ascertain the target population, determine the sampling method, specify a sampling structure, establish the sample size and select the sample. This involves a selection of sufficient number of respondents from the target population that may best represent the population.

3.5.1.1 Population

Orodho (2009a) defines population of a research as a large group of individuals selected to test the research question. A sample is drawn from this group that represent the characteristics of all individuals selected for the study. This method of sampling is adopted where population size is generally large. According to Saunders *et al.*, (2009) sampling is of two types either probability or non-probability (*figure, 7*)

The target population of the in-hand research study was the teaching staff of primary to high level private schools in District Gujrat, Pakistan. The teachers' turnover is higher in private schools compared to public schools (Akhtar et al, 2010) that are why teachers from private schools are selected as the population of this research.

3.5.1.2 Sampling Method

Sampling methods are commonly divided into two categories, i.e. probability sampling and non-probability sampling.

Figure 3.4: Sampling Method; Source: Saunders et al, (2009)

According to Tashakkori & Teddlie (2003) probability sampling allows each possible sample within a population to be selected as a study sample. The chance for each individual to be chosen is equal, common and known. This method is primarily used in quantitative studies and involves the selection of quite a large number of sample units form the target population. Probability sampling methods are further divided into four sub-categories such as

- clustered sampling
- stratified sampling
- simple random sampling
- systematic sampling

unlike probability sampling, non-probability sampling is opposite and is considered to be more useful. This allows the researcher to select a sample that he is interested in studying. Therefore, a subjective judgement of the researcher plays a part in the selectin of a sample. Investigating sampling error in this type of sampling is almost impossible and it is also more cost-effective compared to the probability sampling (Takona, 2002). Thus, the types of non-probability sampling include;

- Quota sampling
- Judgmental/purposive sampling
- Convenience sampling
- Snowball Sampling

3.5.1.3 Sampling Method for the Present Study

Due to the exploratory design of the in-hand study, non-probability method of sampling was adopted. Under this method combination of methods at multi-stages were adopted to select sample due to the complexity of the issue being studied and due to the use of multiple data collection instruments.

Stage 1: Quota sampling was used for both sample A & B based on geographic locations (i.e., tehsils)

Stage 2: Purposive sampling was used for sample A (private schools and existing teachers)

Stage 3: Snowball sampling was used for sample B (leavers or movers)

The data for this study was obtained from two types of samples consist of current and former teachers in private schools of district Gujrat, Pakistan.

Figure 3.5: Present study sampling design

- i. Sample A respondents were the survey respondents from a sample of private schools and teachers in the district Gujrat. The teachers at the time of survey were teaching in the schools selected for the study.
- ii. Sample B respondents were the interview respondents from a sample of former teachers of private schools in district Gujrat who were either leavers (left the profession) or movers (moved to another school (private or public)).

a) Quota sampling

Quota sampling was used to select both sample 'A' and 'B'. The aim of using this sampling technique was to obtain a representative sample from the target population. In quota sampling the population is stratified in various groups on the basis of location and required sample is obtained from each stratum (STT, n.d). Thus, a desired representation of relevant sub-groups is guaranteed with this type of sampling which also increases the likelihood of true representation of the selected population (Orodho, 2012).

Private schools and teachers in District Gujrat are part of the sampling frame for the present study and are sampled on multiple stages using quota sampling. At first stage, sample frame was divided into 3 groups according to the geographic positions such as three tehsils in district Gujrat.

- i. Tehsil Sarai Alamgir
- ii. Tehsil Kharian
- iii. Tehsil Gujrat

Figure 3.6: Distribution of Pakistan on Province, Division, District and Tehsil Level

On the second stage, private schools were selected from the above mentioned three Tehsils based on the stratum of levels namely; primary, middle and high-level private schools (see figure in appendix 5).

Limitations of this method: quota sampling is not a random sampling therefore the possibility of bias is very strong. However, researcher has taken due consideration while grouping the schools according to the geographic positions and levels of the schools thus to avoid any bias in this case.

b) Purposive sampling

Purposive sampling technique was adopted to select Sample 'A' and conduct open ended survey questionnaire. Purposive sampling

“occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the judgment of the researcher. Researchers often believe that they can obtain a representative sample by using a sound judgment, which will result in saving time and money.” (Black, 2010).

Similarly, purposive sampling involves a deliberate selection of the sampling units (individual, groups or institution) to gather information which is not possible to gather from other choices (Maxwell, 1997). There is a clear method of picking the units (i.e., schools in the present study) from a well understood population.

Figure 3.7: Purposive Sampling

The researcher selected the sample units that addressed the specific purpose related to the research questions. The private institutes in district Gujrat were selected deliberately to serve the purpose of the study. Three representative schools from each tehsil, totalling 9 schools, were selected with a sample size of 250 teachers altogether. All the existing teaching staff, i.e. 250, in the selected schools were invited for the participation. This is an average number of samples as all three tehsils are not equally large or small tehsils and the sample size is relatively large for a qualitative research. The reason for selecting a large sample is to eliminate any defects associated with the sampling process of an exploratory research.

The selection of the schools is based on the researcher's own judgement. For example, schools with many branches are selected in a way that if one branch is selected in one tehsil, the other branches of the same school in other tehsils were not selected. Similarly, schools were selected at different levels such as primary, middle and high levels. Schools with a relatively large number of teaching staff were selected to get as many survey responses as possible, however, few small schools (with a smaller number of teaching staff) were also

selected to conduct the open-ended questionnaires survey. The choice of schools was also made according to the schools' popularity in terms of their attractive recruiting policies.

Limitation: this sampling technique can be bias since it involves the researcher's own judgement however due care has been taken in the selection of sample to avoid any bias. The sample of the exploratory research is usually small leading to credibility defects; however, the researcher has included a relatively large sample to eliminate the problem.

c) Snowball sampling

Snowball sampling is also known as referral sampling in non-probability sampling techniques. In this sampling, existing sample subjects refer to other sample subject with similar characteristics for the study. This is a very useful technique for the researcher to identify the potential subjects that are hard to locate in the population otherwise. Generally, one or two sample subjects are found initially and then they are asked to identify more subjects. Upon finding the required sample size, the sample subjects are made aware to stop recruiting more subjects.

For the present study, snowball sampling was used to select sample 'B', that included departed teachers who were either leavers (left profession) or movers (move to another school). Since it was hard for the researcher to identify and locate such teachers, snowball technique was used to select sufficient number of subjects. 2 teachers were initially located who identified further subjects to be recruited for the study.

Total 8 drop out teachers were selected using this technique and contacted for conducting the semi-structured interviews. This method allowed the researcher to take and compare opinions of existing as well as drop-out teachers for better understanding of the salient factors behind teacher turnover.

3.5.2 Data Collection Instruments for Present Study

Both secondary and primary data collection methods were used to collect data for the present research study. Since it was difficult to incorporate all the tools and techniques to collect primary qualitative data in an exploratory research, a couple of techniques were adopted and discussed in this paper, i.e., open-ended survey questionnaire and interview techniques were adopted.

Figure 3.8: Data Collection tools of present Study

3.5.2.1 Secondary Research

Collins (2010) defines secondary data as the data that has been previously collected by another researcher. A completely new topic for research that has not been conducted earlier is almost impossible. The review of previous studies on the relevant topic is the best strategy to start with and highly advantageous when it comes to plan the research and design the methodology. The previous researches help in designing the present goals for research. Reuse of most useful information in new surveys allows the researchers to expand on the topic and help them make a perfect plan of action to conduct their research. The problems can be better understood through reviewing the other research projects within the same domain

prior to conducting the actual research. Social media, blogs, and other forums are also helpful nowadays in understanding the subject matter and people's opinions and behaviour about a certain topic.

Secondary research was carried out by reviewing previous literature for collecting the research data to build a theoretical foundation using following sources.

- Case studies regarding teachers' turnover and Pakistani private education sector
- Journals and articles
- Books
- Reports
- Digital and print media
- Internet sources and database such as Emerald, Sage, EBSCO, Pro-Quest, Google Scholar etc

3.5.2.2 Primary Research

According to Saunders et al., (2009), primary data is the raw data collected by the researcher only for the purpose of the research in hand. Primary research for the purpose of this study was conducted using two techniques. First is through a comprehensive survey questionnaire on private schools' teaching staff with open-ended questions aiming to explore the major job-related factors behind teachers' turnover in this sector. Questionnaires are an efficient and quick way to obtain a relatively large amount of information from a large sample of people. Gay (1992) argues that the participants are free to express their opinions or views and also make suggestions when responding to questionnaires. The most common exploratory researches take place in the form of open-ended questions. Asking participants to respond to the closed-ended questions (such as multiple choice) is in other way forcing the participants to respond in a certain way by picking between the options made available to them by the researcher. This leads to a bias and surrogate information. The respondents are also given a

choice of picking “other please specify” option, however, the answer is not used statistically and therefore defeat the actual purpose.

The researcher believes in the importance of teachers' voice therefore semi-structured interviews were used as a second method for primary data collection. Both interviewer and interviewee get an opportunity in such type of interviews to discuss in more detail on the under-investigated topic. The interviews in the current study were conducted with former teachers who left teaching private schools' sector in District Gujrat. This approach helped the researcher in the collection of data also from both in-service and out-of-service teachers.

a) Open-ended survey questionnaire

In order to obtain data from a sufficient number of teachers, open-ended survey questionnaires were used to collect primary data from sample “A”, that are in-service teachers in the district. 250 survey questionnaires⁷ were distributed among teachers of 9 sample private schools in three tehsils in district Gujrat. Specific selected schools⁸ were accessed in person and after obtaining an oral consent from the principals of the selected schools and knowing the total number of teaching staff, the survey questionnaires were handed over to the principals in a folder to be placed in the staffroom. They were advised to only collect the folders from the staffroom once the completed and uncompleted surveys were returned and placed back in the folders by the teachers themselves. This was to maintain the confidentiality and anonymity of the participant teachers. The folders were then

⁷ 250 survey questionnaires were distributed to sample A and 204 were returned with a response rate of 81.6%

⁸ The survey distribution was carried out by either going straight to school or after making an appointment with the principal over the telephone.

collected from the principal's office. The use of open-ended questionnaires helped the researcher to reveal the unanticipated findings without being influenced by the researcher.

The open-ended questionnaires are exploratory in nature. This is the best tool that allows the research audience to provide feedback and share how they feel about the topic being studied. The method of collecting data generates new ideas and topics that a researcher may have not previously thought of. Although the open-ended questions generate a large amount of information which is somewhat difficult to analyse, however, such type of data informs the future researchers to conduct further studies by indicating import trends.

Although there many advantages of using questionnaire, there are some disadvantages too. Generally, questionnaires require simple questions to be asked however in an open-ended questionnaire the questions can be complex to address the research problem. Another disadvantage of a questionnaire is the lack of control over the respondents' environment, therefore, there is a possibility of getting few questions to be skipped by the respondent leading to a low response rate. Moreover, there is no opportunity to probe the answers and the answers must be considered final. Bryman (2004) claims that questionnaires are a good method to measure the views however they do not measure actions. However, if used properly, questionnaires in the form of open-ended questions provide sufficiently reliable information explaining the underlying views and assumptions of the target population.

- Sequence of questions

The questionnaire consisted of two sections (*appendix 3*). The first section included the demographic information of the respondents such as their age, gender, qualification, marital status and teaching experience. In the second section, respondents were asked opinion-sought questions requiring them to express their perceptions, feelings and thoughts related to the subject matter. The questions began with simple and less complex questions slowly progressing to opinionated questions.

- Pilot test survey

The initial draft of the questionnaire was pre-tested in order to ascertain the clarity and suitability of the questions. This was to ensure that questions are not ambiguous or offensive, are clearly understandable and generate the response required to meet the objectives of the study. The pre-testing was done on a convenient sample of 10 teachers randomly chosen from a local school. Sekaran (2000) claims that a convenient sample of small number of respondents is common for pilot tests. The teachers were requested to pick any difficult wordings and overlapping questions in order to validate the questions. This was also helpful to pick any errors and correct them before the actual survey was conducted. Some overlapping questions and the questions giving contradictory information were detected and removed.

b) Interview

The interview is another very useful technique to collect qualitative data for research. This is the verbal two-way conversation between the researcher and the sample from target population in order to collect relevant data on the topic being studied. McNamara (1999) states that the interview is a useful technique to understand an individual' personal experiences in order to pursue in-depth information related to the subject matter.

The interview can be personal face to face or telephonic as well as structured or unstructured. The interviewer introduces himself and explains the reasons for conducting the interview. The respondents are also informed as to where, why and how the information will be used. The interviewer answers any queries the respondent may have in relation to the personal details and information provided and assures him of the confidentiality of the data.

Probing can be used to encourage the respondent to answer relevantly and completely, however, the respondent is free to express his feelings, opinions and perception (Berry, 1999). The interviewer can audio or videotape the responses with the permission of the respondent and transcribe them in writing after the interview for the purpose of analysis. Otherwise, he can write down the responses at the time of interview.

The personal interview is costly compared to telephonic interview or other methods such as mail or computer surveys. In case of face to face interview, the respondent may not feel comfortable in disclosing certain information which is a downside of the technique. The demographic characteristics and personal approach of the interviewer also influence the responses in some cases. Similarly, the influence of cultural aspects on the responses is also reported where in some cultures female participants hesitate to give an interview to male interviewers.

The primary data was also collected through semi structured open-ended interviews from sample B⁹, i.e., teachers who left teaching or move to another private or public school in the District. Specific open-ended questions (*appendix 4*) were used to help teachers reflect on broad topic areas. The same open-ended questions were asked from each respondent to facilitate faster interview and faster data analysis and comparison. However, a degree of freedom and adaptability was still allowed to get the information within the topic area.

The former teachers of sample B include those who;

- left and were unemployed
- left private school and were working in the government sector
- left school and were working at the college level
- left and were working in another profession

8 out of 11 former teachers agreed to participate in the study. 5 out of 8 were interviewed in person whereas 3 were interviewed on telephone taking 45 minutes to an hour to complete

⁹ For Sample B, 11 teachers were contacted initially for interviewed. 9 agreed to participate. 1 out of 9 could not participate due to their family engagements. So total 8 participated. This was a response rate of 72.7%.

each interview. Only 2 interviewees agreed to tape record their voices. A detailed review of the literature on teaching as a career was carried out to influence the interview guide and process.

Job Areas covered in the interview:

- employment history
- Entry into the teaching field
- The positive aspect of the school left
- The negative aspect of the school left
- Opinion on aspects such as salary and work recognition
- Reasons for leaving school
- Factors that could have changed the decision to leave
- Recommendations/suggestion for teacher retention

3.6 DATA ANALYSIS

According to Hancock (2002), an analysis of the data collected during a research project involves summarising the big amount of data to present the outcomes in the most effective way communicating all important features. Both quantitative and qualitative data analysis process start on a basic level by labelling or coding every item of information so that the differences and similarities between all the different items can be recognized. However, coding qualitative data requires a different technique.

3.6.1 Qualitative Data Analysis Techniques

Since the nature of the primary data collected for the present study is qualitative, there are quite complex methods to analysis such data. The problems associated with the qualitative data analysis methods stressed on using these methods cautiously and with constant awareness in order to offset the bias and subjectivity of the researcher.

The qualitative data is a non-numeric data presenting the opinions and views of the people under study. Such data includes the answers to open-ended questions in the form of an interview or questionnaire, discussion in the form of a focus group or a researcher's own notes from an observation. The analysis involves critique and discussion without the use of numbers and calculations. Open questions in the form of interview or questionnaire produce results that are unanticipated and unexpected, making the research more original and valuable. However, analysing and managing the data collected from open-ended questionnaires and interviews is somehow difficult.

Following are different techniques to analyse the qualitative data.

- Grounded Theory: this is a systematic process of analysing data to construct a theory operating inductively (Strauss et al, 1994)
- Narrative Analysis: this technique is used to analyse the qualitative data collected using field notes in form of stories, personal experiences, photographs, journals or conversations (Clandinin & Connelly, 2000).
- Framework Analysis: The framework analysis is often considered similar to the grounded theory as new theories are often generated, however the primary purpose of this technique is the description and interpretation of something happening in a specific scenario (Snape and Spencer, 2003).
- Discourse Analysis: the origin of this analysis is the discipline of sociology and According to Snape and Spencer (2003), this is about *"Examining the way knowledge is produced within different discourses and the performances, linguistic styles and rhetorical devices used in particular accounts."*
- Thematic Content Analysis: Thematic content analysis is "a procedure for the categorisation of verbal or behavioural data, for purposes of classification, summarisation and tabulation" (Hancock, 2002). The aim of context analysis is to make sense of the primary raw data collected. This technique involves highlight the important messages, features or findings after coding and classifying data. This also refers categorising and indexing the data. The analysis is generally done on two levels;

- Basic or manifest level: at this level a description is made on what was said without making any comment or generating any theories as to why or how.
- Higher or latent level: at this level an interpretation and implication of the response is made.

3.6.2 Data Analysis of the Current Study

3.6.2.1 Current study data analysis method

For the purpose of analysing qualitative data for the present study and to understand the underlying factors behind turnover issue in private education sector in Pakistan outlined in the research questions, the method of thematic content analysis was adopted from Glaser & Strauss' grounded theory approach and their work on content analysis (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) aiming to reveal and comprehend a bigger picture in order to describe the phenomenon. The thematic content analysis is best suited when the primary data is collected through interviews and open questionnaires. This is useful to analyse the data as a whole. In this method the data was analysed in the following three stages:

Stage 1 (Coding): At the first stage codes were developed and explained as categorization of data. Codes represent a theme or an idea in the form of a single word or short phrase, however, expressing meaningful title. Coding is a complex method including range of events and activities. This step is further divided into the following three steps:

- Open coding is an initial step that involves breaking of data into conceptual components. The raw data was organised in categories to make sense of it.
- Axial coding is the second step of coding where categories of open coding were interconnected and linked with each other.
- Selective coding is final step in coding in which a story was formulated through the linked categories of axial coding.

There is many software available to make the steps of coding for qualitative data analysis easier for a researcher such as NVIVO, Hyper Research, Atlas it 6.0, Max QDA and many

others. A researcher can also do manual coding using range of folders, wallets etc to keep similar themes and categories in one folder. For the present study, the manual coding was used though this method of data analysis is considered to be time consuming, labour intensive and outdated. However, data collected for the current research study was in the form of hard copies due to limited use of technology in Pakistan. Therefore, after realising that paperwork was more convenient and less challenging, manual coding was used to sort out the data.

Stage 2 (interpretation): In the second stage of qualitative data analysis using thematic content analysis technique, common themes, patterns and relationships among these patterns were identified in relation to the codes specified at first stage of analysis. Unlike the quantitative analysis, there are no universally applicable tools to apply and generate findings in the qualitative data analysis.

The interpretation of data at this stage involves the identification of words and phrases most commonly used by the participants and interpreting them to make a sense of the data. A researcher's own critical and analytical thinking has a role to play in the interpretation of such type of data analysis.

Stage 3 (critical evaluation): At the last stage of qualitative data analysis, the findings of the participants' responses were compared with the literature review in order to identify and discuss the similarities and differences. The outcome of the critical evaluation was linked with the research aim and objectives. Some major themes within the findings of the primary research transcripts were also used as quotations in the analysis chapter in order to highlight the similarities and possible contradictions.

In the current research, the primary goal of conducting the analysis using thematic analysis was to get the raw data into a more manageable document preserving the integrity of each participants' views. Broader patterns and themes were searched across 204 open-ended survey questionnaires; and 8 interviews. Each individual's response contributed towards the interpretation of the context.

Thus, the analysis of present study data mainly focused on finding the factors that teachers have identified as most strongly influencing their career decisions, whether to leave or stay in the teaching profession. The open-ended questions in both the interview and the survey were designed in a way as to encourage the teachers to reflect their experiences over the time. Both existing and departed teachers were asked to express their feelings about the working conditions, salaries, rewards, support, workload and other work-related aspects, assumptions, and expectations.

3.6.2.2 Current study data analysis process

The process of the analysis began with coding all the responses one by one. During the process of identifying major factors behind teachers' career decisions, many similarities across the codes became evident. After recognising such similarities, the written record of the common themes was identified describing them in as much detail as possible in order to understand the issue of teacher turnover.

By going through all the responses one by one, the list of initial codes was developed out of which emerging themes were identified. During the process, wherever a new theme was identified which did not match the existing themes of the list created previously, then a new category of theme was created. Similarly, when common items were identified that could fit in more than one category, then a single category of broader and more inclusive item was created. The purpose of doing so was to use less categories that would be the best and accurate description of the factors identified in data collection. The list of themes and categories were continually reorganised and refined.

The manual coding process was used to facilitate the initial coding of narrative data provided by the participant. Though the process is considered to require more time and effort, the researcher find it more convenient because the raw data was all handwritten. Therefore, an excel spreadsheet was used to draw a clearer representation of the data. The final results represent the factors identified for the career decision of existing and departed teachers.

Throughout the research report, phase 1 participants are referred as “existing teachers” (ET) whereas phase 2 participants are referred as “departed or former teachers” (FT).

3.6.2.3 Data cleaning & organization of both phases

a) Phase 1: Survey responses

At the first stage, all the hand-written survey responses were organised according to the schools in three tehsils starting the analysis process tehsil by tehsil. The responses were already kept in separate folders for each school in each tehsil. The initial coding of the answers was started with responses from all 3 schools in each tehsil totalling 9 schools.

The demographic information of teachers was analysed, first of all, from each tehsil. After that each and every response was coded. Because of open ended questions, there were all different responses. Some responses were quite similar in nature, however, the way to express them was different so they were coded under one category of theme.

For example, providing reasons to join the teaching profession one said, “I love teaching very much” and the other said, “teaching is my passion” so they were coded under one category as “love/passion for teaching”.

Therefore, where the responses were very close, the number of times it appeared was added instead of rewriting them. Once a list of coded answers was made, the emerging themes and patterns were identified. The categories which were not very frequent were listed as “other” in the thematic analysis.

The similar process was done for the other schools in the same tehsil moving on to the second and third tehsils and schools, thus completing the initial coding and thematic analysis for all the survey responses.

Lastly, a final categorization of the emerging themes out of all three tehsils was made. This method allowed to compare the emerging themes in each tehsil and then analysing them as a whole on district level.

b) Phase 2: Interview responses

The interviews were analysed thematically using the same manual coding process employed for survey responses. The interviewers' responses were recorded as a constructed portrait drawn from the information they provided. Each portrait included their demographics, their career aspirations, reasons to enter and leave the profession, their opinions and feelings about certain work-related aspects such as work environment and support in the schools they have left and the recommendations and suggestions that could have changed their decision to leave or that could contribute in their decision to join back. Some personal factors interacting with the work factors were also recorded. Major themes were recorded around the material provided by each individual respondent exploring the following key topics/themes:

- i. Entry into the profession: reasons of becoming teachers
- ii. Exit from the school/profession: underlying reasons behind decisions to leave and what could have changed their decision to leave.
- iii. Current job role, reasons for choice of new role and how this is different to teaching.
- iv. Minimizing turnover: recommendations to reduce teachers' turnover in general.

Other key variables such age, gender, qualification and teaching experience were also explored where possible, although the impact of such individual characteristics on turnover is not the research purpose. This helped to perform a rigorous analysis of the data collected resulting in a systematic and strategic interpretation of what was said by the teachers in relation to the subject matter.

3.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Much importance has been awarded to the ethical issue while conducting research studies particularly those involving human participation. Babbie (2009) has listed important ethical considerations a researcher should take into account during data collection from participants such as their willingness to participate, the anonymity of their identities and confidentiality

of the data, their safety, fair reporting and honesty on part of the researcher. These are discussed in more detail below.

3.7.1 Willingness to participate

The most important ethical consideration is to seek the participants' willingness who volunteer themselves to participate in the research study. For the present study, the teachers volunteered to participate and were not forced in any way. Principals from the representative schools were briefed on the objectives of the research orally as well as a written information sheet was also provided. An informed consent was sought as a vital ingredient to participate. Principals were also advised to orally make teaching staff aware that they were free to participate in or withdraw from the study at any time during the research. The information sheet explaining the volunteer participation, free withdrawal from the study and confidentiality and anonymity was attached with each questionnaire distributed among teachers of all representative schools so that the teachers do not feel enforced by the principals to participate in the study.

Similarly, for the purpose of collecting data from teachers who had departed from a private school, the voluntary participation was sought. Since they were approached in person, they were also given information about the purpose of the research study and to keep the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses to avoid any hesitation on their part.

3.7.2 Confidentiality and Anonymity

For the purpose of confidentiality, neither the names of the schools nor the individuals are mentioned in the study. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of information provided by them in order to motivate them to willingly participate in the study. The anonymity of their personal identities was ensured during the participation. Although, the identities of teachers who participated in the interview revealed to the researcher however they were kept under strict confidentiality and the participants were ensured by the researcher not to disclose their identities at any stage during the research or after. The participants were informed that the data would be used for analysis and generating results.

They were assured that the names of schools will not be revealed in the research findings and final report.

3.7.3 Safety of Participants

No physical, mental or emotional harm was inflicted upon the participants of the research. The participants were assured of the safety by confirming that no harm would be imposed on them should they participate or do not participate in the study. Few questions related to the demographics of the teachers were included such as their age, gender, qualification and experience, however, the information was only used to analyse as to how many male or female teachers with which age group, degree and experience have participated in the study. No unnecessary pressure was exercised on the participants of the research to yield any specific responses.

3.7.4 Fairness and honesty

The respondents were not deceived at any point while briefing the true purpose of the research study. The purpose was communicated clearly using a suitable language. The participants were not given any misleading or false statements in order to collect the data for the research. The purpose of the research and the identity of the researcher was honestly and fairly reported to the participants. The data was collected without making any false offers.

3.7.5 Analysis and Results

Due care has been taken by the researcher to collect the data. Similarly, the analysis of the data also involves careful considerations to formulate the results. The results are the true outcome of in-depth analysis to the best of researchers' knowledge.

4 CHAPTER FOUR: ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 4 delineates upon the research results and key findings of the in-hand study after analysing and interpreting the data collected with the help of thematic analysis and use of manual coding and excel spread sheets for the purpose of the study. The study examined the underlying factors behind teachers' turnover in three tehsils of District Gujrat private schools. The data was collected in two halves where in the first half, the existing teachers of 9 purposely selected private schools of three tehsils, (3 schools in each tehsil), were surveyed using open-ended questionnaires whereas in the second half, 8 former teachers who taught in any private school in District Gujrat were interviewed. The results have drawn from a comprehensive analysis of the raw data gathered through survey questionnaire administered to existing teachers at the private schools in district Gujrat and also through interviews conducted from departed teachers selected for the study.

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data as a whole. The primary goal of conducting the analysis in this way was to get the raw data into a more manageable document preserving the integrity of each participants' views. Broader patterns and themes were searched across 204 open-ended survey questionnaires and 8 interviews. Each individual's response contributed towards the interpretation of the context.

Throughout the research report, phase 1 participants are referred as "existing teachers" (ET) whereas phase 2 participants are referred as "departed or former teachers" (FT).

4.2 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILING

4.2.1 Phase 1: Questionnaire Profiling

The purpose of phase 1 open-ended questionnaire complement the analysis by providing direct answers to the question related to teachers' reasons behind joining teaching profession, their thoughts about the climate and characteristics of the school they are teaching in, the importance of salary and recognition of their work, their feelings on getting a recognition, their satisfaction level and their reasons to stay in the school or leave if they decide to leave in future.

Given the qualitative nature of topic, phase 1 consisted to a relatively large sample. Therefore, findings have been quantified where appropriate. The analysis of the questionnaire data addresses all the research questions.

Following is the total number of schools and teachers studied through survey questionnaire in phase 1 of the data collection:

Table 4.1: Number of schools and teachers studied for survey

Number of schools		Number of teachers	
Expected	Actual	Expected	Actual
9	9	250	204

Table 2 shows that 9 deliberately selected private schools were targeted to collect primary data through open-ended questionnaire. 250 surveys were distributed in the selected schools however, 204 were returned completed. The response rate is more than 50% of an expected coverage in a survey research, therefore, it is considered an acceptable coverage (Amin, 2005).

All the teaching staff in the selected schools were invited to participate in the study and the surveys were given to either the administration or principal of the school in order to distribute those amongst the teachers. However, some schools returned few unfilled surveys and some also did not return few surveys saying that they were lost by the teachers. Thus, 250 surveys were distributed in 9 private schools and 204 were returned filled which is a response rate of 82% (table 3). The researcher is confident that response rate is large enough to represent the views of targeted population and therefore the findings of the study are realistic.

Table 4.2: Response rate by Schools in each Tehsil

Tehsils	School 1		School 2		School 3		Total		
Sarai Alamgir	D	R	D	R	D	R	D	R	%
	20	14	38	35	52	52	110	101	92%
Kharian	D	R	D	R	D	R	D	R	%
	29	22	21	20	15	11	65	53	81.5%
Gujrat	D	R	D	R	D	R	D	R	%
	10	10	25	18	40	22	75	50	67%
Overall	Total distributed= 250 Total received filled= 204 Total response percentage= 82%								

(key: D=distributed, R=returned)

The above table 3 shows the distribution of survey questionnaires in 3 primaries to high private schools in each three tehsils of district Gujrat totalling 9 schools and an overall response rate of 82%. Table 4 below shows the percentage of survey responses based on gender:

Table 4.3: Questionnaire responses based on gender

Male	53	26%
Female	151	74%
Total	204	100%

The table shows that there are relatively large number of female teachers currently teaching in private school of district Gujrat therefore female teachers represent a large sample compared to male teachers.

4.2.2 Phase 2: Interviews Profiling

The purpose of the second phase of the research was to conduct up to 8 interviews with teachers who departed from private schools in district Gujrat. Initial questions were similar to the questions in survey; however, this phase of the research was slightly changed.

As the interview participants were the former teachers so the main focus was to not only understand the reasons behind their leave decisions from a particular private school in District Gujrat but to discuss and explore the possible solutions to retain the existing staff in the profession to avoid high turnover in private education sector.

Thus, 8 semi-structured interviews were conducted from former teachers using questions related to the factors behind each teacher's exit from a particular school. The semi-structured interview guide (*see appendix 4*) had been used to design questions in a flexible manner that allowed the researcher to change questions to an individual participant where appropriate. The participant teachers were both male and female and ranging different subject teachers.

The interview respondents were the teachers who have departed from private schools. 6 were female teachers and 2 were male (*table, 5*).

Table 6 shows that out of 6 female teachers, 3 were teaching in another private school at the time of interview and are named as “movers”. 2 teachers were currently unemployed and 1 joined a profession other than teaching (named as “Leavers”). Both male teachers were teaching in the government sector as permanent employees after leaving the private schools (government schools’ teachers, “GST”). All these 8 teachers are referred as “former teachers” throughout the report.

Table 4.4: Interview responses based on gender

Female	6	75%
Male	2	25%
Total	8	100%

Table 4.5: Demographic details of interviewees

Teachers’ pseudonyms	Gender	Category	Current status
Esha	Female	Mover	Private college teacher
Faisal	Male	Mover	Government schoolteacher
Kiran	Female	Leaver	Unemployed
Naseer	Male	Mover	Government schoolteacher
Nimra	Female	Mover	Private school teacher
Nadia	Female	Leaver	Unemployed
Sara	Female	Mover	Private school teacher
Sameen	Female	Leaver	Retail

4.3 KEY RESEARCH FINDINGS

Following *table 7* shows the key research findings with themes and sub-themes, followed by *table 8*, which includes an example of how the questions have been analysed to reach and present the findings of the research.

Table 4.6: Key Themes and Sub-themes

Research Questions		Key Themes	Sub-Themes	Sub-Sub-Themes
Q1	What is the current scenario of teachers' turnover in private schools' sector in Pakistan?	Drivers of Teaching Career	Reasons of becoming teacher	Cultural Reasons
				Emotional Reasons
				Social Reasons
				Personal Reasons
		Impressions of Teaching Career	Importance of workplace components in particular schools	Salary
				Recognition
	Job Satisfaction			
Q2	What are the factors behind teachers 'turnover in district Gujrat?	Factors of Teacher Turnover in Gujrat	Lack of Support	Collegial support
				Administration support
				Management & Principal support
				Heavy workload
				Dissatisfaction with working conditions
				student issues
	Low salary & lack of monetary rewards			
	Personal issues			
Q3	What staff retention strategies are available to retain teachers in Gujrat?	Staff retention strategies based on responses		Provide facilities
				Provide enough support
				Salary increments & monetary rewards
				Appreciation & recognition of work
				Decrease in workload
				Improved students
				Respect of teachers
				Availability of resources
	Other factors			
Q4	How can a staff retention framework be developed to retain teachers?	Framework of retention (section 6.3.2, figure 23)		

Table 4.7: Sample analysis of one question: reasons to join teaching profession

THEME	SUB-THEMES	CODES	EXAMPLE COMMENTS
Drivers of Teaching Career	Cultural Reasons	Nobility of profession Respectful profession Good for women	Teaching is a very noble profession and I always wanted to become a teacher. Teaching is a Prophet's profession and therefore it is very respectful. I realized teaching is the best of profession especially in our community.
	Emotional Reasons	Love/passion for teaching Love for favourite subject/teacher Family profession	My love for teaching is natural because my father was a teacher and he always inspired me. I have a great interest in teaching my favorite subjects such as chemistry and biology. I studied in this school, I was impressed by the school system and teaching profession. I was so inspired of my English teacher in high school that I decided to become a teacher myself. Teaching is in my family profession and I love teaching.
	Social Reasons	Contribute in society Share knowledge Make a difference	Wanted to share my knowledge and be a role model. I love to spread knowledge among children I wanted to make a difference in the lives of others, and I think teaching is the best profession to do that. I wanted to bring positive change in society.
	Personal Reasons	Entered temporarily Financial reasons Wanted experience Hobby	I wanted to use free time in some activity. I entered as helper to cover up a vacant seat on temporary basis while I was waiting for my BA results. Entered teaching profession because needed to work. Later started liking teaching. I wanted experience in any field. I desperately needed a job to meet my expenses.

4.4 DRIVERS OF & IMPRESSIONS OF TEACHING CAREER

4.4.1 Reasons of Becoming a Teacher

The reasons to enter teaching profession show initial aspirations of teachers to join the profession. The findings imply that participants were initially very interested to join the profession. When asked to state the reasons of joining teaching profession the responses of the teachers from both phases were as follows.

4.4.1.1 Phase 1 Findings

Existing teachers were surveyed in the first phase of the data collection. Following responses were discovered in their statements regarding their inspirations to enter teaching profession.

Figure 4.1: ETs' reasons for becoming teachers

Teaching is appeared to be the noblest of profession due to the fact that Muslim community in Pakistan relate this with Prophet's choice of profession. Moreover, as most of the participants under study were female teachers, thus they consider teachings highly respectful especially for women. There is a stereotype attached with the career choice for women in Pakistani community where other professions are held less suitable for women compared to teaching. Thus, 26% existing teachers pointed out that the nobility and dignity of the profession was their reason to join teaching as a career.

The love, passion and inspiration to teach is the second most prominent reason (21%) the study has found behind ET's entry into the profession. A desire to teach a specific subject is also found to be a passion for many teachers. One teacher stated that,

Several teachers are inspired to enter teaching profession due to the fact that they are influenced by someone else already in teaching, such as parents, another family member, friend or their own former teachers. This, being the second most cited reason, shows the value of teaching profession.

A desire to work with young students is found to be another reason for entering into the profession as this is said to be a knowledge contribution in their lives. The study has found that 18% existing teachers joined the profession because they wanted to contribute into the

society positively by spreading knowledge and contributing in the lives of their students and make a difference.

Moreover, the results show quite a large number of existing teachers believe that teaching itself is a learning opportunity for teachers. Thus, 16% existing teachers mentioned that teaching is a profession where the teacher teaches as well as learns. These teachers expressed that they wanted to gain knowledge by joining teaching profession and develop their personal learning and skills.

Along with the above mentioned most commonly cited reasons there were other reasons mentioned by existing teachers as shown in the *figure 12*, such as financial reasons, temporary entry into the profession, hobby, salary and benefits etc.

4.4.1.2 Phase 2 Findings

Former teachers were interviewed at the second stage of data collection. Majority of former teachers (5 out of 8) said that teaching was their career aspiration before they enter the profession whereas 3 said that they entered temporarily into this profession however they started liking the profession later. When they were asked to give reasons for becoming teachers, they gave following responses.

Figure 4.2: FTs' reasons for becoming teachers

The responses of former teachers are quite similar to existing teachers and, surprisingly, nobility of teaching profession again emerged as the top most cited reasons behind former

teachers' entry into the teaching field at 33% and the love, passion and inspiration for teaching is further identified as the second most commonly found reason at 20%.

2 out of 8 teachers mentioned that they joined to spread knowledge and 2 mentioned that they joined temporarily, however, they started liking the profession later and therefore continue in the same profession by moving to another schools.

A couple of former teachers also stated that they entered the field because teaching is a family profession for them as many of their close and extended family members are also in this profession. For some teachers teaching itself is a learning process and contribute in teachers' knowledge gain whereas few consider teaching a decent hobby.

4.4.1.3 Cumulative reasons to become teachers

Figure 4.3: Cumulative reasons to become teachers

There are two types of teachers, first who enter the profession taking it as a career choice whereas other type only enters temporarily however the schools' environment and work component such as salary, support, work recognition and job satisfaction influence them to make teaching their permanent career. Teachers' reasons to enter the profession show their initial interest and passion however, their dissatisfaction with either schools in particular or

with teaching job in general led to their departure. The current research has identified the cumulative reasons as to why teachers in Pakistan join teaching profession in the first place that generated following sub-subthemes.

a) Cultural reasons

Reasons to enter teaching profession such as nobility and respect attached with the teaching profession especially in Pakistani community are categorised as cultural reasons. Hence, teachers of private schools in district Gujrat from both phases of data collection has predominantly stated nobility and dignity of the teaching profession as their main reason to enter this profession. Teachers mentioned that teaching is a profession of prophets therefore they consider it the noblest of all profession.

“Teaching is a prophet's profession and therefore it is very respectful in our community.”

Many said that teachers are mostly respected in the community especially women. As there were more female participants under study, thus the gender differences could not be identified in this context. On the other hand, more female teachers in teaching profession, especially in private schools, also show that the nobility and respect attached with the profession in Pakistani culture is primary reason for female teachers to join teaching profession.

b) Emotional reasons

Many teachers said to enter teaching profession due to some kind of emotional attachments. These include attachments with their own primary or high schools, with their own teacher(s) and with their favourite subject(s) at the time of studying. One teacher stated that,

“I have a great interest in teaching my favorite subjects such as chemistry and biology.”

Another teacher who was inspired from her own teacher and who became their motivation to enter the profession stated that,

“I was so inspired of my English teacher in high school that I decided to become a teacher myself.”

Some of these teachers mentioned that they have an emotional affiliation with their own primary schools and therefore they love to teach in the same school. Some teachers are inspired to enter teaching profession due to the fact that they consider this a family profession because this was also their parent(s) career.

“My love for teaching is natural because my father was a teacher and he always inspired me.”

Thus, emotional reasons appeared as one of the key drivers to enter teaching profession for many teachers.

c) Social reasons

Social contributions such as increase the knowledge of others, spread wisdom, make difference and contribute in the lives of young students are also found to be prominent reasons to join the teaching profession. These socially worthwhile motivations are known as altruistic motivations in the previous studies. For instance, one teacher mentioned that;

“I wanted to be a role model for young children and share my knowledge with them.”

Another teacher was found stating that;

“I wanted to make a difference in the lives of others, and I think teaching is the best profession to do that.”

Teachers in district Gujrat private schools are mostly found to enter the teaching profession because they wanted to teach young children and make a positive contribution in their lives.

However, upon finding poor working conditions in a particular school e.g., lack of facilities and enough support, it became challenging for them to continue and therefore they quit or intend to quit.

d) Personal reasons

Unlike intrinsic motivations, the motivational preferences of some to join teaching as career are more personal and extrinsic. The current research has also found teachers' personal reasons to join teaching. Some teachers are found to state that they initially entered the profession on temporary basis, however, they started liking the profession after a while. One teacher mentioned in the interview that;

I entered as helper to cover up a vacant seat on temporary basis while I was waiting for my BA results. But after a while I found that this is the best profession and I decided to stay in the profession.

I desperately needed a job to meet my expenses.

They stated that their job satisfaction increased upon finding positive school characteristics such as enough support, good working conditions and teaching material. Other personal reasons found incorporate teaching as hobby, professional support from family and friends. One interviewee respondent stated that;

"I was unemployed after graduation. I wanted to use free time in some activity, so basically, I was looking for a hobby.... And, I joined a local school for teaching"

Few teachers also stated that they wanted to gain knowledge by teaching because teaching itself is a learning process for them, whereas some other teachers joined to meet their financial needs.

4.4.2 Impression of workplace components in Career Decisions

4.4.2.1 Phase 1 Findings

a) Salary

76% serving teachers agreed that salary is very important in their career decisions. There are number of reasons they mentioned as to why they think that salary is important for them. Most (61%) teachers think the financial reasons to be the reason of importance of salary. They said that teachers like any other employees have to support themselves and their families, and that money is very important to live a life. For instance, one teacher mentioned that:

“Yes, salary is very important because one has to pay their bills and expenses and we all know that money matters.”

24.5% teachers said that salary is the reward of the hard work and effort teachers put in while teaching. While 11.5% said that it is the basic right of employee to get salary because they spent their time in schools like other employees are paid for their work and time. These teachers said that teachers deserve to be paid like all other employees and in some cases, they said, teaching profession should be highly paid in terms of salary compared to other professions as teachers contribute in the society by making up students' lives.

In addition, 24% current teachers do not consider salary as to be the factor behind career decision. These teachers mention that they are teaching because they love to teach and for that reason, salary is not the primary factor for their decision to enter, stay or leave the profession. To these teachers' other factors such as, respect, good environment of a school, encouraging leadership, supportive management and administration are more important in their career decisions.

b) Recognition

Responding to an open-ended question, current teachers expressed their feeling as good, proud, satisfied and motivated upon receiving recognition of their work. Teachers who did not receive any recognition of their good work expressed themselves as to be disappointed.

Recognition of the work in form of a verbal appreciation, monetary reward and incentive is highly important for 97% existing teachers to feel satisfied at job and therefore contribute to stay in teaching or in a particular school. Only 3% current teachers are found to state that recognition does not matter for them. They pointed out that it is not very important for them whether they are recognised or not because they get paid for the work they are doing.

Teachers who agree to the importance of recognition in their career decisions gave many reasons to believe so. 52% teachers believe that recognition in any form increase the productivity of teachers. Teachers are encouraged to work better and give good results if they are recognised for their efforts. One teacher stated that;

“Of course, it is very important for me to receive recognition for my good work.... When I am recognised and appreciated, I feel motivated to work better next time.”

In addition, it is their human nature and instinct to be recognised for 12.5% existing teachers. Everyone like to be praised and appreciated even for smaller projects. This motivates them to complete future tasks efficiently. For instance, one said;

“I feel proud when principal appreciates me for any project. This boosts up my morale and encourages me to improve myself.”

10.5% said that recognition in form of monetary rewards help teachers financially. All other reasons that teachers mentioned as to why recognition is important include, increase of morale and job satisfaction, enhance in self-confidence and raise spirit to complete tasks.

c) Job satisfaction

Questions related to job satisfaction were only targeted for participants of first phase who were serving in private schools at the time of data collection. 65% existing teachers are found to be somewhat satisfied to work in their respective schools whereas 16% are found to be

Figure 4.4: ETs' Level of Job Satisfaction

highly satisfied. Satisfied teachers mentioned many factors responsible in their level of satisfaction. 30% existing teachers showed job satisfaction due cooperative staff of the school. Staff includes the colleagues, management, administration and leadership of the school. 21% believe that good environment is the reason of their satisfaction for working in their

respective schools. Other factors that are mentioned by existing teachers to be important in their job satisfaction are love for teaching, less workload, good students and progression opportunities.

Although, there is less percentage of existing teachers who showed dissatisfaction however the reasons they mentioned to be dissatisfied are important to discuss. Tough schedule and heavy workload found to be the top reason behind existing teachers' dissatisfaction followed by low salary. One teacher mentioned that her satisfaction level can be increased by increasing her salary.

"...I feel my salary should be increased as my fellows are earning more than me...this will improve my satisfaction with the current school."

Other factors that are found to be contributing in ET' s dissatisfaction is lack of incentives, lack of learning material, lack of facilities, lack of enough support and lack of progression etc.

4.4.2.2 Phase 2 Findings

Former teachers were asked to express about the importance of workplace components such as salary and recognition in form of incentives, rewards or verbal appreciation in their career decisions. Their responses are as follows:

a) Recognition

All 8 former teachers, interviewed for the research, agreed that recognition is important to them. They believe that work recognition increases productivity by making teachers feel proud and happy of their work. Another reasoning teacher gave as to why they think recognition of work is important is that it enhances their morale and satisfaction resulting in completion of tasks more efficiently. 2 former teachers mentioned that it is the right of every employee because teachers like other employees deserve to be recognised for their hard work.

b) Salary

As far as salary is concerned, 5 former teachers said that salary is important for them to stay or leave a particular school or profession. They said that everyone works to earn and support themselves financially so when an employee is paid right salary according to his qualification and class grades, they feel motivated to work better.

“Yes, salary is very important. If the salary is not matching the cost of living and at the same time there is no career progression path, then it is difficult to stay in the school”.

3 former teachers said that salary is not much important for them to stay or leave. To these teachers, other factors are more important such as dignity and respect, recognition of work, devotion and passion for teaching.

However, such response is revealed under the specific question related to the importance of salary for former teacher. Whereas, in other open-ended question related to turnover factors,

none of the former teachers under study considered salary as important to contribute in their decisions to exit from the private schools.

4.4.2.3 Cumulative Impression of workplace Components

a) Salary

There are mixed results about impact of salary on teachers' career decisions. Specific questions targeted to extract teachers' perception about the impact of salary revealed that salary is important for some and other factors are more important for others to stay or leave the profession. There is high percentage of existing teachers (76%) who consider salary as important factor whereas former teachers are mostly concerned about other factors such as support, dignity, respect, and recognition of work affect their decisions to stay in the profession.

b) Recognition

97% teachers in the first phase and 100% in the second phase has agreed to the importance of work recognition in their career decision. Teachers expressed their feeling as good, proud, satisfied and motivated upon receiving recognition of their work. Teachers who did not receive any recognition of their good work expressed themselves as to be disappointed and dissatisfied. More than half of the teachers believe that recognition in any form (either monetary or non-financial) increase the productivity of teachers by increasing their morale. Few said that it is human nature to be recognised. Everyone like to be praised and appreciated even for smaller projects. This motives them to complete future tasks efficiently. Similarly, recognition enhance teachers' morale and self-confidence.

c) Job satisfaction

This variable was tested only in the first phase of the research that involves exiting teachers. This was surprising to find that 81% of these teachers were satisfied (16% were highly satisfied, whereas 65% were somewhat satisfied), with their job in their current private schools at the time of data collection. Teachers mentioned many reasons to be satisfied

including co-operative staff of the school. Staff include all the colleagues, management, administration and leadership of the school. 21% teachers believed that good environment was the reason of their satisfaction for working in their respective schools. Other factors that were mentioned by existing teachers to be important in their job satisfaction were love for teaching, less workload, good students and progression opportunities. These reasons are discussed further in a separate section of teachers' stay decisions.

Although, there is less percentage of existing teachers (13%) who showed dissatisfaction however the reasons they mentioned to be dissatisfied are important to discuss. Tough schedule and heavy workload found to be the top reasons behind teachers' dissatisfaction followed by low salary. Other factors contribute in ET' s dissatisfaction is lack of incentives, lack of learning material, lack of facilities, lack of enough support, lack of progression etc. Moreover, only 6% teachers are found neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their job in the respective schools.

4.4.3 Early Career Teachers & Leave Intentions

The analysis of the in-hand research data collected in the first phase from the existing teachers of private schools, who have observed turnover in their particular schools, show that there are only 11% teachers who are working for more than 5 years whereas, 65% teachers have an experience of teaching under 5 years uncovering the fact that these teachers leave early in their career. This shows that the current turnover situation in private schools of district Gujrat is very high. There are a high percentage of existing teachers (64%) who said to continue with their respective schools or profession for 1 to 4 years, thus, intend to leave early. Moreover, existing teachers' intentions to leave early are more skewed towards young female teachers (between ages 20-29) perhaps due to the fact that they mostly leave a profession to get married or start a family.

Likewise, only 2 former teachers out of 8, who were interviewed in the second phase, worked more than 5 years whereas 6 of them were early teachers who worked less than 5 years. This also reinstates the high turnover situation in district Gujrat private school.

4.5 FACTORS OF TEACHERS' TURNOVER IN GUJRAT

4.5.1 Phase 1 Findings

Questions related to existing teachers' main difficulties they face in their relevant schools, reason of their job dissatisfaction and why would they quit if they decide to quit in future targeted the factors behind their decisions to leave teaching altogether or move from a particular school. *Figure 16* shows the cumulative reasons influencing existing teachers' leave decisions as follows:

Figure 4.5: Factors Behind ET's Leave Decisions

4.5.1.1 Heavy workload/Tough schedule

The primary reason found behind teachers' main difficulties in teaching in their particular schools, job dissatisfaction and intentions to leave in future, is the heavy workload and tough schedule making workload unmanageable. 25% of existing teachers expressed that stress of meeting deadlines, lesson planning, copy checking all contribute in workload that becomes unmanageable along with day to day teaching lessons with minimum rest periods. While responding to an open-ended question as to what makes their current job difficult, one teacher stated that;

“The only difficulty I face is planning the lesson according to school’s scheme of study... this increase the burden of work and decrease the freedom of teacher in a classroom. If we miss the part of plan due to some reason, this means more paperwork next day.... This becomes unmanageable...”

Hence, the analysis of the data revealed paperwork adding in the workload of teachers consequently leading to their leave decisions.

4.5.1.2 Personal Issues

99 (21%) existing teachers mentioned that there are some personal issues that might contribute in their leave decisions in future. These personal factors include, family related domestic issues (48%), marriage or relocation with partner (27%), health issues (15%) and intentions for further studies (9%).

Family related issues emerged as leading personal factor influencing teachers’ leave intentions. Such issues include, a change in family circumstances, relocation of family, lack of support from family to continue with teaching and ill health of a family member etc.

In addition, the under studied teachers were mostly female, and it has been observed during the analysis that most of them were unmarried at the time of data collection. Hence, there is a cultural aspect that involves the perception that women would have to leave the profession after marriage to start a family. Consequently 27% teachers mentioned that they may depart from the profession due to marriage or may move to another school due to relocation with partners.

Moreover, health issues may influence some serving teachers’ intentions to leave. Whereas, other may leave because they want to study themselves to earn a higher degree for better job prospects.

4.5.1.3 Lack of support

16% existing teachers consider lack of enough support from management, senior leadership, administration and colleagues as a reason behind their leave intentions. The supportive environment of any school, thus, play an important part to help retain teachers in private schools. Few teachers complained of unnecessary workshops requiring them to spend extra hours in the schools. While citing about lack of management support one working teacher in a private school of tehsil Kharian stated;

“Management makes issues when you need a leave slip to go home... you cannot go home until finish all paperwork and get your leave slip.”

Similarly, lack of support and cooperation from colleagues has been discovered as prominently influencing teachers’ leave decisions and vice versa. In addition, principal support in form of appreciation, work recognition and mutual cooperation leads to increased satisfaction level of existing teachers thus making them stay longer whereas lack of such support results in high teacher turnover.

4.5.1.4 Low Salary and lack of monetary rewards

Many existing teachers believe that the salaries paid to teachers in the private schools are much lower than that paid to teachers in public schools. 11% of these teachers said that low salary can be the reason behind their departure from the current school in future whereas 4% claim that lack of other monetary rewards such as bonuses, incentives and rewards could lead to their departure from private school education system.

Moreover, teachers found high salary differences between public and private schools. Some teachers mentioned that they intend to join public school sector if they get an opportunity due to better salary packages and job security. One sated that;

“I plan to apply for a teaching position in a government school whenever they open recruitments.... because they offer very good pay package and the job is permanent.”

Another revealed that;

“My reason to exit form this school in future would be salary as I do not get enough money in this job and I have financial problems.”

Tough there is a less percentage of teachers who are concerned with low salaries of private schools however this could be due to the fact they are more concerned with other factors and therefore did not mention about salary as most important factor.

4.5.1.5 Better opportunity

Furthermore, 10% existing teachers see themselves leaving their particular school if they find a better opportunity such as permanent teaching job in government education sector, promotion to head or principal, and better opportunity in professions other than teaching. Alternative job advertisements also attracted a small number of teachers as better opportunity for them. For example, a female teacher revealed that she had been thinking for long time to leave teaching and join another profession and she plans to do that as soon as she finds an opportunity.

“to be honest I plan to leave this school for a long time and move to another school or may be another job, but I have not found any better opportunity yet...”

Though not too many, yet there are few exiting teachers of private schools, who at the time of data collection were looking for another better opportunity and leave particular private school.

4.5.1.6 Working conditions

Existing teachers referred to many other factors contributing in their intentions to leave teaching in future such as negative school climate, substandard building, lack of facilities, lack of progression, and lack of learning aids and materials. Such factors are categorised as working conditions of the schools under study. To the researcher’s surprise, there is not a

very high percentage of existing teachers (only 7%) who consider poor working conditions being a factor behind their career decisions.

4.5.1.7 Students issues

Quite a few numbers of existing teachers (5%) mentioned disadvantaged students with learning issues, discipline issues and behavioural issues are the factors that contribute in their dissatisfaction and difficulties in carrying their job in particular schools thus intend to leave in future. While citing about students' attitude, one teacher stated that;

"... the students in my class have some serious issues with their behaviours... neither do principals nor the parents do anything about this... In fact, all blame goes on teacher... this makes me very frustrated..."

Similarly, she mentioned about low performance of students increasing her disappointment as she continued on stating that;

"... they also have poor performances in the tests making the situation worse for me."

Thus, student related issues are causing teachers' dissatisfaction with the schools as well as lack of trust on principals and parents resulting in their leave intentions.

4.5.1.8 Others

There are many other factors revealed by existing teachers that are responsible for their dissatisfaction with current schools and contribute in their leave intentions such as travelling issues due to school location, lack of respect from school leaders, lack of job security, and either too much or too little of parents' involvement.

4.5.2 Phase 2 Findings

Q 12-17 of the interview guide were targeted to extract the information related to former teachers' decisions to depart from the previous private schools. Majority of former teachers

gave multiple reasons contributing in their leave decisions though for few, one reason was more prominent than the other.

Table 4.8: Former teachers' responses to interview questions

Questions	Example codes x number of comments	Themes x number of comments
Q 12. Negative characteristics of school that contributed in leave decision?	<p>Workload is very high (x3) Non-cooperative Colleagues (x3) Misbehaving Students (x2) Negative/unsupportive climate (x2) Lack of progression Lack of freedom Lack of facilities (job security) Low salary</p>	<p>1. Lack of Support x15 ↓ Colleague issues x7 Management and administration issues x4 Principal and section head issues x4 2. Poor Working conditions x11 ↓ Negative school climate x4 Lack of facilities x4 Lack of progression x3 3. Heavy Workload x9 4. Student issues x9 5. Low salary x3 6. Others x6</p>
Q 13. Main difficulties faced in previous school?	<p>Poor timings Autocratic management and administration Disadvantaged students Jealousy/staff clashes among staff (x3) Low salary Lack of progression Favouritism/biased principal/section head A lot of paperwork</p>	
Q 14. What new job/school offer but previous school lacked?	<p>Supportive administration and management (lack of management/admin support) x2 Less workload (heavy workload) x3 Facilities (lack of facilities) x2 Progression (lack of progression) Good environment (negative environment) Good students (disadvantaged students) Good timings (bad timings) School is nearby (distance to school)</p>	
Q 15. Reason to seek alternative job. (e.g. retail, public school job)	<p>Poor standard of education Lack of respect from students (x2)</p>	
Q 16. Reasons of dissatisfaction with previous school?	<p>Disadvantage students (x2) Low pay (x2) Lack of support from section head/principal (x2) Colleague issues Heavy workload</p>	
Q 17. If need to change one thing in previous school what it would be?	<p>Standard of education Misbehaving students Facilities such as provide job security Negative school climate Management/administration School principal Workload</p>	

Table 9 shows the codes and themes found under former teachers' reasons behind their turnover decisions from private schools as follows:

4.5.2.1 Lack of support

Overall 28% former teachers are found to talk most about the lack of support behind their decisions to leave a particular private school. This includes support from colleagues, section heads, principal, management and administration.

Figure 4.6: Lack of support as FTs' reason to quit

Most of the former teachers interviewed mentioned about the issues with colleagues. This was very surprising to find that 85.5% former teachers think that due to colleagues' jealousy at workplace, staff clashes, and non-cooperative attitude of colleagues became reason for them to leave a particular school. while talking about lack of colleagues' support, a former teacher said;

“The most difficult part to carry on with the ‘A’ school was the school culture.... where fellow teachers have grudges against one another.... there was so much jealousy and envy that I had to leave the school ultimately.”

Moreover, issues with management and principal of the school are also found as prominent reasons as they both are mentioned by 50% of former teachers (4/8). These teachers revealed that principals and section head of the schools are biased. They said that leadership of the school should not have favourites instead they should treat every teacher equally. According to a former teacher, one cannot work in such an environment where teachers do not receive equal treatment by the leadership of the school.

***“... how can someone work in a school where you are not their favourite....
This is the responsibility of the school’s head to create an environment where
everyone is treated equally.”***

Same is revealed about school management and administration who are mentioned to be biased by 4 out of 8 former teachers thus affected these teachers career decisions who left the schools ultimately. Unnecessary staff meetings and timetable issues are also mentioned by former teachers as lack of support from management side.

4.5.2.2 Poor work conditions

Unlike existing teachers, poor working conditions are mentioned by quite a few numbers of former teachers (21%) as their departure reasons. *Figure 18* below shows the breakdown of main factors included as subcategories under the category of working conditions. These include the following:

Figure 4.7: Work conditions as reason of turnover

Overall, 50% former teachers mentioned school’s negative climate as reasons of their leave decisions. By negative environment, they meant biased and non-supportive climate in general, however, they did not particularly mention about colleagues or other staff.

Additionally, Facilities such as medical insurance, pension, job security are what is offered in their current job/school, which is different from previous school, therefore, important factors to consider staying in a school. similarly, lack of progression is being mentioned as negative characteristic of private schools and main difficulty in carrying on teaching in the private

school by former teachers. In contrast, public schools offer progression opportunities which is why two teachers left private schools to join public school. talking about job insecurity at private schools Faisal stated that;

“if the students fail, this means teacher fails... and then he is asked to leave without even a notice.”

He continued to say,

“... in public school, my job is permanent, and I have no fear of losing my job only because my students are less advantageous.”

4.5.2.3 Workload

Different questions were targeted to find out former teachers’ perception about the main difficulties they face in teaching in particular schools and reasons behind their dissatisfaction. Heavy workload is found to be the third most important reason found to be a contributor in 17% former teachers’ leave decisions. In the second phase of data collection, excessive paperwork is again appeared as contributing in teachers’ workload. As pointed out by Esha who moved to a private college and left teaching on school level;

“It was highly difficult to teach in the school because of all the copy checking and test marking. Of course, I do the same in college, but it is much less paperwork at college level and there is no lesson planning I have to do...”

Moreover, former teachers mentioned about meeting the deadlines in school, lesson planning according to school’s structure of lessons and tough schedule with minimum rest periods. All these factors are responsible for increasing former teachers’ workload, resulting in their departure.

4.5.2.4 Student issues

Similarly, issues with students such as misbehaviour of students, poor performances and disciplinary issues found to be as big factor behind former teachers leave decision. 17%

former teachers suggest that students of a school are important because a teacher wants to make difference in students' lives. As pointed out by Nimra while talking about what made her disappointed with the previous school;

“I worked so hard to deliver my best because I know it is the teacher who makes the students a doctor, an engineer etc... I joined the profession to make such contribution but when students did not deliver what was expected, I felt very disappointed and I left the school (A) and moved to ‘B’ (another school).”

Thus, if students do not perform as expected after teachers' hard work and effort then a teacher feels demotivated and gets less interested in teaching and tends to leave the particular school or profession ultimately.

4.5.2.5 Low salary

While salary is one of the multiple factors influencing the propensity of teachers to leave, surprisingly, low salary is not indicated as a main factor behind former teachers' quit decisions from their previous private schools. However, when former teachers were directly asked about salaries, only 6% former teachers were interestingly discovered to mention this in their decisions to leave.

They consider salary less important compared to the other factors and therefore they said that they could not have left only if the salary was low. Thus, salary was found to be the least important factor behind former teachers' turnover in private education sector in Pakistan. Hence, a combination of more than one factors were responsible to contribute in their decisions to depart.

4.5.2.6 Other

Few other reasons mentioned by former teachers that had negative impact on them and contributed in their decision to leave the particular school include lack of freedom and flexibility to teach independently, travelling issues and low standard of education in particular school etc.

4.5.3 Cumulative Factors of Teacher Turnover

Figure 4.8: Cumulative factors behind turnover

- a) Lack of support in general such as principal issues and management issues; and lack of administrative and collegial support in particular is the most leading factor influencing teachers' turnover.
- b) Heavy workload is appeared to be the second most prominent factor behind turnover. The workload includes excessive paperwork, minimum rest period, tough schedule, after school meetings, lesson planning, high pupil-teacher ratio.
- c) Dissatisfaction with working conditions is also a significant factor behind turnover such as negative school climate and biased environment, lack of facilities, resources and progression opportunities.
- d) Student related issues such as misbehaviour, lack of respect and poor performance also appeared as major factors.
- e) Low salary, lack of monetary incentives and rewards are among noticeable factors.
- f) Personal reasons (e.g., health issues, marriage and relocation, pregnancy and child rearing, etc.
- g) Other factors such as lack of flexibility and freedom to teach independently, lack of respect, travelling issues, lack of work recognition, low standard of education are also noticeable factors behind teachers' turnover from private schools in district Gujrat.

4.5.4 Relevance of Present Study Factors of Turnover with Existing Theories

Table 4.9: Relevance of Turnover Factors with Existing Theories

Present Study Factors of Turnover	Billingsley et al (1993)	Brownell & Smith (1993)	Karsenti & Collin (2013)
Lack of support	Employment factors	Mesosystem	Task related/social factors
Heavy workload	Employment factors		Task related factors
Poor work conditions	Employment factors		Task related factors
Student issues		Microsystem	Task related/social factors
Low salary	Employment factors	Macrosystem	Socio-economic factors
Personal issues	Personal factors		Individual factors

Table 10 shows the relevance of the present study findings of teacher turnover factors with the existing theories. However, the categories presented by Billingsley et al. do not include teachers' relationships with staff (mesosystem/social factors), and teachers' relationships with students (microsystem/social factors) as factors contributing to teachers' turnover. Similarly, the theoretical framework of Brownell et al. lacks a heavy workload and poor work conditions (task-related/employment factors) as important factors of teacher turnover. However, the present study has found these factors to be highly important in teachers' career decisions in the context of district Gujrat, Pakistan.

Thus, the current study findings on factors of teacher turnover in Gujrat is highly relevant with the turnover categories proposed by Karsenti & Collin as both did not find any external factors (Exosystem/external factors) to be indirectly affecting teachers' leave decisions such as country's economic condition, instability, and political situation.

4.6 STAFF RETENTION STRATEGIES BASED ON RESPONSES

4.6.1 Phase 1 Findings

Although existing teachers were not specifically asked about recommendations to improve teachers' retention, however, they were asked to express their opinions as to what their current schools need to improve and how their job satisfaction level can be increased to continue working in their respective schools. The responses collected from such questions are treated as suggestions by existing teachers to improve retentions. The following graph gives a clear picture of these suggestions.

Figure 4.9: ETs' recommendations to improve retentions

4.6.1.1 Increments in Salary

Surprisingly, while salary was fourth in the list of factors influencing existing teachers' career decisions, it appeared as the most important factor to retain them in teaching profession. Thus, 21% existing teachers expressed that their level of job satisfaction can be improved by schools by giving salary increments annually. They believe that salary play a big role in career decisions and as the inflation is rising fast so should the salaries to help teachers financially in order to retain them in the profession. As pointed out by one teacher;

“My satisfaction with the school can be increased if school offers me a better salary package.”

4.6.1.2 Facilities

While responding to an open-ended question related to job satisfaction levels, 14% existing teachers uncovered that very basic facilities such as availability of staffroom, cafeteria, better lunch menu, pick and drop facility and medical insurance, can improve their job satisfaction with the current schools. Teachers believe that their respective schools need to improve these facilities to improve teachers' level of satisfaction resulting in better retention of teachers in future. One teacher mentioned that;

“I like my school and if the school provide me with the pick and drop facility, this will take my satisfaction level to the highest.”

Hence, to the researcher's surprise, existing teachers identified such basic facilities that can increase their job satisfaction and improve teacher retention.

4.6.1.3 Availability of support

Moreover, existing teachers are found claiming that availability of enough support at schools can contribute in their job satisfaction levels. 14% of these teachers believed that support from senior leadership such as principal or head of the school, administration, management and colleagues support can be improved making teachers feel satisfied and stay in a particular school. For instance, one teacher said that,

“I think principal's attitude needs improvement in this school... if principal becomes more friendly and understand teachers' problems, teachers will feel more supported and satisfied...”

Therefore, providing enough support is crucial in improved satisfaction levels, consequently, retaining teachers for longer time period.

4.6.1.4 Appreciation/cash rewards

Both monetary and non-monetary rewards are important in teacher retention. Verbal appreciation and cash rewards are found to be mentioned by existing teachers as adding in

their level of job satisfaction. 12% teachers said that they want appreciation of their work in schools. As stated by one teacher;

“I am quite satisfied with school’s environment but the only thing I want is the appreciation of my efforts. I know that this is my job to teach, but sometimes I put extra effort to complete a project. And if I get some extra cash on such projects this will also help me financially...”

They are found to mention that teachers work hard, and their efforts must be appreciated by senior leadership to increase their morale and satisfaction. They mentioned about appreciation of work both verbally as well as in form of cash because they claim that cash rewards help them financially as well.

4.6.1.5 Improved Students

Surprising facts are found in survey questionnaire where teachers complained about misbehaving students as frustrating and disturbing. 12% teachers said that their satisfaction in particular school can be increased if the schools develop and implement policies against misbehaving students. As mentioned by one teacher,

“Students need improvements in this school because the students are very disrespectful towards teachers. Management must do something to resolve this issue.”

They said that there should be a system of reward and punishment for good and bad students respectively. These teachers think that students bring high fees to these private schools and therefore they are not punished or expelled if they misbehave with teachers resulting in teachers being less respectful and dissatisfied and therefore leave the school or profession.

4.6.1.6 Other

Other factors identified in phase one that can contribute in teachers job satisfaction and improve retentions are availability of resources (8%) and decrease in workload (7%). The

resources include class learning aids such as duster, chalks, markers, etc as well as IT material such as computers and projectors.

Other particular (13%) suggestions made by existing teachers to improve their levels of satisfaction include progression opportunities, teachers' training programs, teachers' inclusions in decision making, reduction in teacher student ratio in a class, freedom and flexibility to teach and positive school environment.

4.6.2 Phase 2 Findings

At the end of interview in second phase of data collection, the former teachers were asked to provide their suggestions on how teacher turnover can be reduced. Following were the recommendations made by them.

Figure 4.10: FTs' recommendations to improve retention

The most prominent recommendation received by the former teachers was surprisingly different from their reasons to depart from the schools. Though former teachers did mention about lack of facilities as their reason to quit however it did not appear to be the leading factor behind their leave decisions as appeared in the recommendation chart.

4.6.2.1 Facilities

While second in the list of suggestions by the existing teachers, former teachers predominantly mentioned about providing facilities to the teachers to retain them longer in the private schools. While talking about such facilities, Faisal said;

“I did not have any issue with “A” school because I had good salary there and all the staff, including principal and management, was very co-operative. I just left because I found better facilities in government school....”

While explaining about these facilities, he continued stating that;

“...better facilities... I mean I have a medical card and I get free medical check-up in army hospital, and I also get travel allowance...”

Hence, 35% former teachers believe that private schools should facilitate teachers the way government schools do, which can be highly useful in retaining them for longer period of time. These facilities include medical insurance, job security, paid annual leave, travelling allowance and/or pick and drop facility.

4.6.2.2 Availability of support

Availability of support is another factor claimed to be important in retaining teachers as this could have changed 19% of former teachers' decision to leave. The support from administrators, management and head of school is particular in this respect. It is also observed that new teachers need more support as they tend to leave early if they are not supported by their seniors in the start of their career. For instance, one former teacher who left very early in her career mentioned that,

“I would suggest that there should be more positive environment in private schools, especially the school-head and the section-head should encourage new teachers like me instead of just picking mistakes because in the start of

teaching I did not know much about school's system and policies... I might not have left if I had support of my seniors and school-head."

Therefore, a supportive environment is very crucial in retaining teachers. This includes understanding of the problems; teachers face during the early years of teaching. Former teachers also spoke high for the respect they should receive from senior leadership. They mentioned that when teachers get respect from school authorities, they get respect from students also and this is important for a teacher's inner satisfaction. The more a teacher is satisfied, the longer he will stay.

4.6.2.3 Decrease in workload

Another factor important for policy makers to consider is the amount of workload on teachers. This was one of the dominant factors found behind teachers leave decisions. Therefore, reducing workload on teachers can make them stay longer. 10% former teachers pointed towards the reduction of workload for teachers as recommendation for teacher retention. This means much more manageable caseloads, less paperwork, flexible work schedule with sufficient rest period, and flexibility to work independently.

There had been many suggestions made by the participant teachers in second phase to address the issue of overwork. Some suggested that there was no need of re-writing the lesson plan. The other mentioned to have freedom to adapt and annotate the plans instead. Some considered it to be undue pressure on teachers by the schools for accountability purposes and believe that the details the schools require to include in lesson plans are unnecessary. Therefore, it is recommended that the extra workload in form of lesson planning can be minimized with the development of a central scheme of study.

For instance, one teacher said,

"My suggestion is to reduce workload. This is so ridiculous to write down the lesson plan when it is already planned. If this is done to adapt, then I must say that teacher knows better how to adapt in a classroom environment. But making plan not only eliminate freedom to teach but also increase workload."

Another suggestion to decrease the workload was to reduce the larger class sizes. Teachers claimed that larger classes are challenging to manage, and it is hard to develop individual connections with students in larger classes. Marking and providing individual feedback to students becomes highly difficult for teachers. The students also get less individual attention and thus produce less quality work. Teachers also complain of misbehaving students and believe that this is mostly due to larger class sizes. Therefore, in order to decrease workload and to have better teacher retention, class sizes need to be reduced as suggested by the participants of the second phase.

4.6.2.4 Increase in salaries

Unlike existing teachers who consider salary being the first factor that contribute in teachers' stay decision, only 10% former teachers believe that increment in salary could have changed their decision to leave. Former teachers mentioned that other factors are more important than salary. For these teachers a school's positive environment, dignity of teachers, supportive administration, recognition of work and inclusion is what could have made them stay longer in particular schools. However, those who consider that salary should be increased to improve teacher retention believe that rising inflation in the country is affecting career decisions and teachers tend to move to other professions due to such reasons. For instance, one mentioned that;

“My other friends are earning more in other professions, you know, it is so much inflation now a days that with current salary I cannot meet my needs.”

4.6.2.5 Recognition of work

Although this factor is also a part of support from school authorities; however, the researcher deems to consider it important to discuss separately because the researcher found former teachers mentioning it separately from a general support. These teachers (7%) reckon that work recognition is very important to motivate teachers and make them work even better.

This is especially important to increase teachers' morale and satisfaction resulting in better teacher retention. Talking about work recognition one teacher said,

“I think if the school authorities only learn to appreciate teachers for their work, this will resolve the issue to some extent...teachers deserve to be recognised.”

Former teachers reported that in teaching profession recognition of work is a way of increasing respect of teachers which improve retention as a result. Teachers felt that lack of understanding and expertise need to be fixed before implementing other strategies to retain teachers. Although, the suggestions teachers made did not explain the way of achieving the required results, however, it was clear that respect and recognition in form of support would influence them to stay in the sector for long.

4.6.2.6 Other

Other factors that are important in retaining teachers mentioned by former teachers as part of their suggestions are staff cooperation, positive and unbiased school environment, better behaving students, freedom and flexibility to work independently and inclusion of teachers in policy and decision making.

4.6.3 Staff Retention Strategies based on Cumulative Responses

- a) Provide facilities such as medical insurance, job security, travelling allowance, paid annual leave, paid sick leave, availability of café and staffroom for teachers etc.
- b) Support from senior staff, administration, principal/head, management.
- c) Salary increments and monetary rewards.
- d) Appreciation and recognition of work.
- e) Decrease in workload such as manageable caseloads, less paperwork, flexible work schedule with sufficient rest period, and flexibility to work independently.

- f) Improved students such as better learning skills, better conduct and behaviour, good performances.
- g) Respect for teachers as they are the builders of society.
- h) Availability of resources such as learning material and aids.
- i) Other factors mentioned by teachers of both phases to be held important in teachers' stay decisions.

Figure 4.11: Retention strategies based on responses

4.6.4 Relevance of Present Study Factors of Retention with Conceptual Frameworks

Table 4.10: Relevance of retention factors with conceptual frameworks

Present Study Retention Factors	Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs	Herzberg Two Factor Theory
Facilities	Basic needs	Hygiene factors
Support	Psychological needs	Motivational factor
Salary	Basic needs	Hygiene factors
Appreciation/recognition	Psychological needs	Motivational factor
Decrease in workload	Basic needs	Hygiene factors
Better students	Psychological needs	Hygiene factors
Respect	Psychological needs	Motivational factor
Resources	Basic needs	Hygiene factors

Relevance with Maslow's framework

Better facilities, adequate salary, reduced workload and better working conditions of the private schools with enough resources are among those factors which influence a teacher's basic need level in district Gujrat. The teachers will seek alternative opportunities if their basic needs are not fulfilled. However, upon having basic needs fulfilled they get concerned about other factors such as a supportive unbiased school environment, respect, appreciation and recognition of work. The current research confirms the importance for fulfilment of teachers' basic needs as well as psychological needs in district Gujrat private schools. None is found to be at the self-actualization level. This shows that teachers in district Gujrat are yet to fulfil their basic and psychological needs. Once these needs are fulfilled, they might persuade the esteem needs where they will become self-aware of their strengths and weaknesses.

Relevance with Herzberg's framework

Five retention factors found in the present study are relevant to the Hygiene factors of Herzberg two factor theory. Improving these factors can reduce teachers' job dissatisfaction in district Gujrat private schools. These factors include inadequate salaries, lack of facilities, heavy workload, misbehaving students, lack of resources.

Whereas, three retention factors of the present study are motivational factors and improving these factors can improve teachers' job satisfaction. These factors include supportive environment, respect and recognition of work in the form of awards and bonuses. Teachers in district Gujrat are more likely to stay in the profession if the work environment is a supportive. Similarly, if the community and students give them the respect and gratitude they deserve, and if they are appreciated and praised for their hard work, they will choose to stay longer in the teaching profession.

4.7 SUMMARY OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

This research has found underlying factors behind teachers' turnover in private schools of district Gujrat Pakistan. As the research is done in two phases, therefore the findings are also

presented in two phases and then the cumulative findings of both phases are highlighted in order to discuss their relevance with the previous literature in the next chapter. There are four main findings/themes revealed after the data analysis; the drivers of becoming teachers; the impressions of teaching career in particular schools; the factors of leaving teaching career, and factors of teacher retention.

Nobility of teaching profession, love and passion for teaching, and contribution in students' lives are found to be the prominent drivers of becoming teachers. Majority of the current teachers articulated of having enough support available in their respective schools in terms of colleagues, principals and administrations' cooperation. Therefore, they are found to be quite satisfied with their job in the respective schools. Similarly, these teachers expressed about good students and schools' encouraging environment as having positive impression on them ultimately contributing in their level of job satisfaction.

The analysis of personal data such teaching experience of both existing and former teachers as well as intentions of existing teachers to continue with the profession show the current turnover situation of the private schools. Existing teachers who have observed turnover in their particular schools, show that there are only 11% teachers who are working for more than 5 years, whereas, 65% teachers have an experience of teaching under 5 years uncovering the fact that these teachers leave early in their career. This shows that the current turnover situation in private schools of district Gujrat is very high. There are a high percentage of teachers who said to continue with their respective schools or profession for less than 5 years. Moreover, 75% former teachers departed from the profession in less than 5 years. This also reinstates the high turnover situation in district Gujrat private school.

As long as reasons of turnover are concerned, lack of support and heavy workload has appeared as prominent factors followed by tough working conditions, issues with students and low salary. Personal reasons are also found to contribute in teachers leave decisions. In addition, teachers provided many recommendations to avoid this problem of high turnover. These are studied as retention strategies based on teachers' responses such as availability of

facilities, support and learning material along with decreased workload, improved salaries and recognition of work.

5 CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This study has identified and explored several factors influencing teacher turnover in selected private schools in district Gujrat, Pakistan using qualitative research design. The factors affecting teachers' turnover were studied in order to devise a teacher retention framework for policy makers. The results presented many suggestions based on teachers' responses to retain them in the private schools. The study was conducted using an open-ended questionnaire survey from serving/existing teachers of randomly selected 9 private schools in three tehsils of district Gujrat as well as using a semi structured interview from 8 departed/former teachers in the district. Data was collected in October and November 2017 and analysed using thematic analysis technique. The chapter critically discusses the findings of this research against existing literature, draws conclusions and makes necessary recommendations for teacher retention based on the responses and findings.

5.2 KEY THEMES

Key themes found in the research are as follows:

Drivers of teaching career

Impressions of teaching career

Factors of teacher turnover

Retention strategies based on responses

5.3 DISCUSSION

5.3.1 Drivers and Impressions of Teaching Career

There are different drivers that attract the graduates to join teaching as profession, and the impression of the respective schools and its component play critical roles for teachers to stay in the profession or leave. The current study has investigated and found the following key drivers of joining teaching profession as a career as well as impressions of work components on teachers' career decisions.

5.3.1.1 Reasons of becoming teachers

There are two types of teachers, first who enter the profession taking it as a career choice whereas other type only enters temporarily however the schools' environment and work component such as salary, support, work recognition and job satisfaction influence them to make teaching their permanent career. Teachers' reasons to enter the profession show their initial interest and passion however, their dissatisfaction with either schools in particular or with teaching job itself led to their departure. The current research has identified many reasons as to why teachers in Pakistan join teaching profession in the first place. Following is a brief discussion.

a) Communal reasons

Teachers of private schools in district Gujrat has predominantly stated nobility and respect attached with teaching profession as their main reason to enter this profession. Teachers mentioned that teaching is a profession of prophets therefore they consider it the noblest of all profession. Many said that teachers are mostly respected in society especially women. As there were more female participants, thus the gender differences could not be identified in this context. On the other hand, more female teachers in teaching profession, especially in private schools, show that the nobility and respect attached with the profession is primary reason for female teachers to join teaching profession.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

The current study has found nobility of the teaching profession as a primary reason given by the teachers to join teaching in district Gujrat. Mostly appeared to mention teaching as a prophetic profession and therefore consider it the noblest of all other professions. Thus, the finding suggests that Islamic culture in Pakistan has significant implications on career aspirations. The teachers in private schools in Gujrat were found to be highly influenced by Islam when they entered the teaching profession.

These findings confirm the exiting literature on influences of religion on career choices in the context of Islamic countries such as Saudi Arabia, where religion was found to be predominantly influencing MBA students' career choices (Albugamy, 2014). Similarly, the findings are consistent with the study conducted in Pakistan to investigate teachers' motivation to join teaching profession. This study also found cultural and religious aspect to be prominently influencing teachers; career choices (Kamran & Shahbaz, 2018).

In addition, a recent cross-cultural, qualitative research was done on student teachers to compare the career motivations of final-year Canadian and Omani pre-service teachers. The study highlights that Omani teachers are highly influenced by the socio-cultural impacts when they choose teaching as their career. The participating student teachers from Oman highly rated the culturally specific religious and gender roles in their qualitative survey responses such as, "teaching is the profession of the prophets", "teaching is the best job for women". (Klassen et al., 2011). Thus, the culture and religion have a strong influence on choices of career and because teaching is considered to be noblest in the Pakistani community therefore it has appeared as the primary reason in the current research findings.

b) Emotional reasons

Many teachers said to enter teaching profession due to some kind of emotional attachments. These include attachments with their own primary or high schools, with their own schoolteacher(s) and with their favourite subject(s) at the time of studying. Some of these teachers mentioned that they have an emotional affiliation with their own primary schools

and therefore they love to teach in the same school. Others are inspired from their own teachers who became their motivation to enter the profession and therefore they feel pleasure and satisfaction in teaching. Moreover, teaching is a family profession for some teachers, and they claimed that they have passion for teaching due to the fact that their parent(s) profession was also teaching.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

Thus, these emotional attachments found are correlated consistently with the intrinsic rewards mentioned in the Self-Determination Theory (Deci, & Ryan, 1985). According to this theory, intrinsic rewards are more basics and fundamental influencing teachers' sense of pleasure. Being with their children, enjoying teaching their favourite subject, contributing in students' achievements, developing new skills and exercising influence in their role all are included in intrinsic rewards.

Similarly, staying in touch with one's favourite subject is also a frequent motivation found to influence some teachers as an intrinsic reward. Similarly, according to Tomšik (2016) enjoyment of the subject was given to be the most powerful motivation to choose teaching as a career by Slovenian English teachers. Moreover, Clarke, (2009) discovered that in a recent study in Ireland investigating the second-level student teachers' career inspirations, "love of subject" was one of the intrinsic factors that achieved the third highest mean value.

c) Social reasons

Social contribution such as increase the knowledge of others, spread wisdom, make difference and contribute in the lives of young students are also found to be prominent reasons to join the teaching profession. These socially worthwhile motivations are known as altruistic motivations in the previous studies. Teachers in district Gujrat private schools are mostly found to enter the teaching profession because they want to teach young children and make a positive contribution in their lives. However, upon finding poor working conditions in

a particular school e.g., lack of facilities and enough support, it became challenging for them to continue and therefore they quit or intend to quit.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

This finding is somewhat consistent with Lortie's study (2002) who has also reported that the major reason to enter teaching given by the practicing teachers in their study was the "desire to work with young people". Similarly, Lester (1986) also agreed that people are interested to join teaching due to personal satisfaction they feel upon seeing their students' accomplishments later in their lives.

Moreover, contributing in students' lives and making a difference in the society by imparting intellectual knowledge gives an inner sense of pleasure to the teachers (Reid & Thornton, 2000; Ornstein & Levine, 2006). Similarly, Richardson and Watt (2006) tested how various types of altruistic motivational factors influence the career choice, which they categorise as "social utility values." Accordingly, Australian teachers measured a strong desire to "shape the future of children/adolescents", to "enhance social equity", "to make a social contribution", and "to work with children and adolescents." Thus, a "love of and wanting to help children" is considered to be the most significant motive agreed by student teachers for joining teaching and is, therefore, consistent with the findings of the current study.

Additionally, Patton and Kristonis (2006) claim that altruistic rewards should be taken into account at time of recruitment of teachers who are passionate about teaching children in order to improve teacher retention. However, in context of the current study findings, the teachers who entered initially with intrinsic motivations, departed from the schools later due to dissatisfaction with other work-related factors.

d) Personal reasons

Unlike intrinsic motivations, the motivational preferences of some to join teaching as career are more personal and extrinsic. The current research has also found teachers' personal reasons to join teaching. Some teachers are found to state that they initially entered the

profession on temporary basis, however, they started liking the profession after a while. They stated that their job satisfaction increased upon finding positive school characteristics such as enough support, good working conditions and teaching material. Other personal reasons found incorporate teaching as hobby, professional support from family and friends. Few teachers also stated that they wanted to gain knowledge by teaching because teaching itself is a learning process for them whereas some other teachers were looking to some experience in the education field.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

Contrary to the current research findings, where extrinsic motivations of participants to become teachers are more personal, the evidence on extrinsic motivation suggests the monetary aspects of choosing teaching as a career. For instance, people join teaching profession because of the job security it provides (Webster et al. 2004; Kyriacou & Coulthard, 2000;). Similarly, according to Reid & Thornton, (2000), some people chose teaching career due to certain perceived benefits come along with the profession such as promotions, facilities, and length of holidays. On the other hand, the current study did not find such extrinsic motivation and perceived benefits of the profession as drivers of teaching career in private schools.

However, the findings are consistent with Hutchings (2002) and Lewis (2002) who pointed out that teachers' personal experiences with other teachers, their family background and support from family and friends are also important factors in attraction to teaching career.

The findings indicated that some teachers entered the profession temporarily and then derived satisfaction with schools' working condition and decided to stay in the profession. This is also consistent with previous studies showing job satisfaction as key driver of teaching career. The satisfaction one derives from the external work components are major extrinsic reason behind some people choosing teaching profession (Hunt, 2002). Similarly, Skilbeck & Connell, (2003) has identified that having teaching resources and material are one of the most common extrinsic components of job satisfaction among teachers identified. In the presence

of such components, people attract more to the teaching career and remain within the profession.

5.3.1.2 Impression of workplace components in career decision

Teachers also expressed their views about some workplace components that they consider important in their decisions to continue with or leave the teaching profession. The study has observed these important variables separately in relation with teachers' career decisions and established that job satisfaction, work recognition and salaries have a significant effect on teacher stay or leave decisions in the private schools in district Gujrat.

a) Salary

There are mixed results about impact of salary on teachers' career decisions. Specific questions targeted to extract teachers' perception about the impact of salary revealed that salary is important for some and other factors are more important for others to stay or leave the profession. There is high percentage of existing teachers (76%) who consider salary as important factor whereas former teachers are mostly concerned about other factors such as support, dignity, respect, and recognition of work to affect their decisions to stay in the profession.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

As far as impact of salary on teachers' career decisions is concerned, the findings of the participants in first phase (existing teachers), and participants of the second phase (former teachers) are highly different so does their relevance with the previous studies.

Previous research studies confirms the impact of salaries on teachers' decision to stay in or quit the profession are very high (Boe, et al., 2008; Feng, 2006; Hanushek, et al., 2004; Imazeki, 2002, 2005; Ladd, 2007; Podgursky et al., 2004; Scafidi et al., 2007; Stinebrickner, 2002). The evidence shows that salary plays a vital role in teachers' career choices. This is consistent with phase one teachers and opposite with phase two teachers.

Unlike Milkovich & Newman, (2005) who indicated that low salary has identified as the main reason contributing in teacher turnover, none of the former teacher mention about salary having any impact in their decision to depart form a private schools given the fact that private schools in district Gujrat offer very low salaries to teachers.

b) Recognition

97% teachers in the first phase and 100% in the second phase has agreed to the importance of work recognition in their career decisions. Teachers expressed their feeling as good, proud, satisfied and motivated upon receiving recognition of their work. Teachers who did not receive any recognition of their good work expressed themselves as to be disappointed and dissatisfied. More than half of the teachers believe that work recognition in any form (either monetary or non-financial) improves the productivity of teachers by increasing their morale. Few said that it is human nature to be recognised. Everyone like to be praised and appreciated even for smaller projects. This motives them to complete future tasks efficiently. Similarly, recognition enhance teachers' determination and self-confidence.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

A research study by Larry (1990) tested effects of rewards and recognition on teachers by implementing Herzberg motivational hygiene theory. The research results were consistent with the theory so are the results of the study. Similarly, the finding is consistent with Ocham & Okath (2015) who also tested how head teachers of secondary schools can motivate teachers in order to enhance their performance. Upon receiving head teachers' support in form of recognition, teachers feel more motivated. Thus, the study determined the influence of staff recognition by head teachers and found positive impact on teachers' performances leading the likelihood of their stay decisions in the schools which affirms the current study findings.

Haynes (2014) also reported that teachers stay in the profession longer when they receive incentives and recognition for their work. Similarly, Lockwood (2007) found that emotional support in form of giving positive feedback to teachers, appreciating their work efforts and

including them in decision making are important in teachers' career decisions. This also affirms teachers' high morale and confidence in leadership of the school and confirms the findings of the current study.

c) Job Satisfaction

This variable was tested only in the first phase of the research that involves exiting teachers. This was surprising to find that 81% of these teachers were satisfied (16% were highly satisfied, whereas 65% were somewhat satisfied), with their job in their current private schools at the time of data collection. Teachers mentioned many reasons to be satisfied including co-operative staff of the school. Staff include all the colleagues, management, administration and leadership of the school. 21% teachers believed that good environment was the reason of their satisfaction for working in their respective schools. Other factors that were mentioned by existing teachers to be important in their job satisfaction were love for teaching, less workload, good students and progression opportunities. These reasons are discussed further in a separate section of teachers' stay decisions.

Although, there is less percentage of existing teachers (13%) who showed dissatisfaction however the reasons they mentioned to be dissatisfied are important to discuss. Tough schedule and heavy workload found to be the top reasons behind teachers' dissatisfaction followed by low salary. Other factors contribute in ET' s dissatisfaction is lack of incentives, lack of learning material, lack of facilities, lack of enough support, lack of progression etc. Moreover, only 6% teachers are found neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their job in the respective schools.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

Mounting evidence uphold the findings of current study on teachers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction reasons such as studies by Allensworth, Ponisciak, and Masseo (2009); (Fall 2010); Howard (2003); and Ingersoll et al., (2017).

Moreover, the current study findings are also consistent with Ocham and Okoth (2015) who determined the influence of motivational practices on teachers by head teachers, involving 186 teachers and 32 head teachers from Kowiatek district and found that the cooperative leadership of the school enhances teachers' morale and satisfaction with the job. Teachers' performances are positively affected by shared leadership between head teachers and teachers. The teachers who receive head teachers' support are more motivated and satisfied which is found accurate in the current study. Similarly, the evidence suggest that recognition and good working conditions enhance teachers' level of job satisfaction, upholding the findings of the current study.

The current study findings also corresponds to the results presented by Hirsch, (2006) who claim that non-financial incentives play a role in improving teachers job satisfaction and making them stay longer (Such incentives include providing teachers with additional support, reduced load of work, better caseload, rest periods, opportunities to teach with freedom and play a role in decision making). Scafidi et al., (2007) also established that better salaries alone are not sufficient in teachers' job satisfaction and retention. To increase their job satisfaction factors such as respect, better work conditions and positive environment are vital ingredients. They also agreed that lack of opportunity to freely and effectively teach leads to the most teachers' departure. Thus, many teachers consider Job dissatisfaction to be main factor causing their leave decisions.

5.3.1.3 Early Career Teachers & Leave Intentions

The analysis of the in-hand research data collected in the first phase from the existing teachers of private schools, who have observed turnover in their particular schools, show that there are only 11% teachers who are working for more than 5 years whereas, 65% teachers have an experience of teaching under 5 years uncovering the fact that these teachers leave early in their career. This shows that the current turnover situation in private schools of district Gujrat is very high. There are a high percentage of teachers (64%) who said to continue with their respective schools or profession for 1 to 4 years, thus, intend to leave early. Moreover, existing teachers' intentions to leave early are more skewed towards young female

teachers (between ages 20-29) perhaps due to the fact that they mostly leave a profession to get married or start a family.

Likewise, only 2 former teachers out of 8, who were interviewed in the second phase, worked more than 5 years whereas 6 of them were early teachers who worked less than 5 years. This also reinstates the high turnover situation in district Gujrat private school.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The current study findings with regards to teachers' experiences and leave decisions corresponds to the study of Muller et al., (2016) who also noted with regard to the impact of teaching experience on teacher turnover that teachers with 3 years or less experience or with more than twenty years' experience are highly likely to leave the teaching whereas teachers with experience between 4 to 19 years tend to stay in the profession.

Similarly, the individual characteristics of a teacher such as age and gender play a vital role in career decisions whether to stay in teaching profession, move or quit altogether. Young teachers, often 30 years old, are more likely to leave the school compared to teachers with more age (Feng, 2006). This is consistent with the current study findings where more young teachers in first phase are found with intentions to leave early. However, it has been found in the current research that there are more female teachers in private schools compared to male teachers therefore impact of gender differences on turnover has not been identified and this was not the purpose of the study, nonetheless.

5.3.2 Factors of Teachers' Turnover in District Gujrat

The second objective of the current research was to identify the reasons of teachers' turnover in private schools in District Gujrat, Pakistan. According to Karsenti, T. & Collin, S. (2013), turnover is affected by a set of factors rather than a single factor. This is true with the current study findings where data analysis and interpretation of survey questionnaires and interview responses revealed many factors behind this phenomenon. Lack of support is the most prominent theme found behind this phenomenon. Other primary themes that emerged after

the analysis are heavy workload, dissatisfaction with working condition, student issues, low salary and personal problems.

5.3.2.1 Lack of support

It is imperative to examine the support factor as a “cumulative” phenomenon affecting teachers career decisions and regarded as the most prominent sub-theme found under the main theme of turnover factors in district Gujrat. Sub-subcategories emerged under this theme are support from administration, support from colleagues in particular; and support from principal and support from management in general. Thus, collectively, the lack of support is the highest cited reason behind teachers’ leave decisions from private schools in district Gujrat. Majority of the teachers in both phases of data collection are found to refer to the lack of support behind their decisions to leave a particular private school. Teachers stated that their decision are influenced by the lack of support and understanding. Both existing and former teachers consider lack of enough support from management, senior leadership, administration and colleagues as a strong factor affecting their leave decisions and leave intentions. But there is a difference between the thoughts of teachers from first and second phase of data collection about the type of support influencing their career decisions as existing teachers are found to be influenced by one type of support more, while former teachers are concerned about another type.

Collegial support

Former teachers are found to be mostly dissatisfied with colleagues in their respective schools leading to their departure from their respective schools. Thus, the collegial support is particularly found to be the reason behind former teachers leave decisions. While talking about colleagues, the former teachers were surprisingly found to state that jealousy and leg-pulling of fellow teachers made them highly dissatisfied and led to their lack of interest to continue with the profession in general and with the school in particular. According to former teachers, working with colleagues who are not cooperative and helpful make the job difficult. They stated that after classroom, teachers spend most of their time in the staffroom with

colleagues and, thus a lack of supportive environment in the staff room leads to the job dissatisfaction.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

The findings of current study with regards to collegial support is consistent with literature, yet there has been less attention paid to this aspect of examining turnover with relation to collegial support in previous studies. According to Swars, et al. (2009), shared value and teachers' relationship with each other is one of the five essential themes in a school. Similarly, Fall (2010) also suggested a general supportive environment that foster a collegial school culture where new teachers are provided the opportunities to interact with experienced colleagues and where colleagues are supportive to each other. NPR (2016) presented a report on attrition of teachers and revealed that teachers always demand a positive collegial environment where they can collaborate with their colleagues. They want to talk about how feel if they are supported in their efforts by getting a constant moral support. They say that they feel more satisfied in such an environment.

In addition, McCoy (2003) also reported that if new teachers have support from administrators and other colleagues, then they are more likely to remain in the teaching profession. However, it is imperative to examine the support factor as "cumulative" phenomenon consisting support from principal, assistant principal and colleagues in a particular school. The results can then be compared with support from colleagues separately that is more practicable (Gersten et al., 2001).

Administration support

In contrast to the former teachers, existing teachers surveyed during the first phase of the study are found indicating about enough administrative support available to them. This was particularly the reasons behind their satisfaction with their respective schools making them intend to stay longer accordingly. These teachers indicated that they feel satisfied with the positive behaviour of administration because it enhances their trust in schools' system overall. Thus, it can be stated that current teachers' intentions to stay are likely to be

influenced by administrative support and lack of such type of support can lead to their departure from the schools.

Evaluation of sub-sub theme

Many research studies reported that the teachers with plans to stay longer in their current school division consider administration support as being the most important factor in their career decisions (Cochran- Smith, 2004; Haynes, 2014; Ndoye, Imig, & Parker, 2010; Swars, at al., 2009). The current study findings on the relationship between administrative support and teachers' intentions to stay is consistent with the previous studies such as that conducted by Boyd et al., (2009). They suggest that the support from administration have the largest impact on career decisions by teachers. Consequently, these teachers intend to stay longer in these school. Hence, a supportive administration is vital in raising teachers' morale that plays an important part in retaining teachers in private schools. Thus, an inadequate administration support leads towards high turnover as suggested in many researches and found to be true in the current study.

The findings are also consistent with Billingsley, (2004) who found a significant relationship between administration behaviour and teacher attrition. Positive behaviour of administration results in high teacher retention and vice versa. Similarly, the satisfaction existing teachers derive from the administration in the current study corelates with the results of Haynes (2014) who also found that teachers are more satisfied with higher support from administration.

Nevertheless, the results of the current study are not coherent with a relevantly old study of Miller et al., (1999) as this study has not discovered any correlation between central office administration and teacher turnover. The different results might be dependent on the different methods employed to analyse the data or might be due to the different dependant measures adopted. However, latest studies have established the relationship between administration support and teachers' career decisions.

Management & principal support

Overall, the most important type of support required by teachers to stay longer in a school climate is found to be the collegial support and administrative support. Whereas, principal support and management support are also found influencing teachers' career decisions to a great extent especially the former teachers.

While the management was held responsible by the existing teachers for arranging staff meetings after the school timings that they considered unnecessary and nerve wrecking, the former teachers mentioned that biased attitude of management is apparent when timetable is made to suit some teachers' convenience thus making the schedule tough for others. Such issues of lack of support from not only the management but also the principal of the schools is found as prominent reasons of teachers' career decision.

There are 50% of the former teachers (4 out of 8 teachers) who complained of the lack of support from the principals. They said that leadership of the schools should not have favourites and instead they should treat every teacher equally. Same is revealed about school management who is mentioned to be unfair by 4 out of 8 former teachers thus affected these teachers career decisions who left the schools ultimately. These teachers revealed that principals and section head of the schools are biased resulting in their departure from the schools. Current research also suggests that support from the principal, in form of appreciation and inclusion of teachers in decision making, improve productivity of the teachers in a school that results in increased teacher retention. Thus, this type of support is mentioned to be important for teachers' career decisions form both phases.

Evaluation of sub-sub-theme

This finding refers to the existing study by Haynes, (2014) who reported that supportive principal is an important incentive for teachers to stay in the field. Principal play a vital role in generating efficient and collaborative work environment where teachers are included in making ongoing decisions about the curriculum and teaching instructions. These principals may act as reform leaders to promote supportive collaboration and positive social interactions among teaching staff to increase teacher retention.

Darling-Hammond, (2005) also found in her study that job dissatisfaction leads to turnover which is caused by a restrictive controls, bureaucratic leadership, and inadequate administrative support for teaching. Thus, a leadership that do not foster collaborative environment contribute in teachers' quit decisions. Whereas, Wynn et al., (2007) claimed in their study that schools need to have a combination of factors such as mentoring, positive culture and encouraging principal to retain teachers.

The current study findings are highly relevant with the research conducted by Billingsley et al., (2004) on an urban school setting that presented teachers' dissatisfaction with school factors and reported that teachers showed less dissatisfaction with principal whereas more dissatisfaction with the central administration. The results in this study discover that in an urban school setting, 25% teachers reported inadequate support from central office as a reason of their decision to leave while 20% teachers reported dissatisfaction with the principal as the main cause to quit teaching. This is true with the current research where administration support has found to be influencing teachers career decisions more than principals' support.

5.3.2.2 Heavy workload

Heavy workload is found to be the second most cited reason and a prominent factor behind teachers' main difficulties in teaching in their particular schools, their job dissatisfaction and decisions to leave or intentions to leave in future. Tough schedule due to too many numbers of teaching periods with minimum rest periods makes the workload of teachers unmanageable. Teachers revealed that they are required to stay for log meetings after school time and upon reaching home, they do not have enough time to do all copy checking and lesson planning for the next day. This increases the pile of work for the next day and so on. The current study has found 48% existing teachers indicating that they spent 6 to 8 hours outside regular school hours. They expressed excessive paperwork as being nerve wrecking, redundant, inconsistent, unnecessary and devastating for teachers because of the pressure they feel to complete the paperwork for which they do not have enough time. Thus, their work life balance is so disturbed that they ultimately decide to leave. Another prominent

factor that contribute in the excessive workload is the high caseload. There are high number of students in one classroom therefore there are more notebooks and test papers to mark. Moreover, due to high caseload, teachers cannot pay much attention to meet students' individual needs resulting in their poor performances which increases teachers' dissatisfaction levels. Thus, all these factors increase teachers' workload and they tend to leave early.

Evaluation of sub-theme

Many researchers found paperwork as a key cause of role conflict among teaching staff and consider this as a major contributor in teachers' turnover. The studies revealed a significant relationship between paperwork problems and teachers' career decisions after having controlled the other work-related variables. Paperwork increases with addition of each new student in the class as pointed out by a teacher in a study by Billingsley et al., (2004) which correlates with the current study findings where high caseload increases the amount of work on teachers.

Some qualitative studies on teacher turnover explain what an excessive paperwork mean for teachers who describe it as nerve wrecking, redundant, inconsistent, unnecessary and devastating because of the pressure they feel to complete the paperwork for which they do not have enough time. For instance, Carlson & Billingsley (2001) compared the teachers who intent to leave with those who intent to stay. He found that the workload as "not at all manageable" is a significant factor behind teachers' intention to leave compare to the teachers who intent to stay in the profession.

Qualitative studies in the form of open-ended interviews such discovered that workload in form of paperwork contribute in teachers' intentions to leave teaching. For instance, a qualitative study conducted by Lucy (2018) revealed that twenty-two percent of the teachers specifically mentioned about the nerve-wracking amount of paperwork and heavy workload causing dissatisfaction with job. One teacher stated, "the workload is mentally stressful." (p. 57). Another teacher reported, "the amount of paperwork required for my job and the

number of assessments required negatively affect the amount and quality of teaching I feel I can perform.” (p.58).

In addition, Collie, et al., (2012) reported that workload was directly related to teachers being dissatisfied with their job. According a recent survey done by the Department of Education (DoE, 2018) two-third of teachers felt overwhelmed by the amount of paperwork required in the profession. Teachers also revealed that their work-life balance is negatively affected by the heavy workload which increase their stress levels and dissatisfaction, ultimately contributing in their decisions to quit.

Similarly, Fall and Billingsley (2011) concluded in their study that teachers tend to commit to the job and stay longer when the amount of paperwork, and number of caseloads are manageable. It is also likely that the paperwork responsibility given to teacher may vary across schools and districts, hence, influence may also vary on career decisions of teachers.

Similarly, the current study findings with regard to high workload contributing in teachers' leave decisions is true with the findings of Smithers and Robinson (2003) who reported 44.8% teachers indicating that high workload is by far to be the most important factor among the five-main factor influencing turnover (i.e., *“workload, new challenge, the school situation, salary and personal circumstances”*).

Moreover, the theme of workload is found to be the dominant factor of turnover in the analysis of data collected through open ended survey questionnaire during phase one where existing teachers participated and 25% expressed their intensions to leave due to high workload. The findings are consistent with a recent survey report by the Guardian in UK, where 82% percent teachers plan to leave job in future due to unmanageable workload (Lightfoot, 2016). Workload manageability is, therefore, considered to be an important aspect in measuring the turnover rates. Moreover, in Pakistani context, Dawn News Pakistan reported that the teaching profession has lost its true glory in the country due to high workload or stress related reasons teachers found in the profession (Khalid, 2015).

5.3.2.3 Dissatisfaction with working conditions

Another leading factor found to influence teachers' career decisions in the current study is their dissatisfaction with the working conditions of the relevant schools. Such poor working conditions of a school include range of variables such as negative school climate and biased environment; lack of resources and learning material; sub-standard building; lack of facilities such as pick and drop facility, travelling allowance, medical facility, availability of staffroom and café to mention a few; and lack of progression opportunities. All these factors are discovered in the current research to be responsible for teachers' dissatisfaction with current schools' working conditions and contribute in their leave intentions.

Both existing and former teachers reveal working conditions of their relevant school to be a big factor behind their career decisions however former teachers are appeared more dissatisfied with their schools working conditions than the existing teachers. Similarly, negative climate of the school for former teachers meant biased and non-supportive climate, however they referred to this factor separate from the general support therefore included in the category of negative climate.

Additionally, former teachers stated that their current employment (in another school or another profession) offers them facilities such as medical insurance, pension, and job security, which is different from previous schools, therefore, important factors to consider staying in a school. Moreover, lack of progression is being mentioned as negative characteristic of private schools and main difficulty in carrying on teaching in the private schools of district Gujrat. Public schools offer progression opportunities which is why two former teachers left private schools to joined public schools. Thus, the findings show a negative influence of poor working conditions on teacher' retention.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The current study findings are consistent with the previous literature. Researches show that teacher retentions are affected negatively by the poor working conditions in schools (Allensworth et al., 2009; Ingersoll, 2001). The current study findings also correlate the

working conditions with teachers' job dissatisfaction. This is true with the findings of Ladd, (2011) that the working conditions of a school directly affect teachers' satisfaction with the job (Factors such as sub-standard building, furniture and supply, lack of quality resources, and poor teachers' accommodation facilities are generally neglected by schools and districts in teacher retention policies as pointed out by Imazeki (2005).

Ingersoll (2001) argued that such organizational factors cause teachers to leave the profession. Moreover, Allensworth et al. (2009) also reported in their study that school climate conditions have a significant impact on teachers' turnover rates. Additionally, the relationship between school's working conditions and teacher turnover has also been investigated by Boyd, et al. (2009). Hence the findings suggest that working condition is one of the primary factors of teachers' intentions to leave or stay in the profession.

Similarly, the working conditions of a school is a salient predictor of turnover intentions among staff compared to all other factors previously noted by McKenzie, Santiago & OECD, (2005), which corresponds to the current study findings. They assert that; "the reasons that teachers give for leaving the profession (other than retirement) confirm the pivotal role of working conditions (2005, p. 177)."

Furthermore, unlike the context of developed countries, Pakistan is a low resource developing country with terror attacks, economic instability, crises and a destroyed basic infrastructure, nevertheless, in contrast to these previous studies, the current study has surprisingly found teachers in a developing country like Pakistan revealing poor working conditions of the schools as to be a big factor behind their leave decisions. For the researcher, this was expected to be revealed somewhere after salary issues. However, the findings are consistent with Seniwoliba (2013) who reported that the teachers in developed countries, such as Ghana, are more concerned about the quality of working conditions and suitability of these conditioned with school climate. Whereas on the other hand, the teachers of schools in developing countries are stressed about other factors such as lower salaries. This is also reinstated by the results presented by Gross, & Player (2007), who indicated that working conditions are more important issue than salary and finance. It has been largely observed that

schools with less expenditure on working conditions face high teacher turnover, however, the importance of working conditions vary context to context and place to place.

5.3.2.4 Student Issues

Student related issues such as misbehaviour of students, poor performance and lack of respect for teachers are found to be among noticeable factors behind teachers' decisions to stay or leave the school and profession. This theme is emerged as a prominent theme among former teachers in the second phase of data collection compared to the existing teachers from the first phase.

A very few numbers of existing teachers (5%) mentioned that the disadvantaged students with learning issues, discipline issues and behavioural issues are the factors that contribute in their dissatisfaction and difficulties in carrying their job in particular schools in future. However, teachers indicated that high number of students in a class not only increase their workload but also leads towards low performance of students who would otherwise require individual attention. Moreover, there are no strict policies against misbehaving students and teachers are blamed for everything erroneous. They maintained that a policy or counselling facility could prevent students from disrespecting teachers and fellow students.

On the other hand, former teachers consider issues with students such as misbehaviour of students, poor performances and disciplinary issues to be equally as big factor behind their leave decision as heavy workload. 17% former teachers suggest that the students of a school are highly important in teachers' career decisions because a teacher wants to make a difference in students' lives and therefore if students do not perform as expected after teachers' hard work and effort then teachers feel demotivated and lose interest in teaching and therefore tend to leave the profession.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The current study findings are supported by many other studies in the previous literature. Previous studies have maintained that there are a range of problems that teachers encounter

with students and that result in teacher attrition. These problems include diversity of student needs, safety issues lack of students' progress, students' attitudes, and disciplinary issues (Billingsley, 2004). For instance, the findings correspond with the study of Ingersoll (2001) that reviewed teachers who depart from the profession due to dissatisfaction with their job and found lack of student motivation to progress and their discipline issues as being two major contributors to teachers' intentions to leave.

Moreover, the number of students in a classroom is also considered to be worthy of investigation with regards to teacher turnover. The current study has found that less attention is paid towards individual students due to high number of students in a classroom taught by a teacher. This results in poor performance of the students and demotivation of the teachers, which ultimately contribute to teachers' leave behaviour. However, there are mixed results in previous studies in relation with the problem of turnover due to the issue of high number of students in a classroom.

Although the current study finding is contrary to the two empirical studies by George et al., (1995) and Carlson & Billingsley (2001) who did not find any relationship of the number of students with teachers' leave intentions, however, few qualitative studies indicate a consistent relationship of the number of students and the caseload issue with teacher turnover (Morvant et al., 1995; Brownell et al., 1994-1995). Their studies reported that the number of students taught by a teacher and the students with varied type of needs contribute to teachers' leave behaviour.

Similarly, the finding is reinstated with a recent study by Tapper J., (2018) who also reported that classes are getting bigger with more enrolments into the schools resulting in poor control by few teachers. Teaching is getting difficult due to less control over the class and more stressful and heavy work. Less teaching time badly affects students' progress that can be catastrophic for teachers also and leads to turnover.

Hence, students' discipline issues were the second most prominent factor among the three main reasons of teachers leave intention in a qualitative study conducted by Lucy (2018). They found that twenty four percent teachers indicated in a response to an open-ended question

that they would leave due behavioural and disciplinary issue with students. “Student behaviour is draining” (p. 57) as mentioned by one of the participant teachers. These findings correlates with the findings of the current study with regards to students’ issues.

5.3.2.5 Low salary & lack of monetary rewards

Many existing teachers believe that the salaries paid to the teachers in the private schools are much lower than that paid to the teachers in public schools. 11% of these teachers said that low salary can contribute in their decisions to depart from the current school in future whereas 4% claim that lack of other monetary rewards such as bonuses, and cash incentives could lead to their exit from the private school education system.

While salary is one of the multiple reasons causing tendency of teachers’ leave behaviour surprisingly, low salary is not indicated as a main factor behind former teachers’ quit decisions from their previous private schools. However, when former teachers were directly asked about salaries, only 6% former teachers were interestingly discovered to indicate this in their decisions to leave. Hence, a combination of more than one factors were responsible to contribute in their decisions to depart.

Thus, teachers in both phases did refer to the importance of salary for any employee, however, they consider it less important compared to the other factors and therefore they said that they could not have left only if the salary was low. Thus, salary is found to be the least important factor behind teachers’ turnover in private education sector in Pakistan.

Evaluation of sub-theme

In contrast to many studies which indorse that a very significant predictor of teacher turnover has continued to be the salary that teachers receive, the current study shows different results. Although these studies confirm that low pay is a major factor behind teacher turnover, however, the current study finding is opposite to this. For instance, the finding is contrary to the findings in the previous studies by Feng, (2006); Hanushek, et al., (2004); Imazeki, (2002; 2005); Scafidi et al., (2007); and Stinebrickner (2002), who claim that the impact of salaries

on teachers' decision to quit the profession are very high. Their studies revealed that the higher the salaries are the lower the rates of turnover are.

Moreover, in contrast to the current research findings, a study by Tekleab, Bartol, and Liu (2005) on teachers' stay behaviour also shows that teachers stay longer with high salaries as opposed to those with lower salaries. In addition, the current study has not found teachers leaving the profession due to higher salaries in other professions. The finding is also opposite to the findings by Ondrich et al., (2008) who claim that salary differences in the teaching and non-teaching professions contribute towards teachers' career decision.

The findings of the current research is most relevant with the findings of Smithers and Robinson (2003) who present a likewise viewpoint where they consider the salary as the least important factor behind turnover whereas workload is by far the most important factor among the five-main factors influencing turnover (i.e., workload, new challenge, the school situation, salary and personal circumstances). Similarly, Billingsley et al, (2004) also conducted a research to suggest an association between salary and turnover and revealed a very low percentage of departed teachers claiming salary as being one of the prominent reasons to quit the job which correlates to the findings of the current study.

The findings of current study with regards to existing teachers corresponds to the results presented by Dolton & Newson, (2003) who indicated that higher teacher pay is particularly important to reduce teacher turnover probabilities once variances in other job opportunities are taken into account. Therefore, it is imperative to consider the other financial benefits along with salaries in relation with teachers' career persistence such as incentives, cash rewards, bonuses and compensations.

5.3.2.6 Personal issues

99 (21%) existing teachers in the first phase of the research mentioned about personal problems being salient contributors in their leave intentions. These personal problems include family related domestic issues (48%), marriage, child rearing or relocation with partners (27%), health issues (15%) and intentions for further studies (9%).

Surprisingly, the study has found no personal reasons behind former teachers' departure from private schools in the second phase of the research.

The study has not found any teachers revealing individual characteristic such as age or gender, qualification etc being reasons behind their leave intension or decisions. However, the analysis of personal data has revealed that female teachers are more skewed towards leaving the profession due to personal factors (such as, getting married or starting a family) than male teachers. Thus, the findings of the current study with regard to the marital status and fertility behaviour of female teachers influencing their decisions to stay or leave the profession is established.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The findings with regards to personal issues influencing serving teachers career decisions is consistent with the findings of Imazeki (2004) who also found that individual's marriage plays a vital role in his decision to leave especially females leave in order to have children or to relocate with their spouses. Same results are found in Stinebrickner's studies (2002) that personal or family factors affect females' decision of leaving the job more than males. However, the studies are contrary to the viewpoint presented by former teachers in the current study.

Moreover, in contrast to health issues being a noticeable factor found in the current study there has not been any such issues reported abundantly in the previous literature to be cause of teachers' quit decisions, however, stress and mental health due to high work load has been reported as a prominent factor behind this phenomenon (Lucy, 2018). Teachers' level of stress is increasing every year and becoming difficult to deal with. In fact, teachers' stress has been reported to score higher levels than that of doctors. There are several causes of stress reported for teachers such as heavy workload, poor work environment, inadequate salaries and lack of freedom to mention a few.

5.3.3 Staff Retention Strategies Based on Responses

The study has explored the range of feedback from teachers of both phases of the research with regard to potential solutions for improving teacher retention in private schools. It starts with a general feedback and recommendations made by the participant teachers to suggest retention strategies. It then prompts some discussion in relation with existing literature to test views and responses of the teachers on retention strategies. This leading to discussion prompted solutions and the development of a framework (*figure 20*) for retaining teachers in education sector of district Gujrat which is included in chapter six of this document.

The reasons of teacher turnover from the profession or from a particular school were found to be multi-layered and complex. Therefore, it was also challenging for teachers to provide potential solutions to retention issues that are not subjective as they have their emotions attached with the phenomenon. The following findings are based on the surveys conducted in the first phase with 204 teachers from private schools and interviews conducted in phase two with 8 former teachers of the private schools.

5.3.3.1 Provide facilities

Readiness of facilities provided for teachers is found to be the primary factor contributing in teachers' retention in district Gujrat based on their responses in the current research. These facilities are specifically mentioned in relation with public schools that are said to provide all these facilities to their teaching staff which private school teachers are lacking and therefore tend to leave the private education sector when they find a better opportunity.

These include medical insurance, job security, travelling allowance, paid annual leave, paid sick leave, better school location, attractive school building, and availability of café and staffroom for teachers. Existing teachers has revealed that their job satisfaction is dependent on facilities like medical insurance, travelling allowance and pick and drop especially for female staff.

14% existing teachers believe that their respective schools need to improve these facilities to improve teachers' level of satisfaction resulting in better retention of teachers in future. 28% former teacher mentioned that providing such facilities to the teachers can be useful in retaining them for longer period of time. According to these teachers, private schools should also facilitate teachers like public schools do. Whereas, 46% existing teachers see public education sector as a better job opportunity because this is a permanent job with a job security and provide facilities such as medical insurance and pension.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The response of teachers in the current research is consistent with the factors pointed out by Imazeki (2005). According to his study, these factors, such as sub-standard building, furniture and supply, lack of quality resources, and poor teachers' accommodation facilities, are generally neglected by schools and districts in teacher retention policies. Such basic facilities are matter of concern in developed countries where salaries and working conditions are non-issues, is not highly surprising. However, to find out the availability of basic facilities as the primary and most important recommendation for retention from teachers of such a small district of a developing country was highly unanticipated.

5.3.3.2 Provide enough support

Lack of support has been found to be the primary reason behind teachers' turnover in district Gujrat and when it comes to the retention policies, this factor again emerged as a prominent suggestion by the teachers in current research as a retention strategy. Therefore, the current study findings suggest that a greater level of support and understanding is required to retain teachers in private schools.

The teachers in district Gujrat are found to suggest that the availability of enough support at schools contribute in their job satisfaction levels. These teachers believe that support from senior leadership such as principal or head of the school, administration, management as well as colleagues support can be improved in order to make teachers feel highly satisfied and stay in a particular school.

Former teachers also suggested that availability of support is very important in retaining teachers as this could have changed their decision to leave. The support from colleagues and head of school is particular in this respect. It was also revealed that new teachers need more support as they tend to leave early if they are not supported by their seniors in the start of their career.

The types of support teachers pointed out include understanding of those problems; teachers face during the early years of teaching. These teachers also spoke high for the respect as one type of support that they should receive from senior leadership. They mentioned that respect from school authorities, as well as from students is highly important for their inner satisfaction. The more teachers are satisfied, the longer they will stay. In addition, freedom to work independently was another type of support pointed out by the teachers. These teachers maintained that their efficiency is affected under a controlled system where leadership is autoreactive and non-supportive. Similarly, including teachers in important decisions at administration level also contribute in teachers' stay decisions as mentioned by few teachers. Thus, varied types of support are required by the teachers to improve their satisfaction leading to a better teacher retention.

Evaluation of sub-theme

Previous studies also correspond to this important strategy of retaining teachers. According to Fall (2010) a facilitative leadership style of a principal is most effective in retaining the teachers. Research suggests that an effective leadership from a principal improve productive collegial work in an organised school that results in increased teacher retention. Principal play an important role in generating efficient and collaborative work environment where teachers are included in making ongoing decisions about the curriculum and teaching instructions. Studies on school improvements maintain that principals can use the school structure and their authority to encourage collaborative staff in order to achieve common goals. For successful initiatives to implement effective policies and improve school's work environment, the role of a principal is crucial. These principals may act as reform leaders to promote

supportive collaboration and positive social interactions among teaching staff to increase teacher retention.

Brown and Wynn (2009) conducted a study with principals in an urban school district to identify different characteristics present and strategies used to recruit and retain teachers in their schools. They found that districts should ensure that principals are strong supportive leaders. Similarly, Bennett et al., (2013) also found a significant relationship between supportive administration behaviour and teacher retention. Positive behaviour of administration results in high teacher retention and vice versa. This implies that if the management and administration is supportive teachers are less likely to leave.

However, it is very important to review the most important type of support required by teachers to stay longer in a school climate. These include emotional on one hand and instructional support on the other. Emotional support denotes to maintaining open communication with staff, appreciating their work, giving positive feedback and making them feel included in the decision-making process. Instructional support is about providing required resources, space and material.

The study by Ingersoll & Strong (2011) also pointed towards the impact of induction and mentoring program and found that leadership support in form of such program influence teachers career decision in a positive manner. Similarly, Petty et al., (2011) stated that to retain teachers, leaders should provide teachers with the necessary support which included to provide teachers with the opportunity to be heard.

The literature reviewed for the current study shows that by implementing teacher friendly strategies, such as by lessening the bureaucratic systems in schools and by promoting the more genuine support from school leaders and administration, teacher retention can be improved.

5.3.3.3 Salary increments & monetary rewards

Although, in the current research, salary has not been found as a driving factor behind turnover of teachers in district Gujrat, however, this is found as being third in the list of recommendations provided by the teachers to improve retention. This can therefore be implied that salary although is not important in teachers' leave decisions, however, it is important in their stay decisions. 21% existing teachers expressed that their level of job satisfaction can be improved by offering an attractive salary increments annually. They believe that salary play a big role in stay decisions and as the inflation is rising so should the salaries to help teachers financially in order to retain them in the profession.

Unlike existing teachers who consider salary being the first factor that contribute in teachers' stay decision, only 10% former teachers believe that increments in salary could have changed their decision to leave. Former teachers mentioned that other factors are more important than salary. For these teachers a school's positive environment, dignity of teachers, supportive administration, recognition of work and inclusion is what could have made them stay longer in particular schools.

Moreover, most of the schools surveyed seemed to have students who belong to middle class families who could not afford to pay high school fees, leading to low salaries of teachers resulting in higher turnover rates. Nonetheless, those schools with relatively better financial positions also pay inadequate salaries. Thus, it is important to make policy makers and school directors conscious of the low salaries and its influence of on teachers' turnover. Many teachers felt that the salary they are receiving did not match the workload teachers has to manage. Others mentioned that teachers should be able to go for paid holidays for certain number of days in the year within the term time especially when they are ill.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The recommendations with regard to salary increments are consistent with previous studies and reports. Indiana General Assembly's study committee on education also claim that salary may not be the reason for someone to enter into the teaching field however it may influence

their decision to remain (Herron, 2017). Boe, et al., (2008) also revealed in their study that teachers are said to stay with high salaries as opposed to those with lower salaries. In addition, according to Milkovich & Newman (2005), compensation and benefits are one of the most attractive rewards in recruitment process as well as in teachers' stay decisions which also consistent with the current study findings where teachers suggested financial benefits and rewards as important retention strategies.

While on one hand, Ondrich et al., (2008) indicated that substantial increase in teachers' salary alone would not be sufficient to dramatically turn the situation around and retain quality staff with if there is a large concentration of disadvantaged students in a school which is true with the current study findings. On the other hand, Hanushek, et al., (2004), pointed out that school and districts can take advantage during hiring and recruiting teachers by offering competitive salaries as a staff retention policy because districts can set teachers' salaries at competitive level as this variable is in the control of officials while they do not have control over other variables such as socio-economic background of the students.

Moreover, Hammond & Ducommun (2007), pointed out that the incentives during the recruitment are necessary to attract and keep skilled teachers in these schools. Similarly, monetary incentives such as cash rewards, bonuses, increments or progression onto a higher paid position are used as recruitment strategy by many large district schools (Dolton & Newson, 2003). However, the effects of using these financial incentives as retention strategy are debateable.

5.3.3.4 Appreciation & recognition of work

Numerous teachers in the current study reported that in teaching profession recognition of work is a way of increasing respect of teachers which improve retention as a result. Teachers felt that lack of understanding and expertise need to be fixed before implementing other strategies to retain teachers. Although, the suggestions teachers made did not explain the way of achieving the required results, however, it was clear that respect and recognition in form of support would influence them to stay in the sector for long.

Verbal appreciation and recognition of work are found to be mentioned by existing teachers as adding in their level of job satisfaction. 12% teachers said that they want appreciation of their work in schools. They said that teachers work hard, and their efforts must be appreciated by senior leadership to increase their morale and satisfaction. They mentioned about appreciation of work both verbally as well as in form of cash because they claim that cash rewards help them financially as well.

Similarly, though not a high a very high percentage however former teachers (7%) did suggest the importance of work recognition by senior leadership in order to retain teachers in the profession. This factor is a part of support from school authorities however the researcher deems to consider it important to discuss separately because the researcher found teachers mentioning it separately from a general support. These teachers reckon that work recognition is very important to motivate teachers and make them work even better. This is especially important to increase teachers' morale and satisfaction resulting in teacher retention.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The findings are consistent with Herzberg motivational hygiene theory (1983) which emphasis on employees' job satisfaction as a strategy to retain them longer. Similarly, the finding is consistent with Ocham & Okath (2015) who tested how head teachers of secondary schools can motivate teachers in order to enhance their performance. The head teachers' support in form of recognition and appreciation makes the teachers more motivated. Thus, the study determined the influence of staff recognition by head teachers and found positive impact on teachers' performances leading the likelihood of their stay decisions in the schools. This also affirms teachers' high morale and confidence in leadership of the school and confirms the findings of the current study.

Haynes (2014) also informed that teachers tend to stay longer in the profession when they receive incentives and recognition for their work. Similarly, Lockwood (2007) found that emotional support in form of giving positive feedback to teachers, appreciating their work efforts and including them in decision making are important in teachers' career decisions. This

also affirms teachers' high morale and confidence in leadership of the school and confirms the findings of the current study.

According to Lockwood (2007), to attract and retain employees in any organisation the mission of HR should be fostering a positive and encouraging workplace environment where teachers are recognised for their hard work and given due rewards. This also refers to the intrinsic rewards important at the time of recruitment (Patton and Kristonis, 2006). Thus, satisfying teachers' intrinsic motivation by recognising their work and appreciating them make them feel satisfied and stay longer in the profession.

5.3.3.5 Decrease in workload

Another factor important for policy makers to consider is the amount of workload on teachers. This was one of the dominant factors found behind teachers leave decisions. Therefore, reducing workload on teachers can make them stay longer. Teachers from both phases of data collection pointed towards the reduction of workload for teachers as recommendation for teacher retention. This means much more manageable caseloads, less paperwork, flexible work schedule with sufficient rest period, and flexibility to work independently.

There had been many suggestions made by the participant teachers to address the issue of overwork. Some suggested that there was no need of re-writing the lesson plan. The other mentioned to have freedom to adapt and annotate the plans instead. Some considered it to be undue pressure on teachers by the schools for accountability purposes and believe that the details the schools require to include in lesson plans are unnecessary. Therefore, the extra workload in form of lesson planning can be minimized with the development of a central scheme of study.

Another suggestion to decrease the workload was to reduce the larger class sizes. Teachers claimed that larger classes are challenging to manage, and it is hard to develop individual connections with students in larger classes. Marking and providing individual feedback to students becomes highly difficult for teachers. The students also get less individual attention

and thus produce less quality work. Teachers also complain of misbehaving students and believe that this is mostly due to larger class sizes. Therefore, in order to decrease workload and to have better teacher retention, class sizes need to be reduced as suggested by participants.

Evaluation of sub-theme

Previous studies revealed a significant relationship between paperwork problems and teachers' career decisions after having controlled the other work-related variables. Paperwork increases with addition of each new student in the class as pointed out by a teacher in a study by Billingsley et al., (2004) which correlates with the current study findings where high caseload increases the amount of work on teachers and reducing workload can improve teacher retention.

In addition, the study findings are also consistent with Collie, et al., (2012) who found that reduced workload was directly related to teachers being satisfied with their job and therefore they stay longer in the profession. Similarly, Fall and Billingsley (2011) also concluded in their study that teachers are more likely to stay committed to their schools when the amount of work such as paperwork, and number of caseloads are manageable which is true with the current study results. However, it is also likely that the paperwork responsibility given to teacher may vary across schools and districts, hence, influence may also vary on career decisions of teachers.

5.3.3.6 Improved students

Some other suggestions for better retention made by the teachers in both phases are student related suggestions such as improved student behaviour, better conduct, better learning skills and good performances. Surprising facts are found in survey questionnaire where teachers complain about misbehaving students as frustrating and disturbing. Many teachers said that their satisfaction in particular school can be increased if the schools develop and implement

policies against misbehaving students. The higher their satisfaction level is, the longer they will stay. They said that there should be a system of reward and punishment for good and bad students respectively. These teachers think that students bring high fees to these private schools and therefore they are not punished or expelled if they misbehave with teachers resulting in teachers being less respectful, dissatisfied and demotivated; and therefore, leave the school or profession.

Evaluation of sub-theme

These student related suggestions are in line with the study of Ondrich et al, (2008) who found that in order to raise teacher retention rates in poor urban districts with more disadvantaged students is highly unlikely. For example, schools with more disadvantaged students face teachers' mobility at higher rate compared to schools with relatively more advantage students. The working environment with disadvantaged students is quite challenging which makes it difficult for teachers to alter their quit decisions regardless of increase in their salary.

Ingersoll (2001) also reviewed teachers who depart from the profession due to high dissatisfaction level with their job and found lack of student motivation to progress and their discipline issues as being two major contributors to teachers' intentions to leave and vice versa.

However, in a contrary study, Loeb et al., (2005) found to suggest that positive working conditions of a school can negate the problem of disadvantaged students. This finding cannot be reciprocated with the current study findings.

5.3.3.7 Respect for teachers

Respect can be a big motivation to retain teachers in the profession as recommended by many teachers and especially by former teachers in the current study. Former teachers said that they joined the profession due to respect and nobility of the profession in the society. They believe that there were better respectful attitudes towards teaching profession back in the days, however, they do not receive the due respect now a days from school authorities,

students and parents of students, which became one of the reasons of their quit from that school.

Similarly, existing teachers pointed out that respectful behaviour of school authorities, students and parents of students motivate them to stay in the profession. Therefore, due respect should be given to teachers by all of them to retain them in the profession as suggested by participant teachers.

Evaluation of sub-theme

Teachers are the builders of society and therefore deserve a high respect from all the social departments. According to Plucker & Slavkin, (2000), compared to prior generation teachers, there is limited respect teachers receive from the community in these days. This is in line with the current study findings where former teachers said that they do not receive the due respect from school authorities, students and parents of students.

The findings commend to the previous studies of Khan, (1974), Firestone & Rosenblum, (1988) and Gonzalez, (1995) who reported that without respect from the school staff and students as well as from the community, it is unlikely for teachers to attain job satisfaction and remain committed to the profession. Thus, respect can be a big motivation to retain teachers as recommended by many teachers and especially by former teachers and also indorsed by the existing literature.

5.3.3.8 Availability of resources

Though not a high percentage came to suggest availability of quality resources as a retention strategy, but it is held important to discuss this factor in relation with better retention of teachers. The resources include learning material and aids specifically. The class learning aids such as duster, chalks, markers, etc as well as IT material such as computers and projectors are some. In addition, teachers mentioned about high standard building with health and safety measurement, good supply of furniture, availability of café and staffroom to mention a few. It was surprising to find that teachers of a big city like Gujrat are highly concerned about

the lack of basic facilities like staffroom and did consider it important in retaining teachers in private schools.

Evaluation of sub-theme

The study findings are consistent with the study of Ocham and Okoth (2015) who involved 186 teachers and 32 head teachers from Koibatek district in their research and determined the effects of motivational practices on them. The study found that the support from head teachers in form of material and resource availability enhance teachers' morale and satisfaction with the job.

There is a mounting evidence to indicate that teachers' retention decisions are significantly affected by schools' characteristics including availability of resources, material, textbook and facilities (Kukla-Acevedo, 2009; Ingersoll, 2001; Boyd et al., 2009; Allensworth, Ponisciak, & Mazzeo, 2009; Loeb, Darling-Hammond, & Luczak, 2005; Johnson & Birkeland, 2003; Feng, 2006).

However, unlike the context of developed countries, Pakistan is a low resource developing country therefore lack of resources was not among the noticeable causes of teachers' leave behaviour. Whereas on the other hand, in such countries with terror attacks, economic instability, crises and a destroyed basic infrastructure, creating an appropriate teaching learning environment is highly challenging due to lack of necessary resources (Glewwe, P., 2011).

5.3.3.9 Other factors

There were some other factors mentioned by teachers of both phases to be held important in teachers' stay decisions. Few particular suggestions made by existing teachers to improve their levels of satisfaction include progression opportunities, teachers' training programs, teachers' inclusions in decision making, reduction in teacher student ratio in a class, freedom and flexibility and positive school environment. Positive working environment is appeared to be highly important in existing teachers' mobility decisions.

Moreover, the recommendations that are important to consider in retaining teachers mentioned by the former teachers are staff cooperation, positive and unbiased school environment, better behaving students, freedom and flexibility to work independently, inclusion of teachers in policy and decision making. The former teachers thought that the freedom to teach with less dictations on how they should teach and how to plan lessons is the best strategy that can increase teachers' independency and improve retention as a result. There should be more flexibility and fewer constraints from policy makers. These teachers required for greater trust in their abilities and wanted to teach according to their own expertise and according to the individual needs of the students.

Similarly, as poor climate conditions have been found a prominent reason of turnover, a positive and fair climate of a school can have reverse impacts resulting in better retention as suggested by the teachers in the current research. Previous studies on teacher retention show the negative influence of poor climate conditions on retention teachers, both new and experienced (Allensworth et al., 2009; Ingersoll, 2001). The studies also show the negative impact of such conditions on student achievements (DeAngelis & Presley, 2011; Sebring, et al., 2006).

5.4 SUMMARY

In this chapter, the research findings are discussed in detail with regard to existing literature. Work environments play an important role in teachers' career decisions in terms of their job satisfaction. There are many research studies that imply range of analytical approaches to find out the relationship between work environment and turnover rates. Work environment is comprised of various variables that, either single or combined, contribute towards teachers' attrition and retention. These variables include all the school characteristics such working conditions, salary, excessive workload, inadequate support from administration & colleagues, lack of opportunities to develop and progress, lack of facilities, availability and quality of resources and student-related issues.

For the majority of teachers, the driving factors behind their leave decisions were several and overlapping, although for some there was a key factor more prominent than the other. For instance, the quit decision of one teacher had been a trigger incident around a lack of recognition of her performance, and for the other, a specific behavioural incident involving head or principal of the school. Similarly, for few teachers, a better opportunity outside the teaching profession led them quit.

However, the surprising fact was found after interviewing the former teachers when neither of teacher reported that their decision to leave had been driven by personal reasons such as health issues or family related problems and neither by low salaries. Former teachers found it difficult to carry on with previous school and left due to several reasons. Staff clashes and jealousy among colleagues in the previous school was the biggest factor mentioned by former teachers. Other difficulties include autocratic senior leadership, non-cooperative colleagues, administration and management, job timings, disadvantaged students, lack of progression, biased environment and heavy workload. Job security, standard of education and lack of respect prompted them to seek alternative schools/jobs.

In existing teachers, some mentioned that the decision to leave can be triggered by a family issue. This include, for example, they want to devote more time to their family and children. Similarly, health related issues appeared to influence the existing teachers most compared to work related factors.

Moreover, several recommendations made by the participant teachers are discussed in this chapter and are also evaluated against existing literature in order to test the practicality of the suggestions. Most teachers suggest providing fundamental facilities to teachers to retain them longer in the schools. These facilities include travel allowances, paid leaves, availability of material, café and staffroom especially for female teachers. The opportunity to progress is also considered to be a facility by many teachers as they compare these with public school facilities. Similarly, better support, decrease in workload, work recognitions, salary increments, and rewards, are also some of the suggestions made by the teachers in order to improve teacher retention.

6 CHAPTER SIX: TEACHER RETENTION FRAMEWORK, RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS & FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter concludes the research study by informing the reader about how far the research objectives have been achieved. This chapter also presents the manner in which the research contributed in the body of knowledge on three levels; i.e., theoretical, practical and methodological contribution.

A teacher retention framework is devised by the researcher based on recommendations made by the teachers under study and discussion prompted solutions to inform the policy makers in district Gujrat in order to address and resolve the issue of turnover and encourage teaching staff to remain in the profession. The chapter concludes by presenting the research limitations, implications and future recommendations.

6.2 ACHIEVEMENT OF RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

6.2.1 Research Objective One

To evaluate the current scenario of teachers' turnover in private schools' sector in Pakistan.

The first objective of the study was to explore the current scenario of teachers' turnover. This objective is achieved with the analysis of the first key theme and its sub themes and sub-subthemes. Teachers' reasons to enter the profession show their initial interest and passion however, their dissatisfaction with either schools in particular or with teaching job itself led to their departure. Teachers also expressed their views about some workplace components that they consider important in their decisions to continue with or leave teaching profession. The analysis of the personal data of teachers such as teaching experience of both existing and

former teachers as well as intentions of existing teachers to continue with the profession also show the current turnover situation of the private schools in district Gujrat. Existing teachers who have observed turnover in their particular schools, show that there are only 11% teachers who are working for more than 5 years whereas, 65% teachers have an experience of teaching under 5 years uncovering the fact that these teachers leave early in their career. This shows that the current turnover situation in private schools of district Gujrat is very high. There are a high percentage of teachers who said to continue with their respective schools or profession for less than 5 years. Moreover, 75% former teachers departed from the profession in less than 5 years. This also reinstates the high turnover situation in district Gujrat private school.

6.2.2 Research Objective Two

To identify the reasons for teachers' turnover in private schools in District Gujrat, Pakistan.

This study has achieved the second objective of the research by identifying several reasons for teachers' turnover in private schools in district Gujrat under the second key theme of the research findings. Some reasons are more prominent than the others, as teachers have their individual needs to be satisfied at job. Similarly, one teacher is appeared to be more concerned about one factor such as working conditions of the school, whereas the other is found to be apprehensive about work recognition and support. Thus, the overall findings suggest that a lack of enough support and poor heavy workload are the most prominent factors contribute in teachers' leave decisions in district Gujrat.

Support factor is studied as a "cumulative" phenomenon affecting these teachers. Subcategories emerged under this theme are support from administration, support from colleagues in particular; and support from principal and support from management in general. However, there is a difference between existing and former teachers' thoughts about the type of support influencing their career decisions more than the other. The collegial support is particularly found to be the reason behind former teachers leave decisions. In contrast, existing teachers surveyed during the first phase of the study are found indicating

about enough administrative support available to them. This was particularly the reasons behind their satisfaction with their respective schools making them intend to stay longer and vice versa.

The study has found both existing and former teachers imply that the workload in the private schools in district Gujrat is very high due to excessive paperwork and time constraints contributing in their leave decisions consequently. Tough schedule with minimum rest periods, unnecessary paperwork, lesson planning, stress of meeting deadlines and dealing with high caseload all add to the heavy workload.

Another leading factor found to influence teachers' career decision in the current study is teachers' dissatisfaction with the working conditions of the relevant schools. There are many subthemes found under this category such as negative school climate and biased environment; lack of resources and learning material; sub-standard building; lack of facilities such as pick and drop facility, travelling allowance, availability of staffroom and café to mention a few; and lack of progression opportunities. All these factors are discovered in the current research to be responsible for teachers' dissatisfaction with current schools' working conditions and contribute in their leave intensions.

Moreover, Student related issues such as misbehaviour of students, poor performance and lack of respect for teachers are found to be among noticeable factors behind teachers' decisions to stay or leave the school and profession.

Other evident factors found behind turnover is low salary, however, only existing teachers are found to mention this as a reason whereas no former teacher has stated salary as being a reason for them to depart from the schools. Personal reasons are also found to add in the situation, nevertheless, the main objective of the research was to identify the work-related reasons behind teachers' turnover.

6.2.3 Research Objective Three

To examine the options for staff retention strategies available to be used in teaching sector in Pakistan.

This objective has been achieved successfully after evaluating the recommendations made by the participant teachers of private schools in Gujrat as well as discussing and evaluating the available teacher retention strategies in review of the exiting literature in order to test the practicality of the suggestions. Most teachers suggest providing fundamental facilities to teachers to retain them longer in the schools. These facilities include travel allowances, paid leaves, availability of material, café and staffroom especially for female teachers. The opportunity to progress is also considered to be a facility by many teachers as they compare these with public school facilities. Similarly, decrease in workload such as elimination of unnecessary paperwork and reduce the number of students against one teacher (pupil-teacher ratio) has been suggested by the teachers to improve satisfaction level of teachers. Moreover, better working conditions, work recognitions, salary increments, and rewards, support are also some of the suggestions made by the teachers in order to improve teacher retention.

6.2.4 Research Objective Four

To develop a successful teacher retention framework to help retain teaching staff in private schools in Pakistan.

This objective has been achieved successfully by developing a teacher retention framework for policy makers to retain teachers in district Gujrat based on the recommendations made by the participant teachers as well as discussions prompted solutions (*Refer to section 6.3.2 & figure 23*).

6.3 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

This research study has made the following contributions in the body of knowledge. These contributions are categorised on two levels; i.e., contribution on theoretical as well as on practical level.

6.3.1 Theoretical Contribution

The in-hand research study stipulated information about factors behind teachers' turnover and retention and other significant attributes related to teachers themselves as well as about schools in Pakistani private education sector that may be helpful to update policy makers in their decisions to improve teachers' retention.

In this period of growing demands and pressures it was considered to be worthy to investigate the leading factors that govern the continuity or departure of a teacher from the profession. The best and straight method to attain the actual reasons behind this was to directly investigate for the feedback from the teachers about their own individual understandings and how these influenced their views about the profession. There was no direct study from this perspective in district Gujrat, Pakistan, especially at school level, consequently, more pragmatic analyses were needed to appropriately endeavour to assess the causes affecting teacher shortages within the specific areas of the Pakistan.

Table 10 in chapter 4 shows that the teacher turnover factors categorised in the with the existing theories of Billingsley et al. and Brownell et al. the former do not include teachers' relationships with staff (mesosystem/social factors), and teachers' relationships with students (microsystem/social factors) as factors contributing to teachers' turnover. Whereas the later lacks a heavy workload and poor work conditions (task -related/employment factors) as important factors of teacher turnover. However, the present study has found these factors to be highly important in teachers' career decisions in the context of district Gujrat, Pakistan.

This study has, therefore, addressed the issue of teacher turnover and found various factors causing the problem. The study has also proposed a strategic framework of retention for policy makers in district Gujrat, Pakistan (*see figure 23*).

6.3.2 Practical Contribution/Retention Framework

In private education sector in Pakistan, less attention has been paid towards retaining existing teachers than recruiting new teachers by the policy makers though managing the supply of teachers by retaining them in the field is proved to be more cost effective.

Elimination of the factors causing teacher turnover alone is not sufficient to improve teacher retention as the study has found large difference between these two. Therefore, a careful strategy is needed to implement to reduce turnover and improve retention. The challenge for the research, therefore, lies in how to structure and propose a retention framework in order to address and resolve the teacher turnover in District Gujrat and make the framework applicable nationwide despite the lack of resources.

Thus, the framework of retention below (*figure 23*) is devised based on the recommendations made by the sample teachers of both phases as well as the discussion prompted solutions. The framework also corresponds to the fourth objective of the study.

Figure 6.1: Teacher Retention Framework

Following is the detail discussion on the retention solutions laid out in the framework that how these can be achieved.

6.3.2.1 Reward System

A reward system that fulfils teachers’ financial and emotional needs can be put in place to improve teacher retention. Teaching in private schools should be well-paid with annual increments and other monetary rewards such as bonuses to satisfy teachers’ financial needs. Similarly, non-financial rewards such as including teachers in schools’ decision making and giving them continuous appreciation and recognition of their work will motivate them and increase their commitment with work. Such motivational practices will also enhance their morale and satisfaction with the job and make them stay longer in private schools.

6.3.2.2 Support System

There is a great need to change the culture of private schools by imbedding it with a supportive climate, trust and respect. A support system for teachers offering open door policy with open communication from the head of the schools will enhance the trust as well as respect between the leadership and the teachers. This will also help to improve trust and respect between staff and parents in order to devise and implement behavioural policies for students. Thus, the support, trust and respect are reciprocal. Moreover, the management should also leave behind the old autocratic style and adopt facilitative leadership style to motivate teachers and increase their job satisfaction in order to make them stay longer in private schools.

6.3.2.3 Behavioral Policies

Misbehavior of students and disrespect have been found to be contributing teachers' stress levels and therefore, they mentioned about this issue not only in turnover factors but also in retention factors. It is sad that private schools, especially with high fees, in Pakistan do not have any behavioral policies in place to counter such issues with students. Therefore, a suggestion is made to introduce such policies in the schools. Many teachers said that their satisfaction in particular school can be increased if the schools develop and implement policies against misbehaving students.

For this purpose, the policy makers should introduce a reward and punishment system for students. Rewarding those students with positive attitude and respectful behavior will also motivate all other students. This will also have an impact on parents and motivate them to facilitate their children towards developing positive attitudes which ultimately develop a relationship of trust and respect between parents and teachers increasing teachers' motivation at the same time.

6.3.2.4 Work Conditions

In addition, improved working conditions with all necessary ingredients such as job security, progression opportunity, availability of resources and material, and other basic facilities can retain teachers in private schools of district Gujrat. There is not much attention paid in Pakistani private schools towards making work conditions better in order to retain teachers. In contrast, public schools offer better job security and other benefits that attract teachers from private schools in particular.

The private schools offer zero-hour contracts with minimum or no chances of progression. Thus, the heads of the private schools (mostly owners) should pay more attention towards implementing attractive recruitment policies. Offering permanent contract-based teaching positions with progression opportunities and facilities such as medical allowance, travel allowance etc, and other benefits such as necessary learning aids and material, will attract more graduates to teaching in private schools and will retain them longer in the profession.

6.3.2.5 Elimination of Workload

Likewise, decrease in heavy workload, by making it less nerve wrecking can improve retention. This can be achieved by reducing paperwork and by introducing a central scheme of study with a flexibility and freedom for teachers to revise and modify it to cater the needs of the students. Private schools also need to have better staffrooms for teachers where teachers spent most of their time marking notebooks and doing all the paperwork. This will help lessen the level of stress on teachers. Moreover, enough rest periods can decrease the burden of work and increase teachers' level of satisfaction ultimately leading to better retention.

6.4 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

- Handwritten Data

The data collected for the research study was in the form of hard copies. This was the biggest limitation of the study because the use of technology in Pakistan is very limited and even professionals are not very familiar with giving online responses to survey questionnaires. However, if the data was collected electronically, the analysis would have been less time consuming and required less effort, which was not possible as the current research population belonged to a small district in Punjab Pakistan, where people are still not very familiar in using e-technology especially in terms of giving their feedback and responses to an electronic surveys and questionnaires. This was, therefore, the biggest limitation of the research.

- Accessibility & Bias

Another limitation of the study was a direct access to the serving teachers who were potential participants of the study. All the survey questionnaires were administered through central office or through principal therefore there was a high chance of getting biased responses. However, the study also included interviews of departed teachers to not only get honest and unbiased responses but also get the opinions of the actual leavers who experienced turnover themselves.

- Less secondary Data

Availability of secondary data on the data in the context of district Gujrat could have made the comparisons easier and check the validity of the primary data gathered. However, there was neither a single research study found in district Gujrat nor enough data about private schools in Pakistan. Therefore, this was another limitation to conduct the research on the issue.

- Time Consuming & Expensive

The data collection was very time consuming and incurred cost because 300 surveys had been printed initially as well as all the surveys were distributed in person by visiting all the participant schools and similarly the collection of filled surveys was made upon several visits. This was due to the lack of technological use in Pakistan and another big limitation of the study.

6.5 RESEARCH IMPLICATION

The current research has a significance for all internal as well as external stakeholders of the education system because the issue of turnover affects them all. The internal stakeholders comprise all relevant people in the school environment, such as teachers, students, administration, management, principal or head of the schools and policy makers. Many researches show that students' performance is negatively affected in schools by the turnover of teachers year after year. Therefore, retaining effective staff is highly important for students' achievements.

Similarly, external stakeholders, like parents, are also important to take into account when devising policies. There needs to be an open communication and understanding between teachers and parents for higher satisfaction and to avoid turnover.

The research is done in district Gujrat where no previous research is found in this context. Although there is less percentage of teachers who leave due to personal reasons or reasons that schools have no control over, the higher percentage is of teachers who leave due to school related factors such as, the school environment. Lack of availability of relevant research data on the issue of turnover, thus, makes it difficult for school's policy makers to measure the severity and implication of the problem. As a result, factors that influence turnover and retention become challenging to understand.

The research has social implications as well as practical implications. On social level, teachers should receive appreciation and work recognition in form of incentives, rewards and bonuses. Freedom to teach independent will enhance their self-confidence and morale in the profession. On practical level, a support system for teachers that provide them not only non-monetary benefits such as trust and respect but also resources and progression opportunities will improve their job satisfaction and make them stay longer in the profession. The policy implications for the school boards, state and national legislators include the need to be aware of the factors influencing teacher career decisions.

Therefore, the current research is highly applicable for the stakeholders to understand work related reasons of turnover and based on teachers' responses a staff retention policy can be developed and implemented.

6.6 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

The current research study was done on the problem of high turnover in private schools in Pakistan. For the future researches following recommendations are made:

- A research can be done using larger sample of private schools on province level including other nearby districts to compare the results of those with district Gujrat.
- The current study has not surveyed public school teachers so a further comparative research can be carried out in this regard to compare private and public-school attrition behaviour of teachers and to identify the key difference between these two educator providers.
- A comparative research study can also be done to identify the reasons of turnover with regards to male and female teachers and evaluate the differences in them.
- A research study can be done to ascertain the influence of high turnover issue on students' achievement in district Gujrat.
- A study can be done on the issue including principal, management and administration of the schools for the wider prospects.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: Participant Information Sheet

Dear Potential Participant

I am a DBA (Doctorate in Business Administration) student at University of the West of Scotland (UWS), London Campus, carrying out a research study in Pakistani education sector. I would like to invite you to take part in this research study. Before you decide whether to participate, it is important for you to understand why the study is being conducted and what is involved. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study is an individual research being carried out to identify and explore the work-related reasons behind teachers' turnover rate in Pakistan. Turnover rate is the rate at which teachers depart/quit from the profession. Therefore, the purpose to carry out this research is to develop a successful staff retention framework for education sector in Pakistan.

What is the importance of this study?

In an era of increasing pressures and demands on teachers the principle factors that determine whether a teacher remains in the profession or leaves is worthy of investigation. The most direct way to arrive at this point is to ask for input from the teachers about their own personal experiences and how these affect their perceptions of education as a career. There is no direct study from this perspective in district Gujrat, Pakistan, especially at school level, consequently, more pragmatic analyses are needed to appropriately endeavour to assess the reasons for teacher shortages within specific areas of the Pakistan.

What does take part in the study involve?

Taking part in this study would involve you to complete a survey questionnaire or answering interview questions. This will take approximately 15-20 minutes. You are **free to withdraw** from study at any time by contacting the researcher and without giving any reason.

Are there any benefits to join the study?

There will be no immediate direct benefit to you should you participate. However, there should be benefits for the education sector of the country overall and to the future policies regarding teachers' recruitment because the results of study are likely to influence how turnover rates of teachers can be reduced.

How will the information/responses be used and kept confidential?

The information will be used for the purpose of analysing and formulating results of this research **only**. Your personal information and that of your school will be kept **strictly confidential** and will not be disclosed to any individual at any time. The data will be discarded safely after formulating the results.

Who should I contact if I need more information?

If anything is not clear, or if you would like more information, please contact on the following:

Name: Salma Nazim

Phone: [REDACTED]

Email: [REDACTED]

Thank you in advance for your participation.

Sincerely,

Salma Nazim

APPENDIX 2: Consent Form

Title of Project: A Study of Factors behind Teachers' Turnover in Pakistan

Name of Researcher: Salma Nazim

Email: [REDACTED]

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information sheet dated.....for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that the information collected about me will be used to support other research in the future and may be shared anonymously with other researchers.

3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without my legal rights being affected.

4. I agree to take part in the above study

Name of Participant (optional) Date Signature

Name of Person taking consent Date Signature

APPENDIX 3: Survey Questionnaire (phase 1)

Section A: Demographic Data

Please provide the following information.

1. Please specify your gender.

- Male
- Female
- Other

2. Please specify appropriate age bracket you belong to.

- 20-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60+

3. Please specify your marital status:

- Married
- Unmarried
- Engaged

4. Please specify the highest degree/certificate achieved:

- M.Phil./Doctorate
- MA/MSc
- BA/BSc
- FA/FSc.

5. Teaching experience in the current school (*duration*): _____

6. You expect to continue with the current job for?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-4 years
- 5-9 years

- 10-14
- 15-19
- 20 or more years

7. Primary subject(s) of teaching: _____

8. On average, how many hours per week do you spend on class work outside the regular school day? _____

Section B: Turnover Factors

9. (a) Was teaching your career aspiration before you enter the profession?

- Yes
- No

(b) What was/were the reason(s) to join teaching as a career?

10. Do you think that recognition (pay rise, bonuses, awards etc.,) is important to motivate you as a teacher? Why do you think this way?

11. Last time you accomplished a project, did you receive any recognition? How did you feel?

12. Do you think salary is important in your decision to stay or leave the job? How?

13. What one thing you think needs improvement in the current school?

14. What one thing makes working in current job difficult?

15. (a) How would you rate your satisfaction level in your current job at this school?

- Highly satisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Highly dissatisfied

(b) Please tell us why do you feel this way?

16. What one thing school can do to make you feel more satisfied (even if you are highly satisfied)?

17. If you were to leave/quit tomorrow, what would your two reasons be?

Thank you very much for your participation in this survey.

Section A: Demographic Information

1. Gender.

- Male
- Female
- Other

2. Age bracket.

- 20-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60+

3. Marital status:

- Married
- Unmarried
- Engaged

4. Highest degree/certificate achieved:

- M.Phil/Doctorate
- MA/Msc
- BA/Bsc
- FA/Fsc

5. What is your current Profession?

- Working in another school
- Joined another profession
- Unemployed

6. How long did you teach in your previous school (*in case of more than one previous school, the latest will be considered*)?
7. What was/were the primary subject(s) you were teaching in the previous school?

Section B: Turnover Factors

8. Was teaching your career aspiration before you enter the profession?
 - Yes
 - No
9. What was/were the reason(s) to join teaching as a career?
10. Do you think that recognition (pay rise, bonuses, awards etc.,) is/was important to motivate you as a teacher? Why do you think this way?
11. Do you think salary is important in your decision to stay or leave the job? How?
12. School characteristics (facilities, progression, supportive climate etc.) play important role for teachers in career decisions. What were the school characteristics that affected your decision to leave the job? (please specify any two).
13. What one thing made it difficult for you to stay in previous job?
14. What does your new job offer that your previous job/school did not?
15. What prompted you to seek an alternative job/school?
16. What one thing you think the previous school could have done to make you feel satisfied and stay?
17. If you could change one thing in previous school, what it would be?
18. Would you like to give some recommendation on how the turnover of teachers can be reduced?

APPENDIX 5: Types & Levels of Schools in Pakistan

Types of schools

(Source: self-made)

APPENDIX 6: Regional Distribution of Out-of-School Children in Pakistan

(source: Alif Ailaan, 2014)

APPENDIX 7: Ethical Approval Letter

21/09/2017

Dear Salma Nazim,

Your application 0963: Study of Factors behind Teachers' Turnover in Pakistan, submission 836, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr A Kourouklis

Chair of SEC